

Towards more Earthquake-resilient Urban Societies through a Multi-sensor-based Information System enabling Earthquake Forecasting, Early Warning and Rapid Response actions

TURNkey

Deliverable D 4.8

Report on procedures for rapid mapping of earthquake losses

Author(s):	Pierre Gehl, Rosemary Fayjaloun, Caterina Negulescu, Samuel Auclair, Agathe Roullé (BRGM) Enrico Tubaldi, Ekin Özer (UStr) Dina D'Ayala, Li Sun (UCL) Sergio Molina, Alireza Kharazian (UA) Barbara Borzi, Francesca Bozzoni, Antonella Di Meo, Marta Faravelli, Ali Ozcebe (EUC) Atefe Darzi, Bjarni Besson, Benedikt (Ulce) Nooshin Hadidian, Melad Haweyou, Lars Abrahamczyk, Jochen Schwarz (BUW)
Responsible Partner:	BRGM
Version:	1.1
Date:	12/10/2021

Reviewers	Abdelghani Meslem (NOR), Alexandru Tiganescu (INFP)
Distribution level:	Public

DOCUMENT REVISION HISTORY

Date	Version	Editor	Comments
30/09/2021	1.0	First Draft	
12/10/2021	1.1	BUW	

LIST OF PARTNERS

Participant	Name	Country
NOR	Stiftelsen NORSAR	Norway
DEL	Stichting Deltares	Netherlands
KNMI	Koninklijk Nederlands Meteorologisch Instituut	Netherlands
BRGM	Bureau de Recherches Géologiques et Minières	France
EMSC	Euro-Mediterranean Seismological Centre	France
UIce	Haskoli Islands (University of Iceland)	Iceland
EUC	Fondazione Eucentre	Italy
UStr	University of Strathclyde	UK
BUW	Bauhaus-Universität Weimar	Germany
UA	Universidad de Alicante	Spain
ARU	Anglia Ruskin University Higher Education Corporation	UK
UNIBG	Università degli Studi di Bergamo	Italy
UCL	University College London	UK
INFP	Institutul National de Cercetare si Dezvoltare pentru Fizica Pamantului	Romania
YET	YetItMoves S.r.l.	Italy
GMP	Gempa GmbH	Germany
NOA	National Observatory of Athens	Greece
NTC	Nutcracker Research Ltd.	UK
B80	Beta 80 SpA	Italy
Sim	Siminn hf.	Iceland
UPat	Panepistimio Patron (University of Patras)	Greece

GLOSSARY

Acronym	Description
BN	Bayesian Network
DPM	Damage Probability Matrix
EMS	European Macroseismic Scale
GMICE	Ground-Motion Intensity Conversion Equation
GMM	Ground-Motion Model
IM	Intensity Measure
PGA	Peak Ground Acceleration
RRE	Rapid Response to Earthquakes
VC	Vulnerability Class

INDEX OF CONTENTS

Document revision history	2
List of partners	2
Glossary.....	3
Index of contents	i
Index of figures	iv
Index of tables	ix
1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	1
2 INTRODUCTION	2
3 STATE-OF-THE-ART OF SYSTEMS FOR RAPID LOSS MAPPING	4
3.1 Damage assessment algorithms.....	4
3.1.1 Assessment of damage to buildings and infrastructure components	4
3.1.2 Assessment of human losses	6
3.2 RRE systems providing loss estimates.....	8
3.2.1 RRE systems directly based on shake-maps	8
3.2.1.1 USGS PAGER system.....	8
3.2.1.2 USGS ShakeCast system	8
3.2.1.3 GDACS	9
3.2.1.4 SeiSDaRo.....	9
3.2.1.5 ELER.....	9
3.2.1.6 SEISAID	9
3.2.2 RRE systems not based on shake-maps	10
3.2.2.1 QLARM.....	10
3.2.2.2 SIGE-DPC	11
3.2.2.3 Italian railway network system	11
3.2.2.4 Earthquake Qualitative Impact Assessment (EQIA).....	11
3.2.2.5 The TELES system.....	12
3.2.2.6 Japanese systems READY and SUPREME.....	12
3.2.2.7 The Earthquake-Report platform	12
3.2.2.8 ISAR system	12
3.3 Summary of rapid loss assessment systems and suggested advances	13
4 BENCHMARK STUDY OF DAMAGE ESTIMATION METHODS.....	17
4.1 Luchon Valley (TB-2) case-study.....	17
4.1.1 Hazard description.....	18

4.1.2	Choice of the vulnerability indices and fragility curve parameters	19
4.1.2.1	Expert-based choice	19
4.1.2.2	Application of knowledge-based exposure modelling framework.....	21
4.1.3	Damage comparison and conclusions.....	23
4.1.3.1	Results from Expert-based choice	23
4.1.3.2	Results from Knowledge-based exposure modelling framework.....	23
4.1.3.3	Comparison of results	33
4.2	Alicante Case study	36
4.2.1	Hazard description.....	36
4.2.2	Expert-based choice of the vulnerability indices and fragility curve parameters	38
4.2.3	Damage comparison and conclusions.....	40
5	SENSITIVITY OF EARTHQUAKE DAMAGE ESTIMATION TO THE INPUT DATA	42
5.1	Study in TB-2 (Luchon Valley, France): Influence of the resolution of soil amplification maps and building exposure datasets	42
5.1.1	Scenarios and methodology.....	44
5.1.2	Scenario results	49
5.1.2.1	Damage estimation for uniform ground acceleration ($PGA = 200 \text{ cm/s}^2$ on rock conditions).....	49
5.1.2.2	Application to two historical earthquakes	54
5.1.3	Impact on the use of damage scenarios for earthquake crisis management.....	57
5.2	Study in TB-3 (Hveragerði, Iceland): Scenario-based seismic loss estimation accounting for ground motion variability	59
5.2.1	Building exposure dataset.....	60
5.2.2	Intensity measures variability across Hveragerði	62
5.2.2.1	Overall variability of IMs.....	62
5.2.3	Spatial variability of IMs through Kriging analyses.....	63
5.2.4	Seismic loss estimation.....	66
5.2.4.1	Results and Discussion.....	68
5.2.5	Application of knowledge-based exposure modelling framework.....	70
6	NEAR REAL-TIME SEISMIC LOSS ASSESSMENT OF STRUCTURES	76
6.1	Introduction.....	76
6.2	Seismic damage assessment.....	78
6.2.1	Seismic shaking analysis	78
6.2.2	Structural analysis.....	79
6.2.2.1	Peak transient displacements	80

6.2.2.2	Residual displacements	81
6.2.2.3	Peak absolute accelerations	81
6.2.3	Damage analysis	81
6.2.4	Loss analysis	82
6.3	Bayesian framework.....	82
6.3.1	Bayesian network	82
6.3.2	Quantification of sensors' effectiveness for uncertainty reduction	85
6.3.2.1	Pre-posterior variance	85
6.3.2.2	Reduction of relative entropy.....	86
6.4	Case-study	87
6.4.1	Case-study description	87
6.4.1.1	Structural system model for damage and loss assessment	87
6.4.1.2	Seismic scenarios and field observations	92
6.4.2	Rapid damage assessment for a single scenario.....	94
6.4.3	Quantification of uncertainty reduction	97
6.5	Conclusion and future work	99
7	RAPID EARTHQUAKE LOSS UPDATING OF SYSTEMS VIA A BAYESIAN APPROACH	101
7.1	Introduction.....	101
7.2	Proposed approach to update losses from observations	104
7.2.1	Main principles of the loss updating procedure	104
7.2.2	Road network processing	106
7.2.3	Proposed BN modelling.....	107
7.2.4	Definition of prior distributions.....	109
7.3	Numerical verification of the sampling algorithm.....	110
7.3.1	Definition of the synthetic system.....	111
7.3.2	Verification method	111
7.3.3	Results	114
7.4	Application to a real-world road network.....	117
7.4.1	Description of the case-study area.....	117
7.4.2	Construction of the BN model.....	119
7.5	Results and discussion.....	121
7.5.1	Checking the accuracy of the updated ground-motion field	121
7.5.2	Influence of the correlation assumptions on the results.....	123
7.6	Conclusions	127

8 CONCLUSIONS	128
REFERENCES	130

INDEX OF FIGURES

Figure 3-1: Summary of rapid loss estimation systems.....	14
Figure 4-1: Left - Luchon Valley (TB-2). Left: Case study location in the Pyrenees mountain range; Right: 53 municipalities in Luchon Valley. In the Armagedom software, the projection of the project is EPSG:32621 (WGS84/UTM Zone 31N). The Grid cell of the reference raster is 20m.	17
Figure 4-2: Acceleration values (PGA in mg) per municipality. PGA values are estimated at the centroids of polygons/geocodes.	19
Figure 4-3: Method to associate the SERA taxonomies and the RISK-UE taxonomies.....	20
Figure 4-4: Assignment of fragility functions to Luchon Valley area.....	22
Figure 4-5: Damage degrees computed with SELENA and Armagedom for Luchon Valley Case Study; Left: using the soil acceleration and the GMICE by Atkinson and Sonley (2000); Right: using the soil acceleration and the GMICE by Faenza and Michelini (2010).....	23
Figure 4-6: Distribution of buildings types according to approach M2-TX-ST and the most likely vulnerability classes for Luchon Valley.....	24
Figure 4-7: Distribution of damage grades in the level of municipalities, Luchon, TB-2: Approach M2-TX-ST, I _{EMS} = VIII.	25
Figure 4-8: Percentage of damage distribution per determined scenario in Luchon considering I _{EMS} = VIII, approach M2-TX-ST.....	26
Figure 4-9: Comparison of damage distributions between five scenarios approach M2-TX-ST (I _{EMS} = VIII).....	27
Figure 4-10: Distribution of buildings types according to approach M2-TX-ST* and the most likely vulnerability classes for Luchon Valley.....	29
Figure 4-11: Distribution of damage grades in the level of municipalities, Luchon, TB-2: approach M2-TX-ST*, I _{EMS} = VIII.....	30
Figure 4-12: Percentage of damage distribution per determined scenario in Luchon considering I _{EMS} =VIII, Approach M2-TX-ST*.....	31

Figure 4-13: Comparison of damage distributions between five scenarios for whole Luchon area, approach M2-TX-ST* ($I_{EMS} = VIII$).....32

Figure 4-14: Comparison of damage distribution between M1-TX and M2-TX-ST methods.....33

Figure 4-15: Comparison of damage distributions between the two approaches (M2-TX-ST from Figure 4-9, M2-TX-ST* from Figure 4-13) and the results from SELENA and Armagedom (from Figure 4-5).....34

Figure 4-16: Comparison of damage distribution results from M1-TX (from Figure 4-14) , SELENA and Armagedom (from Figure 4-5).....35

Figure 4-17: Name and location of the municipalities for the area of interest. In the Armagedom software, the projection of the project is EPSG:25830 (ETRS89_UTM_zone_30N). The Grid cell of the reference raster is 50m.....36

Figure 4-18: Intensity map (left) and PGA map (right) calculated by SELENA software, for the 1829 Torre Vieja earthquake.....37

Figure 4-19: Intensity map calculated by Armagedom software using the simulated PGA values; Left: conversion with Atkinson and Sonley (2000) GMICE; Right: conversion with Faenza and Michelini (2010) GMICE.....38

Figure 4-20: Damage degrees computed with SELENA and Armagedom; Top: using the soil acceleration and the GMICE by Faenza and Michelini (2010); Bottom: using directly the intensity values.....40

Figure 4-21: Buildings with Extensive Damages; Left: SELENA software; Right: Armagedom software.....41

Figure 5-1: Left: Map of the Luchon Valley and the 53 municipalities; Right: location of the Luchon area overlaid with the French seismic zonation.....42

Figure 5-2: The site characterization maps and the building exposure used for the three scale scenarios defined in this study.....46

Figure 5-3: Pie charts of the distribution of soil characterization classes in urbanized areas for the three defined scale scenarios.....47

Figure 5-4: The damage distribution per scale scenario considering the ground motion amplification due to soil effects. The colour shows the percentage of buildings per level of damage. The number shows the total number of damaged buildings.....50

Figure 5-5: The damage distribution per scale scenario considering the ground motion amplification due to soil effects. The colour shows the percentage of buildings per level of damage. The number shows the total number of damaged buildings.51

Figure 5-6: Percentage of damage degree superior to D3 for scenario SS3 for PGA of 200 cm/s² amplified by the site effects: representation to the level of the municipality and to the infra-municipality level (homogeneous vulnerability census block).53

Figure 5-7: The damage distribution per municipality (last bar chart of each graphic) and per corresponding homogeneous vulnerability census blocks inside each municipality.53

Figure 5-8: The ground motion corresponding to the earthquakes of 1855 (Left) and 1923 (Right). The first row (a and b) shows the ground motion computed at rock site conditions with the GMM by Ambraseys et al. (2005). The surface ground motion is amplified due to the soil effect using SS1 (c and d), SS2 (e and f) and SS3 (g and h) soil characterization maps.....55

Figure 5-9: D3 damage distribution in the Luchon Valley area in number of buildings, at the 53 municipalities, due to the 1855 earthquake. The site effect is considered here.56

Figure 5-10: D3 damage distribution in the Luchon area in number of buildings at the 53 municipalities, due to the 1923 earthquake. The site effect is considered here.57

Figure 5-11: Left panel: Number of buildings in Hveragerði classified by their construction material. Right panel: percentages of buildings classified by their occupancy.61

Figure 5-12: Spatial distribution of buildings in Hveragerði over its respective street map classified by year of construction along with their corresponding histogram of number of buildings. ICEARRAY-I stations are plotted by black triangles over the Hveragerði town.....61

Figure 5-13: Mean (black dashed line) and standard deviation (grey area) of spectral acceleration with 5% damping ratio corresponding to two horizontal components of N-S (a) and E-W (b), and the Average Rotation-Invariant (c) of the two components, determined using the ICEARRAY-I recordings of the May 2008 earthquake.....63

Figure 5-14: The Kriged IM shake-maps, along with the uncertainty maps, for PGA, and SAs at T = 0.2 s across Hveragerði. The rotation-invariant average (ARI) horizontal component is used for Kriging geostatistical analysis. Buildings are colour coded by their construction year. Triangles indicate the ICEARRAY-I stations.....64

Figure 5-15: Kriged shake maps for SAs at $T = 0.65$ (top), and 2 s (bottom) across Hveragerði obtained for two horizontal accelerograms of x (N-S direction, left-side panels) and y (E-W direction, right-side panels).....66

Figure 5-16: a) Mean damage ratio for eight building typologies predicted using MS20 fragility models, in classical municipality level (orange bars) and high-resolution of building-by-building (blue bars), along with its 84th and 16th percentiles (grey transparent bars). b) MDR for three building classes, predicted by MS20 fragility models and their comparison with corresponding values obtained from the Bea20 local loss model.69

Figure 5-17: The lower and upper bounds of MDR estimates for eight building typologies predicted using MS20 fragility models, accounting for ground shaking intensity variability (first row) and monetary value (second row) Application of knowledge-based exposure modelling framework70

Figure 5-18: Mean damage grade distribution and its portion regarding to the building typology71

Figure 5-19: Comparison of mean damage grade distribution between assigned VC scenarios, Hveragerdi, using building stock before 2008 for EQ in 2008.73

Figure 5-20: Mean damage grade distribution using VC scenarios for Hveragerdi, EQ 2008 ...74

Figure 5-21: Comparison of mean damage grade distribution between scenarios regarding to the building typologies using M2-TX-ST* for TB-3, Hveragerdi, EQ 2008.....75

Figure 6-1: Illustration of the bilinear regression model.80

Figure 6-2: Bayesian network illustrating the relationship between the parameters involved in the damage and loss assessment (observed quantities indicated with thick lines).83

Figure 6-3: a) Two-span bridge profile, b) transverse deck section (source Tubaldi et al., 2013).88

Figure 6-4: a) Base moment-curvature response and b) Base shear-top displacement response.88

Figure 6-5: Sample values and model results in terms of RD, TD, and PA vs. IM in the log-log plane (left column) and in the natural plane (right column).....90

Figure 6-6: Map with indications of bridge site, seismic point sources for Scenario 1 and 2, and seismic stations.....93

Figure 6-7: Empirical cumulative distribution function (CDF) of the parameters of interest before and after updating with observations from Scenario 1.94

Figure 6-8: Empirical cumulative distribution function (CDF) of the parameters of interest before and after updating with observations from Scenario 2.96

Figure 6-9: Evolution with the number of samples of the monitoring effectiveness measure based on pre-posterior variance for the various parameters of interest and observation sources (Scenario 1).97

Figure 7-1: Proof-of-concept of the procedure for the rapid earthquake loss assessment of built areas and infrastructure systems. 105

Figure 7-2: Illustration of the construction of a Super-Network from a physical network. 106

Figure 7-3: Proposed BN formulation for a system decomposed into MLSs and for built areas... 108

Figure 7-4: Gaussian BN used for the numerical verification on the synthetic example. Red circles represent nodes that are evidenced (see Section 7.3.3)..... 113

Figure 7-5: (a) Prior distribution of D_i ; (b) Truncated and normalized distribution of D_i ; (c) Discretized weights applied to the decomposition. 114

Figure 7-6: OpenBUGS model for scenario 2. Observations (evidence) are the quantities $Dobs$ and $IMobs$ 115

Figure 7-7: Top left: posterior distributions of variables IM_2 and C_2 , in terms of 16th, 50th and 84th percentiles, with evidence $IM_3 = im_3$ and $DS_2 = 1$; Top right: posterior distributions of variables IM_2 and C_2 , in terms of 16th, 50th and 84th percentiles, with evidence $IM_3 = im_3$ and $DS_2 = 0$; Bottom: Error rate between the Gaussian BN and OpenBUGS estimates. 116

Figure 7-8: Situation map of the Luchon case-study area..... 118

Figure 7-9: Construction of the Super-Network from the physical network..... 120

Figure 7-10: Summary of the identified MLSs and location of the observations. 120

Figure 7-11: Histograms of the error rate of the mean and standard deviation of the posterior IM distribution at the various sites, with respect to the analytical solution, for various lengths of the MCMC chains. 122

Figure 7-12: Left: prior distribution using only the characteristics of the earthquake event; Right: posterior distribution using field observations (with *Corr3* model)..... 124

Figure 7-13: Top: prior mean of μ_D (mean damage grade) of the built areas; Bottom: posterior distribution using field observations (with *Corr3* model). 124

Figure 7-14: Posterior standard-deviation $\sigma_{\log PGA}$ of the IMs at the locations of interest (with *Corr3* model)..... 125

Figure 7-15: Updating of the seismic response of bridges, based on damage observations... 126

INDEX OF TABLES

Table 3-1: Input data and expected outputs for the studied loss assessment systems..... 13

Table 4-1: Name and identifier of the 53 municipalities from Luchon Valley case-study..... 18

Table 4-2: Vulnerability index V_i for the 53 municipalities in Luchon Valley. 20

Table 4-3: Definition of scenarios according to concept of approach M2-TX-ST for Luchon..... 24

Table 4-4: Definition of scenarios according to the concept of approach M2-TX-ST* for Luchon. 28

Table 4-5: UA Taxonomy type and equivalence with SERA and RISK-UE taxonomies and vulnerability index..... 38

Table 5-1: Scale scenario description based on the source of databases to characterize the site amplification as well as the building exposure. 46

Table 5-2: Building exposure data (number of buildings and the average vulnerability index) by municipality in the Luchon Valley area, extracted from the three databases used for this study. 47

Table 5-3: Parameters of the 1855 and 1923 historical earthquakes that affected the region of Luchon Valley, from the FCAT-17 parametric catalogue (Manchuel et al., 2017). 54

Table 5-4: Percentage and number of residential buildings per damage level per scale scenario and the corresponding ground motion shown in Figure 5-8, for the earthquake event of 1855. 55

Table 5-5: Percentage and number of residential buildings per damage level per scale scenario and the corresponding ground motion shown in Figure 5-8, for the earthquake event of 1923. 56

Table 5-6: Examples of damage scenarios that need to be related to crisis management activities, with qualitative assessment of corresponding required level of reliability..... 58

Table 5-7: Building typologies for residential buildings in Hveragerði according to the SERA taxonomy system. 67

Table 5-8: Assigned fragility functions to building types in TB-3.....	71
Table 5-9: Assigned vulnerability classes for building stock in Hveragerdi, Iceland using Annex 4.2 in D4.1.	72
Table 5-10: Defined criteria to relate damage grade and damage ratio (Maiwald & Schwarz, 2020).....	75
Table 6-1: Engineering demand parameters and measurement possibilities.	80
Table 6-2: Median and lognormal standard deviation of prior and posterior distribution of parameters of interest for a realization from Scenario 1.	95
Table 6-3: Median and lognormal standard deviation of prior and posterior distribution of parameters of interest for a realization from Scenario 2.	97
Table 6-4: Pre-posterior variance-based effectiveness measure for estimation of various parameters of interest.....	99
Table 6-5: Reduction of relative entropy-based effectiveness measure for estimation of various parameters of interest.....	99
Table 7-1: Posterior distributions of the variables of interest, for the two evidence scenarios. Observed values are in bold font. C_2 and IM_2 are expressed in $\log_{10} \text{ m/s}^2$	115
Table 7-2: Results of the Bayesian updating, in terms of probability of disconnection between points A and B (i.e., $S = 0$) and of identification of the “best” MLS, for the various correlation assumptions.	123

1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report details the procedures that have been applied, developed or improved in Task 4.5 for the rapid estimation of damages and losses after an earthquake event. The report revolves around several actions and technical results, which are organized as follows:

- Section 3 summarizes the state-of-the-art of current rapid response algorithms and systems, based on a review by [Guérin-Marthe et al. \(2021\)](#). The SELENA and Armagedom software, coupled with shake-map estimates from WP3, are put forward as one of the technical solutions to be implemented in the TURNkey platform.
- Section 4 conducts a benchmark study of two damage estimation methods, namely SELENA ([Molina et al., 2010](#)), using fragility functions, and Armagedom ([Sedan et al., 2013](#)), using semi-empirical vulnerability indices. Both methods are applied on two case-study areas (Luchon area in TB-2 and Alicante area) and the damage distributions are compared.
- Section 5 investigates the impact of various factors (resolution of soil amplification maps and building exposure datasets, influence of ground-motion variability) on the accuracy of the damage estimates when applying earthquake scenarios over built areas. Two case studies are considered, namely the Luchon area (TB-2) and the town of Hveragerði (TB-3).
- Section 6 introduces a probabilistic framework for near real-time seismic damage assessment that exploits heterogeneous sources of information about the seismic input and the structural response to the earthquake. The value of information provided by various combinations of observations and measurements is quantified. The approach is applied to an arbitrary roadway bridge near Patras (TB-4).
- Section 7 introduces a sampling-based Bayesian updating method in order to refine damage and loss estimates from field observations. The method is applicable to large real-world systems, such as extended built areas or real-world infrastructure systems. It is applied to the Luchon area (TB-2), where the damage distribution of common buildings and the connectivity loss of the road network system are estimated in a rapid response context.

The Bayesian approach for the updating of damage and loss estimated has been implemented in a R/Matlab code, which is briefly described in the companion Deliverable D4.9.

2 INTRODUCTION

Work conducted in WP3 has led to the development of methods to derive an updated spatial field of ground-motion parameters (i.e., shake-maps) right after the earthquake event. These shake-maps may in turn be used as an input to damage and loss assessment software, provided that exposure or vulnerability models are available for the affected area. This chain of tools and calculations, from acquiring seismic data to assessing the damages and losses, constitutes the backbone of Rapid Response to Earthquake (RRE) systems. The most pressing need is to optimize the resources available, allocating them strategically on the affected territories for an optimal response to the earthquake. Emergency systems must also be triggered in order to avoid secondary risks linked to transportations, or gas and oil lines, prioritizing inspection, shutting them off when needed, and letting them run when possible, in order to facilitate rescue operations.

The literature review by [Guérin-Marthe et al. \(2021\)](#), which focused partly on the analysis of existing tools for the rapid estimation of damage and losses, has identified several recommendations and gaps that should be addressed:

- Spatial scale of the analysis: while some systems provide a picture of the potential impact at the level of the whole earthquake event (useful information for sizing the disaster and for deciding the level of support required), specific emergency response needs a detailed account of the situation at the local level (e.g., level of city district or building block).
- Scope of the analysis: most rapid loss assessment systems are based on predicting damage to common buildings, while only a few of them include infrastructure components or critical facilities. Moreover, none of the current systems consider yet the effect of failed components on the global performance of the infrastructure, which has a great influence on the crisis management operations (e.g., inaccessible roads, power outage, disrupted water supply).
- Nature of the analysis: most tools perform deterministic assessments of the losses, starting from best estimates of the ground shaking and directly applying damage estimation models. Adopting a probabilistic framework, where all sources of uncertainties (e.g., shake-map outcomes, variability in the vulnerability and fragility models) are propagated, would guarantee a transparent process, while leaving the possibility to refine the loss estimates as more evidence from the field is gathered.

Therefore, the present report aims at addressing and investigating some of the identified shortcomings, namely:

- The comparative analysis of existing systems with complementary damage estimation methods, such as SELENA ([Molina et al., 2010](#)) and Armagedom ([Sedan et al., 2013](#)), as detailed in Section 4.
- The integration of various sources of uncertainty, whether they are due to the estimation of ground shaking, the spatial resolution of the building exposure dataset or the variability in the fragility models (cf. Sections 5 and 7).
- The integration of various sources of field observations and measurements and the quantification of their impact on uncertainties, through Value of Information studies (cf. Section 6).

- The estimation of losses sustained by infrastructure systems, with the generation of performance indicators at the system level, such as the connectivity of a road network (cf. Section 7).

Based on a Bayesian updating approach, the main product of Section 7 is an algorithm that generates GIS layers on the fly to represent building and infrastructure component damage distributions, functional and systemic loss distributions and causality estimates. The related code is briefly described in the companion Deliverable D4.9.

3 STATE-OF-THE-ART OF SYSTEMS FOR RAPID LOSS MAPPING

This section summarizes the review of current RRE systems performed by [Guérin-Marthe et al. \(2021\)](#), with a focus on the damage and loss assessment part. It constitutes an update of the review that has been initiated in TURNkey Deliverable D3.1 ([Azarbakht et al., 2020](#)).

The following sub-sections present the main types of damage and loss assessment algorithms, and the current modules and systems in which they are used, before analysing current gaps and identifying potential measures for improvement.

3.1 Damage assessment algorithms

Physical damage and loss assessment software in an earthquake rapid response context need to be quick enough to deliver first estimates, and they should be able to cover potentially large built areas. There are several types of damage assessment algorithms, as detailed in [Calvi et al. \(2006\)](#). Some of them are based on empirical methods, others on analytical methods that involve mechanical considerations, and finally they can be hybrid and built on a combination of analytical and empirical basis. The sub-sections below list the main algorithm types.

3.1.1 Assessment of damage to buildings and infrastructure components

First, the Damage Probability Matrices (DPM) initially proposed by [Whitman et al. \(1997\)](#) express how likely a discrete level of ground-motion intensity is to generate a given level of damage. The likelihoods are reported in the form of tables crossing the discrete ground-motion and damage levels.

The Vulnerability Index Method (e.g. [Benedetti and Petrini, 1984](#)) uses various building characteristics affecting its stability (e.g. state of conservation, type of materials, floor configuration), it assigns a qualification coefficient to them (from optimal to unfavourable), weighted by the relative importance of the criterion, and it eventually returns a global index reflecting the building vulnerability. This method relies mostly on expert judgment ([Calvi et al. 2006](#)).

Others methods are based on continuous Fragility Curves, which represent an improvement compared to the discrete levels considered in the DPMs. VCs relate a ground-motion parameter (PGA, macroseismic intensity or spectral acceleration or displacement) to the probability of reaching a given damage state (D1 to D5 in the EMS-98 scale, [Grünthal \(1998\)](#)).

Although the aforementioned methods are mostly empirically derived, some part of the DPMs can sometimes make use of non-linear dynamic models of different building classes ([Kappos et al., 1995](#)) for instance, and computer simulations can also be used to complete vulnerability functions ([Barbat et al., 1996](#)). Such methods can be qualified as “hybrid”.

On the analytical side, we can distinguish three main types of methods: collapse mechanism based, capacity spectrum based and fully-displacement based.

The collapse mechanism based methods use so-called collapse multipliers to evaluate if a structure will collapse, based on mechanical principles. VULNUS ([Bernardini, 2000](#)) and FaMIVE ([D'Ayala and Speranza, 2002](#)) are two examples of these methods.

Capacity Spectrum Methods ([Freeman, 1998](#)) rather examine the deformation of a building subject to increasing lateral forces (pushover curve). Ground motion is characterized by spectral response, generally based on a standard spectrum shape. The spatial distribution of ground motion can be determined using either deterministic ground motion analysis,

probabilistic ground motion maps or user-supplied maps. The elastic response spectrum is reduced in order to consider the non-linear behaviour of the buildings when it goes beyond their elastic limits ((hysteretic energy dissipated). Different methods can be used for reducing the elastic response spectrum, mostly based on two principles: (i) the use of overdamped elastic spectrum in Freeman's approach obtained via an additional equivalent viscous damping ratio related to the hysteretic capacity of the system or (ii) the use the inelastic spectra in Fajfar's approach obtained via the behaviour factor which is based on the ductility of the structure. Generally, an iterative procedure is implemented for determining the performance point, in order to ensure the compatibility between the reduced demand spectrum with the capacity spectrum, and the level of non-linearity of the structure. The last methods are the fully Displacement-Based methods (Calvi, 1999). In the latter, only the comparison between displacement capacity and displacement demand is considered.

Most of the current modules able to perform damage estimation have been reviewed in Erdik et al. (2011) and in Makhoul and Argyroudis (2018), a software inventory that comprises the characteristics of around 50 packages. Here, we list the most common tools that enable the use of ground motion estimates and of exposure and vulnerability maps to assess the level of damage and loss at different levels of resolution. They have originally been developed for the computation of prospective damage scenarios at city, regional or national scale in preparedness and mitigation phases; therefore, their application is suitable for near-real-time computations in a RRE context.

ELER's routine (Zülfikar et al., 2017) is a capacity spectrum based method that performs loss estimation (building damage, casualties, economic loss), and that uses building inventories (type, height and year) for the vulnerability assessment. At a high-resolution level, the damage on buildings and associated uncertainties are evaluated using spectral displacement-based analytical vulnerability relationships (Hancilar et al., 2010).

SELENA (Molina et al., 2010), is another capacity spectrum based method, where the vulnerability is assessed based on the spectral parameters (acceleration and displacement), and the ground motion estimates are provided using deterministic or probabilistic analysis, including site-effects. The uncertainties may be computed via a logic-tree and a Monte Carlo approach.

In DBELA (Displacement Based Earthquake Loss Assessment, Crowley et al., 2006) and SP-BELA (Simplified Pushover-Based Earthquake Loss Assessment - Borzi et al., 2008), the vulnerability of the building is determined based on mechanical principles. While DBELA is a fully displacement-based method, SP-BELA uses a simplified technique in order to reduce the computational cost. It has been implemented essentially in regions with European/Mediterranean types of buildings.

We also mention here the Armagedom software (Sedan et al., 2013), which follows the RISK-UE methodology (Milutinovic and Trendafiloski, 2003), and uses a mix of the methods discussed above to perform loss assessment. The building typology is inspired by the EMS-98 classes as defined in Grünthal (1998) and refined with sub-typologies. The basic analysis level is an empirical method (namely LM1 in RISK-UE) and is derived from the work of Giovinazzi and Lagomarsino (2004), where vulnerability indices are assigned to the different building types. The second analysis level (LM2) is an analytical method similar to HAZUS 99 (FEMA, 2003), where each building class is assigned a capacity curve. The performance of the building in response to the seismic demand is then assessed using the capacity spectrum method.

Lestuzzi et al. (2016) applied the RISK-UE methodology (both the empirical method LM1 and the mechanical method LM2) to the building stock of two cities, namely Sion and Martigny, located within the highest seismic zone of Switzerland. They conclude that for qualitative analysis, both methods are able to identify the most vulnerable parts of a city, as well as which one is most vulnerable among a group of investigated cities. They discuss the pros and cons of each level and recommend carefully interpreting the quantitative results for both levels. Finally, the OpenQuake platform (Silva et al., 2012 - www.globalquakemodel.org/openquake), which has been developed from an initiative of the Global Earthquake Model (GEM), provides a free, open-source software for the assessment of earthquake hazard and risk. OpenQuake contains an integrated hazard module, which can perform a wide range of computations (e.g., probabilistic hazard assessment, earthquake scenarios, seismic source disaggregation) along with the treatment of uncertainties via logic trees. Similarly, the risk module offers a variety of features, such as scenario-based damage/risk assessment, classical probabilistic damage/risk analysis or stochastic event-based damage/risk analysis. Inputs for the damage assessment step consist in exposure models (i.e., GEM building taxonomy) in terms of built areas or single assets. Fragility models are then applied to estimate damage distribution. In the end, vulnerability functions may also be applied in order to provide various types of loss measures (e.g., replacement costs, casualties, etc.).

Regarding infrastructure components several studies introducing algorithms for damage and loss assessment are available, such as:

- port infrastructure (Bozzoni et al., 2018; Conca et al., 2020),
- road networks (Di Meo et al., 2018),
- airports (Bozzoni et al., 2020),
- embankment dams (Bozzoni and Lai, 2017).

3.1.2 Assessment of human losses

Experience shows that after destructive earthquakes, it often takes many hours, or even days, to gain a realistic view of the overall magnitude of human tolls (Tang et al., 2019). From a disaster management point of view, the indicators related to human losses are therefore particularly useful during the first hours after the occurrence of a strong earthquake, because they can allow a better dimensioning and a better allocation of resources for search and rescue activities, as well as for assistance to the population. Unfortunately, relatively little work has been devoted to the issue of estimating human impacts to date, and the models used often lack high-quality data for calibration. Using the classification proposed by Maqsood and Schwarz (2011), methodologies for human losses assessment can be classified into five levels of increasing complexity:

- Level 1: empirical definition of loss rate as a function of an IM value (e.g., PAGER empirical model - Jaiswal et al., 2011);
- Level 2: improvement of level 1 by taking into account the building stock by rough typologies and the resident population (e.g., PAGER semi-empirical model - Jaiswal and Wald, 2010);
- Level 3: taking into account the levels of expected damage to buildings and empirical losses rates (Cousins et al., 1998);

- Level 4: improvement of level 3 by taking into account the structural vulnerability of the building stock (e.g., PAGER analytical model - [Porter et al., 2008](#); HAZUS - [FEMA, 2003](#));
- Level 5: improvement of level 4 by taking into account temporal variations in the exposure of populations.

From level 3 and upwards, it is possible to use the results of the building damage assessment models (see Section 3.1.1) to deduce probable human losses associated to the level of physical damage to structures and to the occupation of buildings, for example by using a casualties matrix such as the one proposed by [Coburn and Spence \(1992\)](#). [Spence \(2007\)](#) has also updated the previous casualties matrix by proposing injury distributions for specific building types. Note that while linear models are the most used methods for assessing feature correlation, [Jia et al. \(2019\)](#) recently proposed an integrated ensemble model established using deep-learning techniques, by considering nine different predictive features.

Other models offer a much more detailed consideration of possible human losses as a function of their position within buildings and their actual exposure to failures of structural elements ([Hingorani et al., 2020](#)). However, applicability of such models to RREs systems remains challenging, because it requires a very refined modelling of the damages at the scale of each building considered individually and not statistically at the scale of building blocks.

Due to the many parameters that can directly influence the amount of human losses during an earthquake, the level of uncertainty on the predicted values is therefore high. With the notable exception of the study by [Gobbato et al. \(2014\)](#), very little work has been devoted to quantifying this uncertainty. However, it appears that one of the main avenues for improvement that can reduce this level of uncertainty is the development of level 5 models, explicitly taking into account the spatio-temporal modulations of population exposure, in, near and outside buildings.

Italian Risk Maps (IRMA; [Borzi et al., 2021](#)) is an innovative IT platform developed by EUCENTRE with funds of the Italian Civil Protection Department (DPC), and addressed to the scientific community. IRMA allows data sharing, methods and models aimed to evaluate the seismic risk of Italian residential buildings, in order to comply with the requirements of the "Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015–2030" (Sendai Framework). IRMA uses OpenQuake, a calculation engine developed as part of the Global Earthquake Model, to evaluate earthquake loss estimation. The user can create and upload different exposure/vulnerability databases as well as different sets of fragility curves on the platform. The hazard used in the platform is the hazard model, developed by National Institute of Geophysics and Volcanology, that is actually the reference hazard map for the Italian building code. IRMA is extremely flexible: by combining the different exposure databases with all the possible sets of fragility curves, the user can produce maps of conditional damage (i.e. the return period is selected) or unconditional damage (i.e. an observation time window is selected). Damage scenarios can also be performed by using shake-maps of seismic events as input. The shake-maps, preloaded in the platform, are those referred to the recent seismic events in Italy. IRMA was used in 2018 by DPC to produce the National Risk Assessment, in agreement with EU decision 1313/2013. After the first good experience with residential buildings, the DPC has commissioned also the development of tools for schools and churches within IRMA platform that will be enriched by other tools in the following years.

3.2 RRE systems providing loss estimates

This sub-section details some of the current systems for the estimation of damage and losses in a RRE context. The various existing RRE systems are discussed: a distinction is made between those that propose a direct and automated link between the shake-maps and a damage or loss estimation software, and those that rely on alternative approaches. A summary of the rapid damage and loss assessment systems is proposed in Table 3-1, and illustrated in Figure 3-1, with the required input data and the output format of each system.

3.2.1 RRE systems directly based on shake-maps

The following sub-sections provide a more detailed description of some of the most common RRE systems that use near real-time shake-maps as inputs.

3.2.1.1 USGS PAGER system

The PAGER (Prompt Assessment of Global Earthquakes for Response) system developed by the U.S. Geological Survey (USGS) constitutes a prime example of robust tools used for loss and damage estimation (Wald et al., 2010; Jaiswal et al., 2010). Immediately following the earthquake, updated ground-motions maps are provided by the USGS ShakeMap® system. They can then be combined with exposure and vulnerability for loss estimation. Global population databases provide the amount of people exposed to a given macroseismic intensity level, leading to the estimation of potential casualties and economic losses thanks to country-specific vulnerability and loss models (Jaiswal et al., 2010). The approach is empirical in developing regions having experienced an important number of damaging events. In highly developed countries, strong building codes and inventories enable the use of analytical methods, and semi-empirical solutions exist for regions corresponding to a mix of these end-members.

The use of global databases and models makes the PAGER system applicable worldwide, while its automated and fast execution is crucial for a timely sizing of the event and a triggering of appropriate response protocols. Like-country groups are used for the countries without loss data from past events. It does not use regional models as they tend not to be calibrated, particularly for fatalities which requires building inventories, collapse fragilities, occupancy and fatality rates to be approximately correct. Loss estimates are only based on empirical models while other estimates such as the distribution of impacted buildings make use of the other methods.

3.2.1.2 USGS ShakeCast system

ShakeCast (ShakeMap Broadcast: <http://usgs.github.io/shakecast> - Lin et al., 2018) is another similar fully-automated open-source system using ShakeMap® input, and HAZUS methodology (FEMA, 2003). Although HAZUS is the default methodology, the user can also specify the input such as fragility curves for buildings, bridges, etc. Shake-maps are applied to a list of critical and industrial facilities, for which a probability of damage is estimated through fragility curves. Alerts are broadcasted on a web interface, and sent by emails and texts to registered end-users, in order to be used for prioritizing inspection (green, yellow, orange or red).

3.2.1.3 GDACS

The PAGER tool providing casualties estimates is included in more general alert systems such as the Global Disaster Alert and Coordination System, GDACS (www.gdacs.org). GDACS is a cooperative framework between the United Nations and the European Union comprising and gathering the data and tools from several organizations: JRC (Joint Research Center of the European Commission) & INFORM (Index for Risk Management), NEIC (National Earthquake Information Center) & USGS, OCHA (UN Office of Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs), and INGV. Every five minutes, the data (earthquake magnitude, depth, location, population within 100 km, vulnerability) is obtained via web services, and a qualitative three-level alert is issued (green, orange or red), depending on the extent of the event (earthquake or other natural hazard) and the ability of the country to cope with it.

3.2.1.4 SeiSDaRo

In Romania, SeiSDaRo 3 (Toma-Danila et al., 2018) is a near-real-time system based on the PAGER methodology and the SELENA module. It is directly connected to a custom shake-map system (based on the ShakeMap® v3.5 approach) and it can deliver loss maps by running all of the system's modules in less than six minutes. First, global loss statistics from the event are generated from the PAGER methodology. Then, within a few minutes, a more detailed account of the earthquake's impact is made available, using the SELENA algorithm to estimate damages and losses.

3.2.1.5 ELER

Operational in the Istanbul area, this system (Zülfikar et al., 2017) uses the shake-maps generated by KOERI/RETMC, which are available within a few minutes after the event. The calculations of damage and loss are then performed on a grid using, in addition to the shake-map, exposure and vulnerability data. The grid-based building inventory was first compiled by using the year 2000 Turkish Statistical Institute (TUIK) Building Census (including information on the construction year, number of floors, and building construction type and the demographic data). In a second step of the project, a district-based building inventory of Istanbul was performed to complete the TUIK statistics and the final inventory was finalized into 0.005° grids by using 2008 building line geometries of 1/1000-scaled existing maps. The building damage is evaluated using the ELER methodology, and the loss estimation with the HAZUS-MH methodology (FEMA, 2003).

3.2.1.6 SEISAID

In France, the French Geological Survey (BRGM) has developed a rapid response system based on the PAGER approach (Auclair et al., 2014, 2015). Implemented in the whole French mainland territory, the SEISAID tool generates rapid shaking estimates and it projects population density data on seismic intensity levels, similarly to the PAGER approach. It permits to rapidly estimate the number of casualties and homeless people. Data from past French earthquakes and from most seismic scenarios have been used to calibrate the relation between the macroseismic intensity and the human losses. Currently, BRGM is upgrading the SEISAID system by

automatically connecting the shake-map outputs to the Armagedom software, in order to generate more accurate damage and loss scenarios in areas where vulnerability data is available.

Four versions are currently being finalized:

- Two "research driven" demonstrators (Auclair et al., 2019): one in the Pyrenean cross-border area between France, Spain and Andorra, and the other in Southeast of France (Bosco et al., 2019), which rely on a web service which, upon receipt of a shake-map, performs a rapid loss assessment, and delivers the results in PDF reports.
- Two "user driven" pre-operational systems ordered by the French authorities: one for the island of Mayotte (French overseas territory located in the Indian Ocean) and the other for the French West-Indies (French overseas territories located in the Pacific Ocean, including the islands of Martinique, Guadeloupe, Saint-Martin and Saint-Barthelemy). Already implemented since October 2019, the SEISaid-Mayotte system couples the creation of a Bayesian shake-map (Gehl et al., 2017) with the Armagedom loss assessment code. The results (i.e., number of casualties and injured people, and number of partially or totally collapsed buildings, at the scale of a municipality) are intended to be communicated via e-mail to civil protection services, a few minutes after the earthquake event.

3.2.2 RRE systems not based on shake-maps

In contrast with the above-detailed systems, the following sub-sections describe tools that do not directly rely on the outcomes of the shake-map systems: either they use specific earthquake scenarios without accounting for field observations or they directly estimate losses from the earthquake's characteristics.

3.2.2.1 QLARM

ICES Foundation (<http://www.icesfoundation.org/Pages/qlarmEventList.aspx>) provides loss estimates within less than 24 hours after a potentially damaging earthquake worldwide. This is done in partnership with the Swiss Seismological Service and eventually provides alert levels with the number of fatalities and the average damage of buildings. The software used is called QLARM for earthquake Loss Assessment Response (Trendafiloski et al., 2011). The ground shaking is estimated for each population settlement using the earthquake characteristics and a Vs30 map (based on the topography). The damage estimation is obtained using empirical relations derived from ~1000 earthquakes for which the losses were known. The percentage of population belonging to classes of vulnerability (definition of the classes based on the building type) is evaluated. The distribution of the population depending on the time of the event is also taken into account. The results are the percentage of buildings in each of the five defined damage states, as well as the number of fatalities and injured people in each settlement. Results are available on the ICES Foundation website, and they are automatically sent to the subscribers of the QLARM system.

3.2.2.2 SIGE-DPC

In Italy, an automatic procedure (SIGE - Information System for Emergency Management), activated by the Department of Civil Protection (DPC), uses the early characteristics of the earthquake event in order to estimate an expected distribution of structural damage and human casualties (Di Pasquale et al., 2005): however, interestingly, it appears that the shake-map step is bypassed, with no immediate use of measured or observed ground shaking in order to update intensity maps.

On the other hand, web-based GIS tools have been developed at EUCENTRE (European Centre for Training and Research in Earthquake Engineering) for the Italian DPC: they are aimed at developing near-real time damage scenarios for a wide range of exposed assets and systems, such as residential buildings (Faravelli et al., 2018), schools (Borzi et al., 2011a, 2011b), port infrastructure (Bozzoni et al., 2018), road networks (Di Meo et al., 2018), airports (Bozzoni et al., 2020) and embankment dams (Bozzoni and Lai, 2017). These tools can work also by using as input the shake-maps generated in the immediate aftermath of a seismic event by the National Institute of Geophysics and Volcanology (INGV).

3.2.2.3 Italian railway network system

In Italy, EUCENTRE developed web-based tools for large-scale post-seismic emergency management of railway infrastructures. The system has been set-up for the Italian railway manager. It allows the user to compute, in the immediate aftermath of a seismic event, the damage scenario of the railway network starting from the main seismological characteristics. The focus of the current version of the tools are on the railway bridges. Further details can be found in Bellotti et al. (2018).

3.2.2.4 Earthquake Qualitative Impact Assessment (EQIA)

EMSC (Euro-Med Seismological Centre) has developed EQIA, an Earthquake Qualitative Impact Assessment (Gilles, 2010), which provides fast and automatic impact assessment for worldwide crustal earthquakes, with a magnitude 5 or higher. It provides a range of potential impacts (based on intervals of potential fatalities), in order to rate the severity of the event for the triggering of rapid actions. To this end, two empirical equations are used: a GMM for the estimation of the impacted area, and an equation relating the number of fatalities to the earthquake magnitude and to the population density. This approach has the merit of bypassing the shake-map step and of providing a direct impact estimate with a little amount of input data. For large earthquakes of magnitude 7 or higher, the source is modelled as a 1D finite rupture, and different assumptions regarding the position of the fault and its nodal plane are taken into account, adding up to the uncertainties of the earthquake scenario. A comparative study by Julien-Laferrrière (2019), between EQIA predictions on past earthquakes and actual impacts, reveals a satisfying performance by EQIA. Currently, EQIA outcomes are not made publicly available, however they are communicated to a group of selected end-users or when prompted by governmental organizations (e.g., French civil protection).

3.2.2.5 The TELES system

The Taiwanese system TELES (Taiwan Earthquake Loss Estimation System – Yeh et al., 2006) is based on the HAZUS methodology, and it provides decision support after strong earthquakes. The earthquake data comes from the Central Weather Bureau networks and the parameters (location, magnitude) are given by TREIRS (Taiwan Rapid Earthquake Information Release System) within 90s after the event. This enables to estimate the ground motion (PGA and PGV) from a scenario earthquake and prediction equations. The liquefaction effects are included in the method and a probability of damage state for 15 different types of buildings is given, using analytical methods. Damage maps and tables are automatically generated within three to five minutes after receiving the earthquake alert. For now, this procedure does not seem to integrate the new Taiwanese shake-map system yet.

3.2.2.6 Japanese systems READY and SUPREME

Two other systems exist in Japan: the READY system (Midorikawa, 2005), and the more specific SUPREME system (Shimizu et al., 2004), for possible damages on gas infrastructures. READY has an associated array of strong motion accelerometers and borehole systems for liquefaction monitoring. The stations are connected to observation centres via high-speed telephone lines and satellites as a backup. The intensity map is immediately issued, along with other useful information such as hospital or shelter locations. Thanks to an agreement with civil construction firms, the damage of road structures and transportation conditions can also be rapidly assessed. The SUPREME system uses Spectrum Intensity Sensors in order to evaluate damages on gas pipes. The response spectra are evaluated in the range 0.1-2.5s, and if the spectral intensity becomes greater than 30-40 cm/s the decision to shut down the gas supply is made.

3.2.2.7 The Earthquake-Report platform

The independent Earthquake-Report platform, created by researchers from various organizations, is able to provide earthquake reports, shake-maps, and damage estimates for worldwide earthquakes. It uses Did You Feel It data from EMSC and USGS, while the results are further constrained by social media feedback and specifically felt earthquake testimonies (own report form available on the website www.earthquake-report.com).

3.2.2.8 ISAR system

Resulting from a cross-border project between France, Spain and the principality of Andorra, and followed by the SISPyR project (www.sispyr.eu), the ISARD system (Goula et al., 2008) has been used in operational mode since 2007 by the civil protection of Catalonia (Spain). Operated by the ICGC (regional geological survey of Catalonia), this system performs rapid loss assessment by coupling a rough estimate of the seismic intensity using an Intensity Prediction Equation (IPE), with a loss model similar to that described by Sedan et al. (2013). The result is sent in less than 10 minutes by SMS to an on-call seismologist in charge of its validation, then of sending reports to civil protection via SMS and e-mails.

3.3 Summary of rapid loss assessment systems and suggested advances

A summary of the rapid damage and loss assessment systems is proposed in Table 3-1, with the required input data and the output format of each system. Figure 3-1 provides a visual representation of the different systems characteristics.

Table 3-1: Input data and expected outputs for the studied loss assessment systems.

Loss estimation system	Input data	Output	Scale	Operationally & Output status
PAGER	Shake-map + empirical or analytical vulnerability assessment	Fatalities & economic losses estimates + user-friendly depiction of uncertainties	- Population exposed at each intensity level - At the level of the whole event	- Operational as a service - Public
ShakeCast	Shake-map + facility inventory	Shaking values and inspection priorities. Email/text alerts	At the level of individual facilities	- Operational as a service - Restricted to registered users (e.g., infrastructure managers)
GDACS	PAGER output	Three-level color alert	At the level of the whole event	- Operational as a service - Public
SeisDaRo	Custom shake-map + building inventory + vulnerability data	Fatalities graphs and exposure tables. Fast global damage estimates + more accurate analysis of fatalities due to building collapse.	At the level of cities / municipalities	- Operational as a service/demonstrator - Restricted to authorized users
Istanbul ELER	Shake-map + building inventory database + occupancy/population database	Damage and loss maps	At the level of a city district / large building block	- Operational as a service/demonstrator - Restricted to authorized users
SEISAID	Shake-map + building inventory database + occupancy/population database	Collapsed dwellings, and injuries	At the level of the whole event, and disaggregation at the municipality level	- Operational as a service/demonstrator - Restricted to authorized users
QLARM	Scenario earthquake + empirical relations	Fatalities and average damage on buildings on global scale	- Exposure of each population settlement - Grade for the whole event	- Operational as a service - Public
SIGE-DPC	Earthquake characteristics + empirical relations	Collapsed dwellings, unusable dwellings, fatalities and homeless.	At the level of cities / municipalities	- Operational as a service - Restricted to Italian civil protection
EQIA (ESMC)	Earthquake characteristics + population density (LandScan)	Global impact estimate (range)	At the level of the whole event	- Under development & test
TELES	Earthquake scenario + liquefaction effects	Damage maps and tables	At the level of a city district	?

Loss estimation system	Input data	Output	Scale	Operationally & Output status
READY	Intensity map	Damages on roads and buildings, inaccessible roads	At the level of a city district / large building block	?
SUPREME	Spectral intensity	Damage on gas pipes / automatic shut-down	At the level of facilities (buried pipelines)	- Operational as a service - Restricted to gas line operators
Earthquake-Report	Intensity maps, online news	Injuries, fatalities, evacuations	At the level of the whole event	- Public webpage activated for large and damaging events
ISARD	Earthquake characteristics + empirical relations	Collapsed dwellings, unusable dwellings, fatalities and homeless.	At the level of cities / municipalities	- Operational as a service - Restricted to Catalan civil protection

Figure 3-1: Summary of rapid loss estimation systems.

The above review has highlighted several noteworthy points and issues related to the implementation of rapid loss assessment systems worldwide, and especially in Europe. The following comments and recommendations can be made on existing rapid loss assessment tools:

- Some systems, such as PAGER, GDACS or EQIA, aim at providing a picture of the potential impact at the level of the whole earthquake event. This scale is useful for rapidly sizing the disaster and for deciding at which level (e.g., regional, national, international) crisis management operations need to be activated, as well as the amount of aid and resources to dedicate. However, much more detailed information is needed very quickly: usually

first responders require a detailed account of the situation at a local level, in order to establish in which street or building block to operate and to rescue potential casualties. Therefore, systems that estimate damage and losses at a more detailed resolution (e.g., SeisDaRo, ELER, SEISAID) constitute the strict minimum to meet these operational needs, although providing reliable results at such a scale remains very challenging. Conversely, it is not planned for the ShakeMap® and PAGER services to head in this direction, since these tools are intended for disaster management, not emergency response. As a result, the coupling between a shake-map system and a rapid loss assessment tool (at least at city district level) seems like the best way to go: shake-maps are able to provide updated ground-motion estimates, which can in turn feed fragility models of various structural types.

- Most rapid loss assessment systems are based on predicting damage to common buildings (residential or office types). Conversely, only a few of them consider infrastructure components or critical facilities (ShakeCast, SUPREME), and none of the current systems consider yet the effect of failed components on the global performance of the infrastructure, which has a great influence on the crisis management operations (e.g., inaccessible roads, power outage, disrupted water supply). This crucial aspect requires further research efforts, since preliminary proof-of-concept studies have shown its potential (Gehl et al., 2018), although modelling and computational issues need to be improved. Currently, the California Department of Transportation is also testing component-based fragilities in ShakeCast in addition to global functions (Lin et al., 2018).
- Furthermore, when carried out, the estimation of human impacts (fatalities, injuries, homeless people, etc.) is based on empirical methods that are often very simple. These consist either in directly applying predefined loss rate to the resident population according to the seismic intensity (PAGER), or in propagating predicted damages to building to their occupants (SIGE, SEISAID, ISARD) thanks to empirical conversion matrix and hypothesis about occupancy rate of buildings. Due to the criticality of the estimation of these human losses on decision-making in a crisis management context, further research should be conducted to reduce the associated uncertainty. For instance, by developing methodologies to model population exposure no longer as "static data" as is the case today, but as "dynamic data" taking into account hourly (accounting for pendulum movements) and seasonal (accounting for tourist populations) changes.
- Finally, while most recent shake-map systems show a strong focus on uncertainty treatment, such uncertainties are not propagated to the damage and loss assessment steps (i.e., generation of probabilistic distributions of loss metrics, accounting for all sources of variability). Although feasible in theory, one may wonder whether such a probabilistic framework would be of any use to decision makers, unless it could be easily communicated. Possible solutions could, for instance, follow rendering formats that are similar to the Earthquake Impact Scale (Wald et al., 2011) used in PAGER, which is as an effort to simplify the challenge of providing very uncertain fatality estimates.

Another important point of the review is that, while harmonization of RRE systems is desirable for using a robust shake-map algorithm taking into account the various data available with associated uncertainties, it is important to bear in mind that some inputs such as specific GMMs, soil amplification factors and building inventories have to be provided at a local scale, in order for the resulting information to be usable by authorities. Moreover, the level of confidence that risk and disaster managers can have in such tools should be improved if these systems are also used in a planning and mitigation capacity (e.g., generation of prospective hazard and risk scenarios). For instance, USGS services (e.g., ShakeMap, ShakeCast, and PAGER) are not only tools for disaster operational management, but they are as important when used for exercises and planning via scenarios, as well as for risk studies and mitigation efforts. Most of the other damage and loss assessment tools presented in Table 3-1 have first been developed for planning and mitigation purposes, before being adapted to operate in a near real-time context.

Finally, this review has highlighted the co-existence of RREs having international or even global coverage (e.g. USGS services) with others being rather country or regional specific, each with its own advantages. Thus, while the former are often technologically more robust (in terms of IT infrastructure, interoperability, service continuity, etc.) and can be validated very frequently in real situation, the latter allow, on the contrary, to take into account more detailed local specificities conditioning the estimation of losses (zoning of site effects, characterization of the vulnerability of buildings, etc.) as well as the particular needs of local stakeholders, but most often with a lack of validation and an operability rather as demonstrators than as services. Finally, it is important to be aware that, as valuable as rapid response can be for crisis management, if it is not immediately understandable or if no operational implication follows naturally, it will be quickly dismissed and forgotten. Even beyond the cautious choice of indicators to provide, it is therefore also a question for the scientific community of making suitable choices in terms of information representation mode, semantics used, dissemination format, sequencing sending and versioning, etc. To overcome the well-known pitfall of “non-applicable applied research”, and with a view to favouring the operational declination of RREs (e.g. SIGE, ISARD, ...), it appears to be very important to involve stakeholders early in the development of these tools.

4 BENCHMARK STUDY OF DAMAGE ESTIMATION METHODS

This section evaluates two damage estimation methods, namely the application of vulnerability indices based method in the Armagedom software (Sedan et al., 2013) and the application of capacity spectrum method in the SELENA software (Molina et al., 2010). Both procedures are applied to the TB-2 Luchon Valley area (Section 4.1) and to the Alicante (Spain) area (Section 4.2), for specific earthquake scenarios.

4.1 Luchon Valley (TB-2) case-study

Luchon Valley is located in the Pyrenees mountain range in France (Figure 4-1). For the Luchon Valley case-study, where input information has been gathered concerning the hazard calculation and its intensities measures (IMs), the spatial distribution of buildings and the description of the vulnerability for the area of interest. This information has also been converted to the input files required for the SELENA software.

Figure 4-1: Left - Luchon Valley (TB-2). Left: Case study location in the Pyrenees mountain range; Right: 53 municipalities in Luchon Valley. In the Armagedom software, the projection of the project is EPSG:32621 (WGS84/UTM Zone 31N). The Grid cell of the reference raster is 20m.

The area of interest is composed by 53 municipalities presented in Figure 4-1 and named in Table 4-1.

Table 4-1: Name and identifier of the 53 municipalities from Luchon Valley case-study.

ID	Commune	ID	Commune
ID1	ANTIGNAC	ID28	FRONSAC
ID2	ARGUT-DESSOUS	ID29	GARIN
ID3	ARLOS	ID30	GOUAUX-DE-LARBOUST
ID4	ARTIGUE	ID31	GOUAUX-DE-LUCHON
ID5	BACHOS	ID32	GURAN
ID6	BAGNERES-DE-LUCHON	ID33	JURVIELLE
ID7	BAREN	ID34	JUZET-DE-LUCHON
ID8	BENQUE-DESSOUS-ET-DESSUS	ID35	LEGE
ID9	BEZINS-GARRAUX	ID36	LEZ
ID10	BILLIERE	ID37	MARIGNAC
ID11	BINOS	ID38	MAYREGNE
ID12	BOURG-D'OUEIL	ID39	MELLES
ID13	BOUTX	ID40	MONTAUBAN-DE-LUCHON
ID14	BURGALAYS	ID41	MOUSTAION
ID15	CASTILLON-DE-LARBOUST	ID42	OO
ID16	CATHERVIELLE	ID43	PORTET-DE-LUCHON
ID17	CAUBOUS	ID44	POUBEAU
ID18	CAZARIL-LASPENES	ID45	SACCOURVIELLE
ID19	CAZAUX-LAYRISSE	ID46	SAINT-AVENTIN
ID20	CAZEAUX-DE-LARBOUST	ID47	SAINT-BEAT
ID21	CHAUM	ID48	SAINT-MAMET
ID22	CIER-DE-LUCHON	ID49	SAINT-PAUL-D'OUEIL
ID23	CIERP-GAUD	ID50	SALLES-ET-PRATVIEL
ID24	CIRES	ID51	SIGNAC
ID25	ESTENOS	ID52	SODE
ID26	EUP	ID53	TREBONS-DE-LUCHON
ID27	FOS		

4.1.1 Hazard description

Both software, SELENA and Armagedom, start the calculation from the peak ground acceleration (PGA) values presented in Figure 4-2. The PGA values and the corresponding SA values are compatible with the regional hazard level in France. According to the French seismic zonation, the Luchon Valley area is located in seismic zone 4, prone to an earthquake generating a ground acceleration of 0.16g on rock conditions. In the selected scenario, the maximum PGA value, accounting for soil amplification, is between 0.2 and 0.27g for the municipalities represented with the red colour. For Armagedom software, the PGA values are converted into EMS-98 intensity using two GMICE:

- [Atkinson and Sonley \(2000\)](#),
- [Faenza and Michellini \(2010\)](#).

Figure 4-2: Acceleration values (PGA in mg) per municipality. PGA values are estimated at the centroids of polygons/geocodes.

4.1.2 Choice of the vulnerability indices and fragility curve parameters

4.1.2.1 Expert-based choice

For the Luchon Valley area, the exposure data of the buildings are available from three different approaches for data collection and inventory: SERA European Building Exposure Database, the National statistics data INSEE at municipality level and the Field inventory at homogeneous census block level, as detailed in Section 5.1 (Fayjaloun et al., 2021a). The different sources give the information about the material of construction, the technique of construction, the number of the stories, and the number of occupants, with the assumption that the building stock is lumped at a single coordinate (i.e., centroids of polygons representing built areas) with different resolution. For the comparison with SELINA software, we are using the information from the SERA European Building Exposure Database that collects the data in France per municipality, which is a commonly used level of resolution in regional loss modelling.

The different exposure data expressed in SERA taxonomy are associated to vulnerability indices following the building classification scheme proposed within the framework of the Risk-UE European project (Figure 4-3).

SERA		RISKUE		
GEM Taxonomy	Corresponding Acronym in RISKUE	Description	Vi*	
W/LWAL	W	Wood structures	0.447	
CR/LFLS	RC1	Concrete shear frames	0.442	
MCF/LWAL	RC2	Concrete shear walls	0.386	
CR/LFINF	RC3.2	Irregular frames	0.522	
CR/LDUAL	RC4	RC dual systems, RC frame and walls	0.386	
CR+PC/LWAL	RC6	Precast concrete frames, concrete shear walls	0.544	
MUR+ST/LWAL	M1.1	Rubber stone fieldstone	0.873	
MUR+CL/LWAL	M1.2	Simple stone	0.74	

$$\text{The final } V_i = V_i^* + V_{i_{DC}} + V_{i_{NS}}$$

This parameter is corrected if low consideration was given for the design code ($V_{i_{DC}} = 0.16$).

If number of stories is Low (1-2 stories), $V_{i_{NS}} = -0.02$;
if it is medium (3-5 stories), $V_{i_{NS}} = 0.02$;
for high buildings (+6 stories); $V_{i_{NS}} = 0.06$.

Figure 4-3: Method to associate the SERA taxonomies and the RISK-UE taxonomies.

The typological classification of the exposure data is defined based on the European Macroseismic scale EMS-98 (Grünthal, 1998), for which we associate the corresponding RISK-UE typology classes and the associated vulnerability index V_i as defined by the RISK-UE approach (Milutinovic & Trendafilovski, 2003). This parameter is corrected if low consideration was given for the design code during the construction and it also takes into account the number of stories. A vulnerability index V_i is then computed to the 53 municipalities in Luchon Valley area by averaging the V_i of the buildings in each municipality. The specific values are shown in Table 4-2. The corresponding fragility models for residential buildings have been described in the TURNkey Report D4.2 (Borzi et al., 2021).

Table 4-2: Vulnerability index V_i for the 53 municipalities in Luchon Valley.

Id	ID	SERA			RISKUE	Vi	Vi+code level
1	CR+PC/LWAL+CDN/HBET:3-5	CR+PC	LWAL	CDN	RC6	0.544	0.544
2	CR/LDUAL+CDM/HBET:6-/7.0	CR	LDUAL	CDM	RC4	0.386	0.386
3	CR/LDUAL+CDN/HBET:6-	CR	LDUAL	CDN	RC4	0.386	0.386
4	CR+PC/LWAL+CDN/HBET:6-	CR+PC	LWAL	CDN	RC6	0.544	0.544
5	CR/LFINF+CDL/H:1/4.0	CR	LFINF	CDL	RC3.2	0.522	0.682
6	CR/LFINF+CDM/H:2/7.0	CR	LFINF	CDM	RC3.2	0.522	0.522
7	CR/LFINF+CDL/H:2/4.0	CR	LFINF	CDL	RC3.2	0.522	0.682
8	W/LWAL+CDN/H:1	W	LWAL	CDN	W	0.447	0.447
9	CR/LFINF+CDN/HBET:3-5	CR	LFINF	CDN	RC3.2	0.522	0.522
10	CR/LFINF+CDM/H:1/7.0	CR	LFINF	CDM	RC3.2	0.522	0.522

Id	ID	SERA			RISKUE	Vi	Vi+code level
11	MUR+ST/LWAL+CDN/H:2	MUR+ST	LWAL	CDN	M1.1	0.873	0.873
12	CR/LDUAL+CDL/HBET:3-5/4.0	CR	LDUAL	CDL	RC4	0.386	0.546
13	MUR+CL/LWAL+CDN/H:2	MUR+CL	LWAL	CDN	M1.2	0.74	0.74
14	CR/LDUAL+CDM/HBET:3-5/7.0	CR	LDUAL	CDM	RC4	0.386	0.386
15	W/LWAL+CDN/H:2	W	LWAL	CDN	W	0.447	0.447
16	CR/LFLS+CDN/HBET:6-	CR	LFLS	CDN	RC1	0.442	0.442
17	MUR+CL/LWAL+CDN/H:1	MUR+CL	LWAL	CDN	M1.2	0.74	0.74
18	CR/LDUAL+CDL/HBET:6-/4.0	CR	LDUAL	CDL	RC4	0.386	0.546
19	MUR+ST/LWAL+CDN/H:1	MUR+ST	LWAL	CDN	M1.1	0.873	0.873
20	CR/LFLS+CDM/HBET:3-5/7.0	CR	LFLS	CDM	RC1	0.442	0.442
21	CR/LFLS+CDL/HBET:3-5/4.0	CR	LFLS	CDL	RC1	0.442	0.602
22	MCF/LWAL+CDL/H:2	MCF	LWAL	CDL	RC2	0.386	0.546
23	CR+PC/LWAL+CDN/H:2	CR+PC	LWAL	CDN	RC6	0.544	0.544
24	MCF/LWAL+CDL/H:1	MCF	LWAL	CDL	RC2	0.386	0.546
25	CR/LFLS+CDN/HBET:3-5	CR	LFLS	CDN	RC1	0.442	0.442
26	CR/LDUAL+CDM/HBET:6-/4.0	CR	LDUAL	CDM	RC4	0.386	0.386
27	CR/LDUAL+CDM/HBET:3-5/4.0	CR	LDUAL	CDM	RC4	0.386	0.386
28	CR/LFINF+CDM/H:1/4.0	CR	LFINF	CDM	RC3.2	0.522	0.522
29	CR/LFINF+CDM/H:2/4.0	CR	LFINF	CDM	RC3.2	0.522	0.522
30	CR/LFINF+CDL/H:2/8.0	CR	LFINF	CDL	RC3.2	0.522	0.682
31	CR/LDUAL+CDL/HBET:6-/8.0	CR	LDUAL	CDL	RC4	0.386	0.546
32	CR/LFINF+CDM/H:1/11.0	CR	LFINF	CDM	RC3.2	0.522	0.522
33	CR/LDUAL+CDM/HBET:6-/11.0	CR	LDUAL	CDM	RC4	0.386	0.386
34	CR/LFINF+CDM/H:2/11.0	CR	LFINF	CDM	RC3.2	0.522	0.522
35	CR/LDUAL+CDM/HBET:3-5/11.0	CR	LDUAL	CDM	RC4	0.386	0.386
36	CR/LDUAL+CDL/HBET:3-5/8.0	CR	LDUAL	CDL	RC4	0.386	0.546
37	CR/LFINF+CDL/H:1/8.0	CR	LFINF	CDL	RC3.2	0.522	0.682
38	CR/LFLS+CDL/HBET:3-5/0.0	CR	LFLS	CDL	RC1	0.442	0.602
39	MCF/LWAL+CDN/H:1	MCF	LWAL	CDN	RC2	0.386	0.386
40	MCF/LWAL+CDN/H:2	MCF	LWAL	CDN	RC2	0.386	0.386
41	CR/LDUAL+CDL/HBET:3-5/0.0	CR	LDUAL	CDL	RC4	0.386	0.546
42	CR/LFINF+CDM/H:2/0.0	CR	LFINF	CDM	RC3.2	0.522	0.522
43	CR/LFINF+CDL/H:2/0.0	CR	LFINF	CDL	RC3.2	0.522	0.682

4.1.2.2 Application of knowledge-based exposure modelling framework

The Deliverable 4.1 (Schwarz et al., 2021) provides a comprehensive framework for the modelling of the seismic hazard exposure of physical assets, with the consideration of the completeness of exposure catalogue and various level of uncertainties (see Figure 3.1 in the Deliverable 4.1 for the several methods of the framework). This section is a limited application of damage scenarios using the vulnerability classes (empirical method) and fragility functions, defined in the framework as M2-TX-ST and M1-TX respectively.

In the application of the two methods, the building types in Table 4-2 for the 53 municipalities were used to define the damage scenario. A constant intensity of $I_{EMS}=VIII$, corresponding to $PGA = 0.2g$ (see chapter 6.4.4, D4.1) is used for M2-TX-ST method, and a constant acceleration of $PGA = 0.2g$ as well as the acceleration values from Figure 4-2 are used for M1-TX method.

Empirical method based on vulnerability classes and EMS-98 (M2-TX-ST):

As described in chapter 3.2.2 from D4.1, method 2 is selected as the empirical approach for definition of scenarios based on vulnerability classes. Here, method 2 is applied in two approaches which are defined as follow:

M2-TX-ST: EMS-98 vulnerability classes

Applying assigned vulnerability indices in Table 4-2, seven structural types are recognized to allocate defined taxonomies in EMS-98. The evaluation process for structural type and vulnerability classes based on EMS-98 is carried out considering SERA taxonomy and determined vulnerability indices plus their code level. More detailed information are described in Table A-2 in Appendix I.

M2-TX-ST*: Enhanced

This approach considers the types suggested in Deliverable 4.1 (refer to Annex 4.2: Tables A4-4 to A4-7), where the vulnerability classes based on EMS-98 are extended for other SERA types.

Fragility functions method (M1-TX):

Following the knowledge-based exposure modelling framework presented in D4.1, fragility functions are assigned for each building type in Luchon Valley area. The selected functions are classified into three groups: Most Suitable, Still Suitable and Less/No Suitable, and the selection criteria is shown in Figure 4-4. The best available suited group of functions is used whenever available, following the scenario type M1-4 as explained in section 6.3.1.2 in D4.1. The assigned functions are listed in Appendix I.

Figure 4-4: Assignment of fragility functions to Luchon Valley area.

4.1.3 Damage comparison and conclusions

4.1.3.1 Results from Expert-based choice

Figure 4-5 presents the comparison between the damage degrees obtained with the SELENA and Armagedom methods, respectively. We can notice the importance of the GMICE relation that can highly impact the damage distribution. For the Luchon Valley case-study, both software give a damage distribution centred on the buildings without damages (None - D0). Using the GMICE by [Atkinson and Sonley \(2000\)](#) in Armagedom, the damage distribution is much closer to the one calculated with SELENA software.

Figure 4-5: Damage degrees computed with SELENA and Armagedom for Luchon Valley Case Study; Left: using the soil acceleration and the GMICE by [Atkinson and Sonley \(2000\)](#); Right: using the soil acceleration and the GMICE by [Faenza and Michelini \(2010\)](#).

4.1.3.2 Results from Knowledge-based exposure modelling framework

Empirical method based on vulnerability classes and EMS-98 (M2-TX-ST):

Using the provided information from Luchon Valley case study in the level of municipalities, leads to get new knowledge levels and definition of scenarios in two approaches based on vulnerability indices and SERA taxonomy (see Table 4-2) to assign vulnerability classes according to EMS-98 in different status. Figure 4-6 shows the number of buildings per type and the distribution of the most likely vulnerability classes.

Following the mentioned criteria for M2-TX-ST approach, the determined vulnerability classes in five scenarios are explained in Table 4-3. The results of executed scenarios are shown in Figure 4-7 considering the concept of mean damage grade distribution in each municipality. It should be mentioned that these results do not include the detailed outcomes for counted districts.

Table 4-3: Definition of scenarios according to concept of approach M2-TX-ST for Luchon.

EMS-98 type	VC						Scenarios				
	A	B	C	D	E	F	1	2	3	4	5
Rubble stone, Field stone	○						A	A	A	A	A
Simple stone	-----○						A	AB	B	B	B
Reinforced or confined masonry			-----○-----				C	CD	D	DE	E
Frame with moderate level of ERD		-----○-----					B	C	D	DE	E
Walls with moderate level of ERD			-----○-----				C	CD	D	DE	E
Walls with high level of ERD				-----○-----			D	DE	E	EF	F
Timber structure		-----○-----					B	C	D	DE	E

** scenarios:

Scenario Abbr.	(vp)	(p)	(ml)	(o)	(vo)
Definition	Very Pessimistic	Pessimistic	Most Likely	Optimistic	Very Optimistic

Figure 4-6: Distribution of buildings types according to approach M2-TX-ST and the most likely vulnerability classes for Luchon Valley.

**Legend:

DG	0	1	2	3	4	5				
MDG	0-0.5	0.5-1	1-1.5	1.5-2	2-2.5	2.5-3	3-3.5	3.5-4	4-4.5	4.5-5

Figure 4-7: Distribution of damage grades in the level of municipalities, Luchon, TB-2: Approach M2-TX-ST, I_{EMS} = VIII.

Comparing to the performed scenarios from TB-2 for PGA=0.2g, the percentage of each damage grade for five executed scenarios assuming $I_{EMS}=VIII$ are analyzed and the related results are shown in Figure 4-8.

Figure 4-8: Percentage of damage distribution per determined scenario in Luchon considering $I_{EMS} = VIII$, approach M2-TX-ST.

Comparison of damage distributions between five scenarios for whole area of Luchon according to approach M2-TX-ST definitions is illustrated in Figure 4-9.

Scenario **Mean damage grade distribution for whole Luchon, TB-2**

Figure 4-9: Comparison of damage distributions between five scenarios approach M2-TX-ST ($I_{EMS} = VIII$).

Table 4-4 explains the assigned vulnerability classes in five scenarios based on the concept of approach M2-TX-ST* (Enhanced) for Luchon Valley.

Table 4-4: Definition of scenarios according to the concept of approach M2-TX-ST* for Luchon.

EMS-98 type	Type*	VC						Scenarios**				
		A	B	C	D	E	F	1	2	3	4	5
MASONRY unreinforced, simple stone	M3							A	AB	B	B	B
MASONRY unreinforced, with manufactured stone units	M5							B	BC	C	CD	D
MASONRY confined masonry	M7							C	CD	D	DE	E
REINFORCED CONCRETE frame without ERD	RC1_L							A	B	C	CD	D
REINFORCED CONCRETE frame with moderate level of ERD	RC1_M							B	C	D	DE	E
REINFORCED CONCRETE dual system without and low level of ERD	RC3_L							B	BC	C	CD	D
REINFORCED CONCRETE dual system with moderate and high level of ERD	RC3_M/H							C	CD	D	DE	E
PRECAST REINFORCED CONCRETE walls	RC4							C	D	DE	E	F
REINFORCED CONCRETE flat slab	RC6							A	B	C	D	E
TIMBER walls	W2							B	BC	C	CD	D

* refer to Annex 4.2 in Deliverable 4.1 for the types and the correlation with SERA taxonomies.

newly introduced

** scenarios:

Scenario Abbr.	(vp)	(p)	(ml)	(o)	(vo)
Definition	Very Pessimistic	Pessimistic	Most Likely	Optimistic	Very Optimistic

Figure 4-10 shows the number of buildings per type and the distribution of the most likely vulnerability classes using approach M2-TX-ST* (Enhanced) for Luchon Valley.

The results of executed scenarios are shown in Figure 4-11 and Figure 4-12 considering the concept of damage distribution in each municipality.

Figure 4-10: Distribution of buildings types according to approach M2-TX-ST* and the most likely vulnerability classes for Luchon Valley.

Similar to results of approach M2-TX-ST, comparing to the performed scenarios from TB-2 for $PGA=0.2g$, the percentage of each damage grade for five executed scenarios assuming $I_{EMS}=VIII$ in approach M2-TX-ST* are illustrated in Figure 4-13.

In comparison between Figure 4-8 (approach M2-TX-ST) and 4-11 (approach M2-TX-ST*), it is clear that the portions of higher damage grades decreased significantly in M2-TX-ST* due to the assignment of new and additional typologies for the building stock in Luchon area.

**Legend:

DG	0	1	2	3	4	5				
MDG	0-0.5	0.5-1	1-1.5	1.5-2	2-2.5	2.5-3	3-3.5	3.5-4	4-4.5	4.5-5

Figure 4-11: Distribution of damage grades in the level of municipalities, Luchon, TB-2: approach M2-TX-ST*, I_{EMS} = VIII.

Scenario

Mean damage grade distribution for whole Luchon, TB-2

Figure 4-13: Comparison of damage distributions between five scenarios for whole Luchon area, approach M2-TX-ST* (IEMS = VII).

Fragility functions method, M1-TX:

Figure 4-14 shows the damage distribution using the fragility functions method M1-TX, with a constant PGA of 0.2g, compared to the results from M2-TX-ST. The damage distribution in M1-TX method shows a significantly larger number of the building reaching damage grade 5, which is normally observed when fragility functions are used. This highlights the importance of the calibration of fragility functions to have comparable results with the Most Likely results of the empirical approach.

Explanations: M1-TX: Fragility functions, vp: Very Pessimistic, p: Pessimistic, ml: Most Likely, o: Optimistic, vo: Very Optimistic.

Figure 4-14: Comparison of damage distribution between M1-TX and M2-TX-ST methods.

4.1.3.3 Comparison of results

In the application of Expert-based choice in section 4.1.2.1, the assignment of vulnerability indices in Armageddon is similar to M2-TX-ST approach in Deliverable 4.1. However, the vulnerability indices are assigned by linking the SERA taxonomies to RISKUE structural types and not the EMS-98 as in applied M2-TX-ST and M2-TX-ST* approaches in section 4.1.2.2.

Figure 4-15 illustrates the comparison between the results obtained using Expert-based choice and knowledge-based exposure modelling framework. It can be observed that the results from Armageddon are comparable to very optimistic results from M2-TX-ST and M2-TX-ST*. That could be attributed to the hazard input used in the two approaches, as the accelerations from Figure 4-2 were used in the case of Armageddon and a uniform PGA was used in both M2-TX-ST and M2-TX-ST*. It could be concluded that the application of refined zoning would result in more optimistic results.

As for the assignment of fragility functions in SELINA section 4.1.2.1, the followed approach is comparable to M1-TX approach, and the functions assigned to the building types were taken from [Martins and Silva \(2020\)](#). The main difference is that when applying the M1-TX in section 4.1.2.2, a large number of publications is used and multiple functions are assigned per type according to their suitability.

Explanations:

SE: SELENA, Ar(1): Armagedom using the soil acceleration and the GMICE by [Atkinson and Sonley \(2000\)](#)
 Ar(2): Armagedom using the soil acceleration and the GMICE by [Faenza and Michelini \(2010\)](#).

Figure 4-15: Comparison of damage distributions between the two approaches (M2-TX-ST from Figure 4-9, M2-TX-ST* from Figure 4-13) and the results from SELENA and Armagedom (from Figure 4-5).

Explanations: M1-TX: Fragility functions, SE: SELENA, Ar(1): Armagedom using the soil acceleration and the GMICE by [Atkinson and Sonley \(2000\)](#). Ar(2): Armagedom using the soil acceleration and the GMICE by [Faenza and Michelini \(2010\)](#).

Figure 4-16: Comparison of damage distribution results from M1-TX (from Figure 4-14) , SELENA and Armagedom (from Figure 4-5).

Figure 4-16 shows the comparison of results between SELENA and M1-TX, and it can be observed that the set of functions selected for SELENA gave a lower number of buildings reaching damage grades higher than DG1. It is worth mentioning that the types with the Id of 11, 13, 17, and 19 (Table 4-2) represent about 72% of the building stock, and the choice of functions for these non-ductile clay and stone masonry building types highly influence the outcomes. Careful selection of region-specific functions (in the case of availability) is highly advised for these types.

4.2 Alicante Case study

For the Alicante case-study, the area of interest is composed by 54 municipalities (Figure 4-17).

Figure 4-17: Name and location of the municipalities for the area of interest. In the Armagedom software, the projection of the project is EPSG:25830 (ETRS89_UTM_zone_30N). The Grid cell of the reference raster is 50m.

4.2.1 Hazard description

The chosen earthquake scenario is the 1829 Torrevieja earthquake with a magnitude of M_w 6.5 and a depth of 5km (epicentral distance to the city ranges from 20 to 56 km). IMs (PGA) have been estimated while including site effects (Figure 4-18).

Figure 4-18: Intensity map (left) and PGA map (right) calculated by SELENA software, for the 1829 Torrevieja earthquake.

Hence, in this case, Armageddon software use directly the values of PGA provided by UA, without considering the step related to the amplification of the bedrock acceleration with the site effects coefficients. The maximum value of PGA is 0.211g in the Isla Nueva area. The others maximum values near Alicante city centre are around 0.148g.

As for Luchon Valley case-study, the PGA values, accounting for soil amplification, are converted to the intensity (EMS98) using two GMICE (Figure 4-19):

- [Atkinson & Sonley \(2000\)](#),
- [Faenza and Michelini \(2010\)](#).

Figure 4-19: Intensity map calculated by Armagedom software using the simulated PGA values; Left: conversion with [Atkinson and Sonley \(2000\)](#) GMICE; Right: conversion with [Faenza and Michelini \(2010\)](#) GMICE.

4.2.2 Expert-based choice of the vulnerability indices and fragility curve parameters

A total of 37 building typologies have been identified in the area of interest: this local taxonomy is then converted into the SERA and RISK-UE taxonomies (Table 4-5). An expert-based judgment, based on the [Lagomarsino & Giovinazzi \(2006\)](#) approach, has led to the choice of the vulnerability indices V_i to be used in Armagedom software. The final vulnerability index used in damage calculation is the summation of the: (i) V_i , which is the most probable value of the vulnerability index for the Risk-UE typology, (ii) the behaviour modifier ΔV_c related to the seismic design code level, (iii) the behaviour modifier ΔV_{Nb} related to the number of floors and (iv) the regional vulnerability factor ΔV_R , established here on a base of an expert judgment, at 0.04. The number of buildings belonging to the 37 typologies are distributed into the 54 municipalities in order to correctly represent the building distribution within the city. The corresponding fragility models for residential buildings have been described in the TURNkey Report D4.2 ([Borzi et al., 2021](#)).

Table 4-5: UA Taxonomy type and equivalence with SERA and RISK-UE taxonomies and vulnerability index.

ID	Taxonomy type					SERA			RISKUE	V_i	$V_i + \Delta V_c$	$V_i + \Delta V_{Nb} + \Delta V_c$	$V_i + \Delta V_{Nb} + \Delta V_c + \Delta V_R$
1	MUR-STRUB/LWAL-DUN/H:1	Masonry, unreinforced	Stone, unknown technology	Wall	Non-ductile	MUR+ST	LWAL	CDN	M1.1	0.873	0.873	0.873	0.913
2	MUR-STRUB/LWAL-DUN/H:2	Masonry, unreinforced	Stone, unknown technology	Wall	Non-ductile					0.873	0.873	0.873	0.913
3	MUR-STDRE/LWAL-DUN/H:1	Masonry, unreinforced		Wall	Non-ductile					0.873	0.873	0.873	0.913
4	MUR-STDRE/LWAL-DUN/H:2	Masonry, unreinforced		Wall	Non-ductile					0.873	0.873	0.873	0.913
5	MUR-CL99/LWAL-DUN/H:1	Masonry, unreinforced	Fired clay unit	Wall	Non-ductile	MUR+CL	LWAL	CDN	M1.2	0.74	0.74	0.74	0.78

6	MUR-CL99/LWAL-DUN/H:2	Masonry, unreinforced	Fired clay unit	Wall	Non-ductile						0.74	0.74	0.74	0.78
7	MUR-CL99/LWAL-DUN/H:3-5	Masonry, unreinforced	Fired clay unit	Wall	Non-ductile						0.74	0.74	0.76	0.8
8	MUR-CL99/LWAL-DUN/H:5+	Masonry, unreinforced	Fired clay unit	Wall	Non-ductile						0.74	0.74	0.8	0.84
9	MUR/LWAL-DUN/H:1	Masonry, unreinforced		Wall	Non-ductile	MUR	LWAL	CDN	M3.4		0.616	0.616	0.616	0.656
10	MUR/LWAL-DUN/H:2	Masonry, unreinforced		Wall	Non-ductile						0.616	0.616	0.616	0.656
11	MUR/LWAL-DUN/H:3-5	Masonry, unreinforced		Wall	Non-ductile						0.616	0.616	0.636	0.676
12	MUR/LWAL-DUN/H:5+	Masonry, unreinforced		Wall	Non-ductile						0.616	0.616	0.676	0.716
13	CR/LFM-DUL/H:1	Concrete, reinforced		Moment frame	Ductile, low	CR	LFLS	CDL	RC1=>RC3.2		0.522	0.682	0.682	0.722
14	CR/LFM-DUL/H:2	Concrete, reinforced		Moment frame	Ductile, low						0.522	0.682	0.682	0.722
15	CR/LFM-DUL/H:3-5	Concrete, reinforced		Moment frame	Ductile, low						0.522	0.682	0.682	0.722
16	CR/LFM-DUL/H:6-8	Concrete, reinforced		Moment frame	Ductile, low						0.522	0.682	0.762	0.802
17	CR/LFM-DUL/H:8+	Concrete, reinforced		Moment frame	Ductile, low						0.522	0.682	0.762	0.802
18	CR/LFM-DUM/H:1	Concrete, reinforced		Moment frame	Ductile, medium	CR	LFLS	CDM	RC1=>RC3.2		0.522	0.522	0.522	0.562
19	CR/LFM-DUM/H:2	Concrete, reinforced		Moment frame	Ductile, medium						0.522	0.522	0.522	0.562
20	CR/LFM-DUM/H:3-5	Concrete, reinforced		Moment frame	Ductile, medium						0.522	0.522	0.522	0.562
21	CR/LFM-DUM/H:6-8	Concrete, reinforced		Moment frame	Ductile, medium						0.522	0.522	0.582	0.622
22	CR/LFM-DUM/H:8+	Concrete, reinforced		Moment frame	Ductile, medium						0.522	0.522	0.582	0.622
23	CR/LFM-DUH/H:1	Concrete, reinforced		Moment frame	Ductile, high	CR	LFLS	CDM	RC1=>RC3.2		0.522	0.362	0.362	0.402
24	CR/LFM-DUH/H:2	Concrete, reinforced		Moment frame	Ductile, high						0.522	0.362	0.362	0.402
25	CR/LFM-DUH/H:3-5	Concrete, reinforced		Moment frame	Ductile, high						0.522	0.362	0.362	0.402
26	CR/LFM-DUH/H:6-8	Concrete, reinforced		Moment frame	Ductile, high						0.522	0.362	0.402	0.442
27	CR/LFM-DUH/H:8+	Concrete, reinforced		Moment frame	Ductile, high						0.522	0.362	0.402	0.442
28	CR/LFINF-DUL/H:1	Concrete, reinforced		Infilled frame	Ductile, low	CR	LFINF	CDL	RC3.2		0.522	0.682	0.682	0.722
29	CR/LFINF-DUL/H:2	Concrete, reinforced		Infilled frame	Ductile, low						0.522	0.682	0.682	0.722
30	CR/LFINF-DUL/H:3-5	Concrete, reinforced		Infilled frame	Ductile, low						0.522	0.682	0.682	0.722
31	CR/LFINF-DUL/H:6-8	Concrete, reinforced		Infilled frame	Ductile, low						0.522	0.682	0.762	0.802
32	CR/LFINF-DUL/H:8+	Concrete, reinforced		Infilled frame	Ductile, low						0.522	0.682	0.762	0.802
33	CR/LFINF-DUM/H:1	Concrete, reinforced		Infilled frame	Ductile, medium	CR	LFINF	CDM	RC3.2		0.522	0.522	0.522	0.562
34	CR/LFINF-DUM/H:2	Concrete, reinforced		Infilled frame	Ductile, medium						0.522	0.522	0.522	0.562
35	CR/LFINF-DUM/H:3-5	Concrete, reinforced		Infilled frame	Ductile, medium						0.522	0.522	0.522	0.562
36	CR/LFINF-DUM/H:6-8	Concrete, reinforced		Infilled frame	Ductile, medium						0.522	0.522	0.582	0.622
37	CR/LFINF-DUM/H:8+	Concrete, reinforced		Infilled frame	Ductile, medium						0.522	0.522	0.582	0.622

4.2.3 Damage comparison and conclusions

Figure 4-20 presents the comparison of the results in terms of damage degrees computed with the SELENA and Armagedom software, respectively. Despite the fact that the two damage calculation approaches are completely different (one based on vulnerability indices and the other on fragility curves), the shape of the distribution is similar with a mean damage degree between 1 and 2 for both methods. However, Armagedom software presents larger number of buildings without damage (D0 – None) compared to SELENA software.

Figure 4-20: Damage degrees computed with SELENA and Armagedom; Top: using the soil acceleration and the GMICE by [Faenza and Michelini \(2010\)](#); Bottom: using directly the intensity values.

This can be explained firstly by the description of the IM of the hazard in each software: Armagedom uses EMS98 intensity (converted from PGA values) as values for IM for the damage calculation, while SELENA considers the spectral acceleration values as IM. This step introduces a first difference since Armagedom does not consider the spectral values, which are different than the PGA values.

Secondly, the difference can be due to the definition of the vulnerability and the difference between using fragility curves and vulnerability indices. For SELENA software, the spectral acceleration values are related directly to the mean and standard deviation of a lognormal fragility curve for each of the damage degrees described for each building typology; while in Armagedom software, the intensity and the vulnerability indices are used to the calculation of the mean damage degree, which is later the only parameter used, for the beta distribution and for all the damage degrees of a building typology.

Moreover, in addition to the fact that the damage assessment procedures are completely different, even the damage descriptions and the limit-state thresholds from one method to another are not completely in agreement. Nevertheless, considering all these differences between the two approaches, the results seem quite consistent and the spatial distribution of damages seems coherent, but with lower damage values for Armagedom software (Figure 4-21).

Figure 4-21: Buildings with Extensive Damages; Left: SELENA software; Right: Armagedom software.

5 SENSITIVITY OF EARTHQUAKE DAMAGE ESTIMATION TO THE INPUT DATA

5.1 Study in TB-2 (Luchon Valley, France): Influence of the resolution of soil amplification maps and building exposure datasets

This section studies the effects of the soil data and exposure data of residential building inventories, as well as their spatial resolution, on seismic damage and loss estimates for a given earthquake scenario: it represents the summary of the study by [Fayjaloun et al. \(2021a\)](#) on this specific issue.

The aim is to investigate how beneficial it would be to acquire higher resolution inventories at the cost of additional effort and resources. Seismic damage computations are used to evaluate the relative influence of varying spatial resolution on a given damage model, where other parameters are held constant. We use soil characterization maps and building exposure inventories, provided at different scales from different sources: the European database from the SERA project, a national dataset at the municipality scale, and local field investigations. Soil characteristics are used to evaluate site effects and to assign amplification factors to the strong motion applied to the exposed areas. Exposure datasets are used to assign vulnerability indices to sets of buildings, from which a damage distribution is produced (based on the applied seismic input). The different spatial resolutions are benchmarked in a case-study area which is subject to moderate-to-average seismicity levels (Luchon Valley, France, in TB-2, see Figure 5-1).

Figure 5-1: Left: Map of the Luchon Valley and the 53 municipalities; Right: location of the Luchon area overlaid with the French seismic zonation.

[Corbane et al. \(2017\)](#) shed light on the influence of methodological and data input choices on the risk estimates at a pan-European level. Reliable inventories of the building stocks and soil characteristics, along with their spatial resolution, are crucial components in a given earthquake scenario, when the magnitude, epicentre, and fault mechanism are known. Besides this, the choice of an inventory and its spatial resolution depends not only on data availability and accessibility, as well as their degree of complexity and usability, but also on the purpose of the seismic risk assessment; for example, financial planning of earthquake losses, disaster risk mitigation, retrofit design, emergency rescue, and so on ([Goda & Tesfamariam, 2019](#); [Goda et al., 2020](#); [Hofer et al., 2020](#); [Shahbazi et al., 2020](#)).

[Bal et al. \(2010\)](#) showed that, for emergency response applications where the interest is in the distribution of damage as well as the total impact, a more refined spatial resolution of the exposure data is clearly a necessity. The collection of harmonized data at a regional scale, as well as at the local scale, still represents one of the major challenges in seismic risk assessment studies. Preparing for data inventory is usually the most time-consuming and costly aspect of a loss study. It is also the most frustrating as, in principle, it is ideal to develop a perfect inventory; however, in practice, compromises must be made. It is wise to compile and update inventories that are as accurate as possible, under the circumstances and resources available. In this section, we focus on two key inventories that are needed to estimate seismic damage: the soil database, which is part of the hazard factor when considering site amplification, and the building database, which establishes the exposure and vulnerability factors. The first inventory is about the local site conditions that have a great effect on earthquake losses. Due to local site effects, greater seismic losses often occur due to ground failures, increased intensity of shaking under some soil and topographic conditions, and selective amplification of ground motion at the frequencies critical to the structural response. While geotechnical data collected at individual construction sites can be very valuable in this effort, geological maps of districts and zones in a region – which are more commonly available – are more useful (e.g., [Falcone et al., 2018, 2021](#)). [Silva et al. \(2020\)](#) proposed that the relationship between a model's resolution and the ground motion spatial correlation, as well as the consideration of local effects, such as ground motion site amplification, should be investigated further.

The second inventory is related to the buildings and their vulnerability. It provides the spatial distribution of buildings at the territorial scale (i.e., the number of buildings in each territorial unit of analysis), as well as the vulnerability classification of these buildings; that is, the seismic resistance considered by the adopted vulnerability model ([Polese et al., 2019](#)). Census data on housing, which contain information on construction age, building material, and number of stories, are the primary source for building inventory, together with those on population, providing information about the exposure of the population through building occupancy. Building-by-building surveys, providing detailed data for single buildings in an investigated area, are the most complete source towards vulnerability classification. On the other hand, regional or national seismic damage assessments generally use information from remote sensing and national housing databases, where information is typically provided at a coarse resolution (i.e., at district or municipality level). In addition, exposure models of portfolios of buildings from the (re)insurance industry can be developed at a high resolution, as the location of each asset is documented. In these cases, spatial aggregation of the assets is performed, in order to minimize the computational effort. In all cases, [Bal et al. \(2010\)](#) explained that, when the building stock data are aggregated, the modeller would usually assume each building class to be uniformly distributed over the area of the aggregated scale. In this case, the simplest

approach would be to estimate the ground motions at a single point within each aggregated unit (e.g., administrative zone) and to use this value for all the damage calculations within that unit (which effectively models all the exposure data as being concentrated at this single point) (Crowley, 2014; Silva, 2016). The practical implementation of aggregated exposure models unavoidably includes some form of spatial aggregation. Furthermore, the aggregation and relocation of buildings result in a misrepresentation of the distance between the assets and the seismic sources (Kalakonas et al., 2020). Thus, such building exposure models add uncertainty to the damage assessment. Another important source of uncertainty arises from the grouping of the building inventory into a certain number of building classes, which depends on the detail of exposure information (Pittore et al., 2020).

A question thus arises: to what extent is acquiring a higher resolution inventory beneficial? In this section we studied the effects of spatial scale (i.e., the resolution of input data describing the soil conditions and the characteristics of residential buildings) on the estimation of damage and loss for a given earthquake scenario, by considering either “weak data” (collected at a large-scale) or “more accurate”, yet more difficult-to-obtain, detailed surveys. Specifically, we address the question of how detailed such datasets should be, in order to yield a robust enough estimation of damage and loss, and how this affects the information delivered to operational emergency managers.

Descriptions of the different soil and building exposure inventories are presented in Section 5.1.1, as well as the approaches used to associate the soil amplification factors and the building vulnerability index. The structural damage is estimated using the intensity-based empirical vulnerability relationships developed by Lagomarsino & Giovinazzi (2006), without considering site effects at the first stage (constant PGA), to study the effect of exposure data resolution in a deterministic scenario; and with site amplifications at a second stage to study the effects of both soil and exposure data resolution on the damage estimates. Finally, two historical deterministic scenarios are studied. The findings of this study are detailed in Sections 5.1.2 and 5.1.3. The objective of studying the two historical regional earthquakes is not to compare the damage prediction with the observed damages, but rather to illustrate the differences obtained using different resolutions of the input data.

5.1.1 Scenarios and methodology

The risk evaluation procedure used herein consists of various steps, which are briefly outlined in this section. The first step of the procedure is to set the level of strong motion for rock conditions (i.e., without site effects), expressed in PGA, using either (i) a user-defined PGA map, or (ii) calculation performed using a GMM, based on the magnitude and location of the scenario-earthquake assuming rock site conditions. Then, the impact of site effects on the PGA due to local variations in the near-surface lithology—and, possibly, topography (not considered here)—are modelled, by applying soil amplification coefficients using a site classification map (ideally coming from a seismic microzonation study). The PGA maps are then converted into macroseismic intensity, in terms of the EMS98 European Macroseismic Scale (Grünthal, 1998), using a GMICE developed by Atkinson & Sonley (2000). The elements at risk (in this study, residential buildings) are characterized by vulnerability indices (V_i): a V_i value is assigned to each building type, defined in terms of its age, material, technique of construction and, potentially, other characteristics. Next, the damage degree is estimated, using the intensity-

based empirical vulnerability relationships developed by [Lagomarsino & Giovinazzi \(2006\)](#) on the basis of the EMS98 macroseismic scale, where an analytical expression for the mean damage grade, μ_D (mean of the discrete beta distribution), is provided as a function of the macroseismic intensity and the V_i of a given building type. Finally, the distribution of damage at each location is assessed, based on μ_D and a value, t , which governs the spread of the discrete beta distribution. The outcome is the distribution, in terms of the six damage levels defined in the EMS98 – D0 (undamaged), D1 (slight damage), D2 (moderate damage), D3 (heavy damage), D4 (partial collapse), and D5 (total collapse) – for each location, which are all separately considered. This procedure is implemented in the software Armagedom, which is used for the computations presented here. Details on the procedure and the software are provided by [Sedan et al. \(2013\)](#) and [Negulescu et al. \(2020\)](#).

We identify three sources for the databases, concerning the soil classification maps:

- The European map (issued from SERA project), Municipal level ([Crowley et al., 2019a](#));
- The National map (issued from a collaboration between BRGM and CCR, *Caisse Centrale de Réassurance* in France), Municipal level ([Monfort & Roullé, 2016](#));
- The maps issued from microzonation studies at the specific area (SISPy project), District level ([Roullé et al., 2012](#)).

We also identify three databases for collecting data concerning building exposure:

- The European database (issued from SERA project), Municipal level ([Crowley et al., 2018](#));
- Data from the French national statistics institute (INSEE), Municipal level – in which the spatial distribution is superimposed with the occupancy areas ([Sedan et al., 2008](#));
- Data issued from site inspection at the specific area (SISPy project), district level ([Monfort et al., 2012](#)).

Therefore, we define three scale scenarios, in order to estimate the seismic damage corresponding to a given ground-motion scenario, using the various data sources:

- **SS1—Europe:** using the European soil map and the European database for the buildings, at the municipal level;
- **SS2—France:** using the National soil map and the national statistics database for the buildings, at the municipal level;
- **SS3—Luchon:** using the soil maps and building data issued at the district level.

In the following, we collect and harmonize the input data for the three scale scenarios (SS), corresponding to different scales of data collected: SS1—Europe, SS2—France, and SS3—Luchon (Table 5-1 and Figure 5-2). Then, we estimate the seismic damage, using a constant ground acceleration of 200 cm/s^2 in rock conditions (see Section 5.1.2). This is the value of the PGA for a return period of 475 years in the area, given by the French Annex of Eurocode 8 ([CEN, 2004](#)).

Table 5-1: Scale scenario description based on the source of databases to characterize the site amplification as well as the building exposure.

Level of Detail	National Statistics Data		In-Situ Investigation Data
Scale Scenario	SS1: Europe	SS2: France	SS3: Luchon
Hazard	Conversion of the intensity from acceleration		
	European Geological map	National geological map	Regional geological map
Soil	Geol map (1/1,000,000)	Geol map (1/40,000) + Boreholes	Geol map (1/10,000) + boreholes + geophysical measurements
Site effect zonation			
Site effect amplification	3 classes (1–1.35–1.5) following EC8	6 classes (1–1.2–1.35–1.5–1.6–1.8) following EC8 (with three classes only in the area of study)	5 classes (1–1.18–1.35–1.5–1.8) following EC8
Exposure	SERA	INSEE and soil occupation	Homogeneous census block
Inventory and zonation	53 zones (municipalities)	53 zones (municipalities)	203 zones (infra-municipal districts)
Vulnerability index	Vi corresponding to SERA typology based on RISK-UE	Vi from INSEE statistics (based on age, type, number of floor)	Vi from INSEE statistics improved with Field inspection
Damage	Methodology [23]: Building Damage using EMS98 intensity-based buildings vulnerability		

Figure 5-2: The site characterization maps and the building exposure used for the three scale scenarios defined in this study.

More details about the constitution of the soil classification maps for Luchon Valley are provided in [Fayjaloun et al. \(2021a\)](#). A comparison between soil classes distributions for the urban areas and the three studied scales (Figure 5-3) shows that the extent of the urban areas located on soils prone to site effects (soil classes from B to E) varied strongly with the map scale: it represents 25% of urban areas at the European scale, 56% at the regional scale, and 65–74% for the local scale site map (depending on how the classes A and B class are considered; see Figure 5-3). Therefore, the chosen scale is a key parameter, which can cover (or not) the critical size of the geomorphological object studied.

Figure 5-3: Pie charts of the distribution of soil characterization classes in urbanized areas for the three defined scale scenarios.

More details about the constitution of the building exposure dataset for Luchon Valley are provided in TURNkey Report D4.2 (Borzi et al., 2021). The fragility of residential buildings to earthquake shaking can be characterized by the vulnerability indices (V_i), which range from zero (no vulnerability to earthquake shaking) to one (building is extremely vulnerable to shaking). The exposure data for the three scenarios, in terms of number of buildings per municipality and the corresponding average vulnerability indices, are presented in Table 5-2. Looking at the vulnerability indices for the three datasets, we can notice that the three average values are quite similar, with a small decrease of the average value with the increase of the characteristics describing the typologies. A first observation is that, in this specific case, the European and Regional databases were on the safe side, with higher vulnerability indices than those determined from the Local database. A second observation from Table 5-2 is that the variation in the vulnerability indices is smaller for the Local database, with respect to the Regional Database, and almost equivalent to that of the European Database.

Table 5-2: Building exposure data (number of buildings and the average vulnerability index) by municipality in the Luchon Valley area, extracted from the three databases used for this study.

Number	Name	SS1		SS2		SS3	
		Buildings	V_i	Buildings	V_i	Buildings	V_i
1	ANTIGNAC	59.34	0.72	70.31	0.68	69.24	0.62
2	ARGUT-DESSOUS	62.07	0.67	74.53	0.66	76.55	0.62
3	ARLOS	107.73	0.72	114.14	0.7	113.83	0.63
4	ARTIGUE	27.3	0.72	35.18	0.77	39.35	0.69
5	BACHOS	33.82	0.74	33.97	0.7	30.81	0.64
6	BAGNERES-DE-LUCHON	999.79	0.67	1787.08	0.7	1860.71	0.64
7	BAREN	12.9	0.65	20.1	0.6	14.08	0.67
8	BENQUE-DESSOUS-ET-DESSUS	37.33	0.72	39.25	0.65	44.45	0.62
9	BEZINS-GARRAUX	61.2	0.67	69.09	0.66	66.98	0.65
10	BILLIERE	24.17	0.72	23.62	0.68	27.93	0.67
11	BOURG-D'OUAIL	37.77	0.72	32	0.68	35.32	0.62
12	BOUTX	496.05	0.71	542.47	0.71	520.76	0.65
13	BURGALAYS	99.42	0.72	110.07	0.68	105.68	0.61
14	CASTILLON-DE-LARBOUST	55.34	0.72	83.19	0.67	74.02	0.62
15	CATHERVIELLE	47.99	0.73	52.51	0.71	64.33	0.65
16	CAUBOUS	14.27	0.74	16.5	0.79	17.94	0.62
17	CAZARIL-LASPENES	23.3	0.71	27.42	0.69	23.43	0.62

Number	Name	SS1		SS2		SS3	
		Buildings	V_i	Buildings	V_i	Buildings	V_i
18	CAZAUX-LAYRISSE	38.86	0.73	43.74	0.68	46.75	0.62
19	CAZEAUX-DE-LARBOUST	80.74	0.72	85.66	0.7	77.75	0.62
20	CHAUM	143.07	0.73	164.94	0.67	179.28	0.62
21	CIER-DE-LUCHON	169.57	0.7	193.44	0.67	188.19	0.62
22	CIERP-GAUD	502.23	0.72	574.22	0.68	603.57	0.62
23	CIRES	32.36	0.71	37.58	0.65	35.6	0.62
24	ESTENOS	119.95	0.73	135.84	0.69	127.02	0.62
25	EUP	115.03	0.72	123.07	0.68	118.63	0.62
26	FOS	381.08	0.74	388.19	0.72	401.09	0.6
27	FRONSAC	157.41	0.72	172.51	0.72	187.68	0.62
28	GARIN	123.17	0.7	143.97	0.64	127.37	0.64
29	GOUAUX-DE-LARBOUST	57.17	0.69	62	0.72	71.38	0.69
30	GOUAUX-DE-LUCHON	58.83	0.71	64	0.68	71.49	0.69
31	GURAN	66.62	0.73	73	0.72	75.12	0.62
32	JURVIELLE	30.62	0.72	22.75	0.78	23.83	0.62
33	JUZET-DE-LUCHON	163.82	0.68	232.81	0.62	227.8	0.65
34	LEGE	38.9	0.74	42.81	0.75	46.3	0.62
35	LEZ	64.22	0.74	71.45	0.68	69.53	0.62
36	MARIGNAC	299.97	0.72	336.94	0.68	356.29	0.64
37	MAYREGNE	53.96	0.72	60	0.72	62.09	0.62
38	MELLES	183.85	0.74	193.72	0.73	174.25	0.65
39	MONTAUBAN-DE-LUCHON	157.99	0.67	248.94	0.65	253.42	0.62
40	MOUSTAJON	72.82	0.69	88.94	0.62	97.59	0.61
41	OO	84.03	0.7	98.68	0.7	109.8	0.67
42	PORTET-DE-LUCHON	27.66	0.72	30.53	0.74	31.79	0.62
43	POUBEAU	55.3	0.7	61.69	0.64	53.23	0.67
44	SACOURVIELLE	22.59	0.72	26.29	0.71	27.03	0.62
45	SAINT-AVENTIN	131.55	0.72	142.89	0.72	147.44	0.66
46	SAINT-BEAT	409.87	0.71	368.36	0.7	375.4	0.62
47	SAINT-MAMET	287.57	0.66	411	0.66	485.64	0.66
48	SAINT-PAUL-D'OUAIL	60.63	0.72	73	0.72	80.13	0.67
49	SALLES-ET-PRATVIEL	72.22	0.72	81.91	0.65	88.33	0.62
50	SIGNAC	47.82	0.71	53.4	0.75	58.38	0.62
51	SODE	20.73	0.73	21.65	0.76	22.34	0.62
52	TREBONS-DE-LUCHON	12.87	0.71	13.89	0.7	14.37	0.62
53	BINOS	27.3	0.71	28.6	0.71	36.68	0.64
		Total	Average	Total	Average	Total	Average
		6572.15	0.71	8103.84	0.69	8338	0.63
			Stdv		Stdv		Stdv
			0.02		0.04		0.02

5.1.2 Scenario results

5.1.2.1 Damage estimation for uniform ground acceleration ($PGA = 200 \text{ cm/s}^2$ on rock conditions)

First, we observe the results for the simulations with a uniform moderate ground acceleration of 200 cm/s^2 applied to the buildings, without considering the local soil effect (Figure 5-4). Scale scenario 1 (SS1) shows that 11.5% of the buildings would face heavy damage to complete collapse (D3, D4, and D5). On the other hand, scale scenarios 2 (SS2) and 3 (SS3) show similar estimates for the heavy to complete damage of the buildings (8.14% and 8.24%, respectively). We can conclude that the large-scale European building characterization overestimate the estimation of heavy damages to buildings by a factor of 1.4, compared to the National statistics database and the in-situ collected database. We also observe that SS2 estimated more undamaged buildings, D0 (a difference of 5%), than SS1 and SS3. These observations, resulting from the simulation run without considering site effects, are coherent with the observations related to the vulnerability indices shown in Table 5-2 as, in these estimates, the damage calculations are solely influenced by the vulnerability descriptions of the buildings: SS1 shows the largest average vulnerability values; however, SS2 shows the largest variability for the vulnerability.

Next, we observe the results of the simulations computed for the three scale scenarios, where the ground motion was amplified by the corresponding site amplification factors (Figure 5-5). SS1 (using the European soil map with an amplification factor up to 1.5 and the European exposure database) shows that 12.7% of buildings would face heavy damage to complete collapse, versus 18% following SS2 (using the regional soil map with an amplification factor up to 1.8 and the National statistics database) and 20.3% following SS3 (using the local soil map with an amplification factor up to 1.8 and the field-investigation database). The impact of the soil conditions is not linear/translational. We note that the low resolution of the European soil map in SS1 barely changes the results when comparing the results with and without consideration of the soil amplification map, with a difference factor of only 1.1. This factor is about 2.2 and 2.5, respectively, for SS2 and SS3. Thus, SS1 highly underestimates the proportion of heavily damaged to collapsed buildings (D3–D5). Even though SS3 has the lowest vulnerability indices, it estimates the largest damages, due to the site effects highly amplifying the local ground motion at buildings

An important increase of severe damage (D5) is observed for the three different scale scenarios when comparing the computations with and without soil amplification: when considering the soil maps using SS1, 4 additional buildings completely collapsed, versus 24 additional buildings for SS2 and 21 for SS3. This result cannot be extrapolated, as such, to some other regions and areas, as it is very dependent on the local geology.

Figure 5-4: The damage distribution per scale scenario considering the ground motion amplification due to soil effects. The colour shows the percentage of buildings per level of damage. The number shows the total number of damaged buildings.

Figure 5-5: The damage distribution per scale scenario considering the ground motion amplification due to soil effects. The colour shows the percentage of buildings per level of damage. The number shows the total number of damaged buildings.

Bal et al. (2010) studied the geographical resolution of exposure data and of the ground motion (PGA amplified by the soil effect) for the Sea of Marmara region in Turkey, using several different levels of spatial aggregation to estimate the losses due to a single earthquake scenario. They show that, if only mean estimates are needed, the effort required to refine the spatial definition of exposure data is not justified. The average damage values over the simulations are almost insensitive to the resolution of the ground motion field. Their results indicate that a significant reduction in the variability of these estimates can be achieved by moving to higher resolution ground-motion fields. As the effect of moving to higher resolutions is to introduce some regions with higher-than-average damage and others with lower-than-average damage, these two effects largely cancel each other out.

For the Luchon Valley area and for moderate earthquakes, we conclude that SS1 overestimates the heavy damages, when considering the building database only, and underestimates the heavy damages, when additionally considering the soil characterization maps. We also conclude that SS2 and SS3 generate comparable results, in terms of heavy damages. These results are in accordance with Kalakonas et al. (2020), who mention that the loss estimates become accurate and stable beyond a certain (fine) spatial resolution. They also propose that a potential way to reduce this type of uncertainty is by improving the detail of information, concerning the location of the building inventory; however, this process can be time- and resource-demanding and, in many cases, it is simply impractical (e.g., for risk analysis at the national level). Dabbeek and Silva (2020) recommend effective alternatives, involving the disaggregation of the exposure in each unit using night-time lights, satellite imagery, or the location of roads.

When we compare the simulations of the three datasets at the municipality level, the results are quite consistent; however, if we are interested in the infra-municipality level, better resolution of the building data can provide some information about the spatial distribution of damage inside a municipality.

We note that more outliers (or extreme values) are present for SS1 and SS2 than for SS3, where the latter database was collected from field inspections. The percentage of damages D3–D5 is, however, more uniformly distributed for SS3, compared to SS2 (for which the values of V_i are more variable). Pittore et al. (2020) conclude that an adaptive model is favorable, with higher spatial resolution in highly urbanized areas (where most of the assets are located) and lower resolution in rural, less-inhabited regions (where higher spatial aggregation could increase the robustness of the risk estimates).

When we consider the total amount of damages in the area, the difference in the heavy damage degree (D3) should be an important issue from the emergency management point of view, as this damage degree implies heavy structural damages and generally inhabitable buildings before inspection. In addition, these levels of damage can also result in road closures, which can have a very significant impact in terms of the routing of emergency resources as well as the evacuation of victims. Figure 5-6 presents the results of SS3, in terms of the percentage of heavily damaged buildings ($\geq D3$), represented at the municipality (as for the scenarios SS1 and SS2) and infra-municipality levels (homogeneous vulnerability census block). Figure 5-7 supports Figure 5-6, with numerical values for the three most populated municipalities (31500, 31360, and 31244) around the main municipality (31042; Bagnères de Luchon).

Damage distribution

% D3+D4+D5

Census block level

Municipality level

Figure 5-6: Percentage of damage degree superior to D3 for scenario SS3 for PGA of 200 cm/s² amplified by the site effects: representation to the level of the municipality and to the infra-municipality level (homogeneous vulnerability census block).

Figure 5-7: The damage distribution per municipality (last bar chart of each graphic) and per corresponding homogeneous vulnerability census blocks inside each municipality.

5.1.2.2 Application to two historical earthquakes

Several destructive earthquakes have occurred in the past around the Luchon Valley area, as evidenced by the historical seismicity database SISFRANCE (BRGM-EDF-IRSN: www.sisfrance.net; Scotti et al., 2004); including, in particular, two earthquakes that occurred in the 19th century –in 1855 and then in 1870 – with an epicentral macroseismic intensity of VII, felt in the Luchon Valley with maximum macroseismic intensities of VII and VI, respectively. However, the most important recent regional earthquake remains that of Viella, which occurred on November 19, 1923, in Spain in the Aran Valley, with an epicentral macroseismic intensity of VIII, felt with a macroseismic intensity of VII in the Luchon Valley: in Bagnères-de-Luchon, some walls, chimneys, and roofs had cracked. Considering the epicentral positions and the macroseismic intensity level in the area of interest, we evaluate the seismic damage in the Luchon Valley region for the two historical earthquakes (i.e., those of 1855 and 1923). Utilizing the characteristics of these two earthquakes (location, magnitude, and depth) determined by Manchuel et al. (2017) in their FCAT-17 parametric catalogue (Table 5-3), we use the GMM by Ambraseys et al. (2005) to estimate the ground motion in the region, in terms of PGA (Figure 5-8a,b). Then, the PGA estimated under rock site conditions is convoluted with site effects, following the three soil characterization maps corresponding to each of the three scale scenarios. The resulting PGA maps are shown in Figure 5-8 (c,e,g) and (d,f,h) for the two earthquakes, respectively, and the corresponding damages are computed.

Table 5-3: Parameters of the 1855 and 1923 historical earthquakes that affected the region of Luchon Valley, from the FCAT-17 parametric catalogue (Manchuel et al., 2017).

Year	Lat (deg)	Lon (deg)	Mw	Depth (km)
1855	42.833	0.5	5.4	12
1923	42.7	0.833	5.6	8

Concerning the 1855 earthquake (Table 5-4), due to the proximity of the epicentre to the study area, high PGA values are obtained, resulting in damages up to D4 and D5. The distribution of the damage differs from one scenario to another and it is very sensitive to the soil characterization map, as well as to the resolution of the building distribution. Without considering the site effects, SS1 generate higher D5 damages (almost double, compared to SS1 and SS2) and less D2–D3 damages, whereas SS2 and SS3 exhibit a similar distribution of damages. When considering the amplified ground motion due to site effects, the conclusions are reversed: SS2 and SS3 generate considerably more damages at levels D3–D5. Figure 5-9 shows the spatial distribution of damaged buildings at level D3. Here, we focus on the Bagnères-de-Luchon municipality, where important differences appear: only 10 buildings are expected to have D3 damage in this area when using SS1; however, 195 buildings are expected to have D3 damage when using SS2, and 190 in total with SS3, which are spatially dispersed.

Table 5-4: Percentage and number of residential buildings per damage level per scale scenario and the corresponding ground motion shown in Figure 5-8, for the earthquake event of 1855.

1855	D0			D1			D2			D3			D4			D5		
	SS1	SS2	SS3	SS1	SS2	SS3	SS1	SS2	SS3	SS1	SS2	SS3	SS1	SS2	SS3	SS1	SS2	SS3
%	65	50	43	21	25	27	9	14	18	4	7	9	1	3	3	0.1	0.4	0.3
#	4262	4065	3562	1359	2037	2292	608	1172	1471	252	584	745	81	214	243	10	31	26

Figure 5-8: The ground motion corresponding to the earthquakes of 1855 (Left) and 1923 (Right). The first row (a and b) shows the ground motion computed at rock site conditions with the GMM by Ambraseys et al. (2005). The surface ground motion is amplified due to the soil effect using SS1 (c and d), SS2 (e and f) and SS3 (g and h) soil characterization maps.

Figure 5-9: D3 damage distribution in the Luchon Valley area in number of buildings, at the 53 municipalities, due to the 1855 earthquake. The site effect is considered here.

For the event of 1923 (Figure 5-8), the epicentre being further away from the study area, low to moderate levels of PGA give rise to relatively similar distributions of damage. Damages are dominated by levels ranging from D0 to D3. Without considering any soil amplification, SS1 scenarios are the most conservative, whereas SS2 and SS3 generate a similar distribution of damages. When considering the amplified ground motion, this observation does not hold and SS3, followed by SS2, is slightly more conservative. Through observation of Figure 5-10, which shows the spatial distribution of D3 for the three scale scenarios in the municipality of Bagnères-de-Luchon, we can estimate that six buildings reach damage level D3 using SS1, and 11 buildings using SS2; however, checking SS3 at the infra-municipality level, we can notice that the buildings with damage D3 are spatially distributed with unit values. When collectively aggregated at the municipality level, the number rises to 10. SS2 and SS3 give similar results.

Table 5-5: Percentage and number of residential buildings per damage level per scale scenario and the corresponding ground motion shown in Figure 5-8, for the earthquake event of 1923.

1923	D0			D1			D2			D3			D4			D5		
	SS1	SS2	SS3	SS1	SS2	SS3	SS1	SS2	SS3	SS1	SS2	SS3	SS1	SS2	SS3	SS1	SS2	SS3
%	87	85	83	11	12	14	2	3	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
#	5691	6857	6897	712	1004	1162	147	211	243	21	30	34	1	2	2	0	0	0

Figure 5-10: D3 damage distribution in the Luchon area in number of buildings at the 53 municipalities, due to the 1923 earthquake. The site effect is considered here.

We can notice that, for the two studied events, the site effect has a large impact on the proportion of destructive damage, and SS2 and SS3 resulted in similar damage distribution estimates, with SS3 having a better spatial resolution of the building locations on the map. However, as this comparison is not based on damage observations, this study is not a validation of damage predictions, but rather an illustration of the variations expected in terms of loss assessment in the event of a major earthquake.

5.1.3 Impact on the use of damage scenarios for earthquake crisis management

Damage scenarios are useful tools in different phases of seismic risk management, from the preventive “inter-event” phase to the post-seismic phase of crisis management, including for (note that this is a non-exhaustive list):

- Pre-earthquake phases:
 - Awareness of local institutions and population about seismic risk;
 - Preparation for crisis management through the development of plans and performing exercises; and
 - Identification of the zones where supplementary risk studies are needed.
 - Seismic input: Historical earthquakes; uniform hazard spectra
- Post-earthquake phases:
 - Decision support for crisis management practitioners, mainly for civil protection services; and

- Estimation of economic losses following the occurrence of an earthquake.
- Seismic input: ground shaking scenario corresponding to the occurred earthquake

Besides the common interest in realistic damage assessment scenarios, each particular use corresponds to a different level of required precision, which may justify the use of more or less resolved input data. Regarding the specific issue of crisis management, Table 5-6 identifies the diversity of these requirements and the corresponding impact on the expected resolution of the damage assessments. This table suggests that intermediate-scale scenarios (e.g., SS2) are likely sufficient to meet a number of needs, for which the effort of acquiring very precise data (e.g., SS3) may not be justified. However, this discussion deserves to be conducted at the scale of a territory, on the basis of a broad analysis of needs, and including relevant stakeholders. Indeed, as soon as a single need justifies the acquisition of precise local data, it becomes relevant to use them for all damage scenarios carried out in this territory.

Table 5-6: Examples of damage scenarios that need to be related to crisis management activities, with qualitative assessment of corresponding required level of reliability.

Crisis Management Activity	Scenario Earthquake	Needs	Accuracy		
			Global	Expected Spatial Resolution	Expected Accuracy of Assessments
Crisis planning	Fictive	To get trends regarding the magnitude of the consequences of credible/dimensioning earthquakes, in order to adapt the response capacity, or even to carry out a pre-sectorization of intervention	Low to Moderate	<i>Due to the fact that the characteristics of the scenario earthquake(s) do not prefigure those of future real earthquakes, the spatial resolution of the scenarios does not need to be very fine (the scale of the municipality can in most cases suffice).</i>	<i>Quantitative estimates are considered to be orders of magnitude, with however a more pronounced expectation on the most marked damage levels (D3 to D5) which directly generate the severity of the crisis situation.</i>
		To get a quantified and spatialized assessment of damages, in order to propose a credible scenario on which to build a realistic exercise to test the crisis management procedures			
Rapid response	Real	To get quickly the most precise possible trends in terms of the extent of the consequences of a particular earthquake, so as to size the operational response (including requests for reinforcements), or even help to prioritize the allocation of resources by sector (search and rescue, post-seismic building diagnosis, ...)	Low to Moderate	<i>Immediately after the occurrence of an earthquake, the challenge is to be able to have as quickly as possible (around 30 after the earthquake) a first estimate, while the parameters of the earthquakes are still often uncertain (particularly location and depth). At this time, the required spatial resolution necessary remains moderate.</i>	<i>In the first hour after the earthquake, the precision required on the assessments remains moderate. More pronounced expectation on the most marked damage levels (D3 to D5), which directly generates the severity of the crisis situation.</i>
			Moderate to High	<i>As time passes and before the authorities can have a clear vision of the magnitude of the damages on the sole basis of their feedback from the field, there is a need to update the damage scenarios in order to improve their accuracy as much as possible. Widened interest in lower damage levels (D2) to judge the habitability of the building.</i>	

A major source of uncertainty in damage estimations is the intrinsically difficult inventory problem. Despite these limitations, it is important to thoroughly document the manner in which the inventories are established and damages are estimated, and that the main findings and conclusions are presented in a way that is useful and clear. Seismic damage studies which are properly conducted and used with an understanding of the strengths and limitations of the used method(s) can be of great value in planning, initiating, and updating programs for earthquake risk reduction and in emergency planning.

This section has explored the impact of the resolution of both the ground motion field due to the soil effect and building exposure data on the estimation of seismic damages. The study is limited necessarily to a single seismic ground shaking affecting the region, and the damage calculations are carried out using only one methodology.

For the Luchon Valley area and for moderate earthquakes, the use of the European soil map (with an amplification factor up to 1.5) and the European building database led to an underestimation of the heavy damage classes (D3–D5). Using the regional soil map (with an amplification factor up to 1.8) and the National statistics building database results in similar estimates to those using the local soil map (with an amplification factor up to 1.8) and a field-investigation database for the buildings; however, the spatial resolution to detect the locations of buildings of interest is unsurprisingly better when using the better-resolved exposure database. We would like to highlight that the main conclusions from this study are valid for the case of the Luchon Valley area and, as such, their application to other countries or cities should be carefully considered.

5.2 Study in TB-3 (Hveragerði, Iceland): Scenario-based seismic loss estimation accounting for ground motion variability

The most recent destructive earthquake in the south Iceland seismic zone was the Mw 6.3, May 29, 2008 Ölfus earthquake close to the town of Hveragerði (TB3). The town experienced intense near-fault strong-motion, characterized by large high-frequency accelerations and large amplitude near-fault velocity pulses recorded on a small-aperture strong-motion array (ICEARRAY-I). Horizontal peak ground accelerations (PGA) in the range of 38 to 88%g were recorded on the array. Despite the Ölfus earthquake being the costliest natural disaster in Iceland to date and caused widespread damage, there were no collapsed residential buildings and no casualties. In the context of the TURNkey H2020 project, comprehensive building exposure data has been compiled for TB-3 towns (see Deliverable 4.1) and collocated with the Open Street Map buildings through validation and integration. This database stores key information for each building, e.g., construction year, building material, number of storeys, floor area, replacement value, etc. Having complete building characteristics, the key building typologies are identified according to the SERA classification (ESHM20 project).

The ICEARRAY-I high-quality waveform recordings give the opportunity to compute various intensity measures (IMs) in unusually high spatial resolution. To explore the spatial variability of the selected IMs across the study area, Kriging spatial is performed to generate shake-maps for these IMs along with their corresponding uncertainties. The IMs considered are PGA and Pseudo-spectral acceleration (SA) at short-to-long periods.

Having detailed ground-motion data and complete building exposure database in Hveragerði gives the unique opportunity to perform loss estimation associated with the higher level of detail building typologies on the contrary to the simple classification of concrete, masonry and timber buildings considered in previous studies in Iceland. Moreover, the estimated IM shake maps for the Ölfus earthquake enables to perform high-resolution earthquake-specific loss estimation (i.e., building-by-building level) and compare the results with the classical loss estimation conducted at the municipality level. To this end, we carry out a detailed probabilistic seismic loss estimation at Hveragerði using the most recent global fragility curves developed by [Martins and Silva \(2020\)](#) as part of the global seismic risk model (ESRM 2020 project) as well as the local fragility and vulnerability model proposed by [Bessason et al. \(2020\)](#). For this, we take into account the variability of the spectral-based IMs and the replacement cost values (monetary value) at building locations through a logic-tree framework and their independent contributions to the risk metric are presented.

5.2.1 Building exposure dataset

The most recent building exposure database presented in Deliverable 4.1 for Hveragerði town is employed. The building-by-building databank, including all unit's information, is assembled in various formats such as Excel spreadsheet, GIS-based shapefiles linked to the Open Street Map, and MATLAB structure for clear spatial visualization and convenient use of the units and buildings' characteristics in future research studies.

In total, 1299 buildings are in the Hveragerði; of these 166 were constructed after 2008 when the Ölfus earthquake took place. Almost all buildings are low-rise with less than two storeys (97.7%). Moreover, in Iceland, structural walls dominate the lateral load resisting system in nearly all buildings. It is worth noting that prescribed wind loads in Iceland are among the highest in Europe. Therefore, the Icelandic buildings are constructed to withstand substantial lateral loads imposed by winds, which especially affects the design of light weight structures like timber buildings. For all building typologies (RC, timber, masonry), the floor slabs and the building foundations are built using reinforced concrete that ties the foundations together and makes them more earthquake resistant.

The horizontal histogram in Figure 5-11 indicates the number of buildings classified by detailed construction material in Hveragerði. The histogram illustrates that the critical construction materials are reinforced concrete, timber (wood) and cinderblock, which is an unreinforced masonry comprised of hollow pumice blocks with a low weighted density of $\sim 14 \text{ kN/m}^3$. Therefore, to assign a specific building typology according to the SERA classification, the detailed material-based classes are simplified to three categories as follows: 1) reinforced concrete including concrete and precast concrete classes, RC, 2) wood, W, and 3) unreinforced masonry including cinderblock, bricks and concrete's combination with blocks/bricks, MUR. It should be noted that masonry buildings are no longer constructed in Iceland. Note that 16% of the building stock (residential, public, commercial, and industrial) does not belong to any of these three classes, mainly due to their unknown construction material. Regarding the building occupancy classes in Hveragerði, the majority of buildings are residential (82%), whereas 14% of them are commercial/public and only 4% are industrial buildings, respectively (see the pie chart in Figure 5-11). For the present study's scope, only residential buildings in Hveragerði constructed before 2008 (the May 2008 Ölfus earthquake) are selected. The selected building

database includes 55.6% (421 number), 38% (288), and 6.4% (48) reinforced concrete (RC), timber (wood), and masonry material (MUR) buildings.

Figure 5-11: Left panel: Number of buildings in Hveragerði classified by their construction material. Right panel: percentages of buildings classified by their occupancy.

Figure 5-12 illustrates the distribution of buildings classified by their construction year across Hveragerði. 47% of buildings are built before 1976, when the first seismic code (i.e., ÍST 13) was implemented in Iceland. In 1989, the seismic code was upgraded and employed for building design until 2002 when Eurocode 8 and the corresponding National Application Documents were implemented in Iceland (Standards Council of Iceland/ Staðlaráð Íslands (SI) 2002). From the property database it can be seen that 22% of buildings in Hveragerði are constructed in the period 2002-2008 period. Notice that in an international context, the Icelandic building stock is relatively young, and for instance, in the SISZ region, no building in use was built before 1870 (Bessason et al., 2020).

Figure 5-12: Spatial distribution of buildings in Hveragerði over its respective street map classified by year of construction along with their corresponding histogram of number of buildings. ICEARRAY-I stations are plotted by black triangles over the Hveragerði town.

5.2.2 Intensity measures variability across Hveragerði

Iceland is the most seismically active country in northern Europe. The largest earthquakes take place in the two major transform zones of the country, one of which is the South Iceland Seismic Zone (SISZ), where earthquakes up to M_w 7 have occurred and caused damage in the predominantly flat rural agricultural region with a few small population centres/towns and all critical infrastructure and lifelines of modern-day society. Hveragerði is one of the small, populated towns located in the middle of the SISZ. It is one of the country's tourist destinations, and many critical infrastructure facilities are in Hveragerði. Through the centuries, it has been hit by several destructive earthquakes. The most recent destructive earthquake striking the town was the 29 May 2008 Ölfus earthquake (M_w 6.3). Exceptional high-quality strong ground motion waveforms were recorded during this event on the ICEARRAY I strong motion array.

5.2.2.1 Overall variability of IMs

In this section, a set of spectral-based IMs is computed from the processed waveforms of the Ölfus earthquake recorded by ICEARRAY-I stations. The near-fault seismic ground motion recordings were characterized by intense accelerations of a relatively short duration of 5-6 seconds and large amplitude near-fault velocity pulses. The variation of horizontal PGA in the area was considerable given the small area of the array, having a minimum between 0.43 to 0.53 g in the centre of Hveragerði to a maximum of 0.76 to 0.88 g in the eastern and western parts of the town, respectively. It should also be noted that the recording stations were located about 1-2 km from the vertical surface projection of one of the causative faults of this earthquake, a distance that can be considered to be negligible compared to the size of the fault.

Figure 5-13 shows the scatter of horizontal components of the Pseudo-spectral acceleration (SAs) for 5% critical damping ratio obtained from Ölfus earthquake accelerograms recorded by ICEARRAY-I stations across Hveragerði, corresponding to N-S (x), E-W (y) and the rotation-invariant average (ARI) of the components (Rupakhety and Sigbjörnsson, 2013). Figure 5-13 shows the very large values of SA exceeding 10 m/s^2 ($\sim 1.0 \text{ g}$) over short periods of 0.08-0.38 s. It should be noted that the recording stations were located about 1-2 km from the vertical surface projection of one of the causative faults of this earthquake, a distance that can be considered to be negligible compared to the size of the fault. For comparison, in the present seismic hazard map for Iceland with a 475-year return period, specified in the National Annexes for Eurocode 8, the reference PGA on soil class A (rock) is $a_{gR} = 0.5g$ for Hveragerði (SI, 2010), accordingly, the 5%-damping elastic response spectra is at 1.25g between the corner periods of 0.15s and 0.5s for ground type A.

Figure 5-13: Mean (black dashed line) and standard deviation (grey area) of spectral acceleration with 5% damping ratio corresponding to two horizontal components of N-S (a) and E-W (b), and the Average Rotation-Invariant (c) of the two components, determined using the ICEARRAY-I recordings of the May 2008 earthquake.

From Figure 5-13, the larger variability of SAs at $T < 0.6$ sec is clearly evident compared to longer periods. Since short-period motions are more susceptible to small-scale differences in source, path, and site effects that are not modelled (i.e., effectively considered random), we propose to interpret the horizontal orthogonal components combined through SA_{ARI} for $T \leq 0.5$ sec. On the contrary, the strike-parallel (y , N-S) component of SA showed different characteristics, namely a narrow-band near-fault velocity pulse at $T \sim 0.7$ sec, associated with a permanent surface displacement along the fault (Halldorsson and Sigbjörnsson, 2009). Therefore, for intermediate-to-long periods, it is suggested that both individual horizontal components of spectral acceleration are analyzed further for spatial interpolation maps, while for shorter periods, the priority is given to the average rotation-invariant component.

5.2.3 Spatial variability of IMs through Kriging analyses

Interpolation methods estimate the values in unsampled locations to transform the observed data into a continuous form, such as raster data formats. Kriging spatial interpolation is one of the most frequently used optimal interpolator offering a minimum sampling error variance. In this section, the Kriging geostatistical analysis is carried out to generate shake maps for the PGA and selected SAs over Hveragerði town and their corresponding uncertainty maps, which are essential for decision-making purposes. Kriging uses the variogram model to compute localized weighting parameter, in essence, the weights of neighbouring points based on the distribution of those values. To find the model that represents the slightest uncertainty, different semivariogram models are tested, and the sensitivity to the lag parameter is explored. For this reason, errors from Kriging were evaluated using fundamental statistical parameters such as root-mean-square-error, the variance of errors, and mean absolute error. For most IMs, an ordinary kriging method with a spherical semivariogram model is used.

Figure 5-14 exhibits the Kriged shake maps (left panels) at short periods, i.e., for PGA, and SAs at $T = 0.2$ s for the ARI horizontal component, i.e., the short-period ground motion intensity is interpreted using a measure that combines the two horizontal components, as mentioned above. The grey-scale maps indicate the uncertainty distributions at interpolated cells. The

darker the colour, the smaller the standard deviation. We note that the comparison between different shake maps is relative, as the different ranges of ground motion IM values are represented spatially by the same colour scheme and number of contours. Buildings are colour coded by construction year. Triangles depict the ICEARRAY-I stations, which are the observation points with inter-station distances of 50 to 1900 m over Hveragerði. The remarkably dense data provides the opportunity to construct detailed shake maps for a set of ground-motion IMs for the town and, consequently, explore the spatial correlation amongst a wide range of IMs. As expected, around ICEARRAY-I sites, the uncertainty is negligible. However, as the distance from the observation sites increases, the uncertainty increases as well. For all Kriged shake maps, the level of uncertainty is acceptable across the whole study area. Figure 5-14 shows that a consistent spatial pattern emerges with largest values being recorded on the E-W outskirts of the town with the centre's motions being persistently lowest, a phenomenon most apparent at SA of 0.2 s. This pattern was consistently seen for IMs for peak parameters at short periods.

Figure 5-14: The Kriged IM shake-maps, along with the uncertainty maps, for PGA, and SAs at $T = 0.2$ s across Hveragerði. The rotation-invariant average (ARI) horizontal component is used for Kriging geostatistical analysis. Buildings are colour coded by their construction year. Triangles indicate the ICEARRAY-I stations.

Figure 5-15 presents the Kriged shake maps for the x (N-S, left) and y (E-W, right) components separately and for SA at $T = 0.65$ s. The central part of town (around IS608, IS611 and IS609 sites) persistently exhibits lower acceleration values, whereas higher SAs are indicated in the town's outskirts (except at longer periods, not shown). The SA 0.65 s along the x -direction, as seen in Figure 5-15, is at the period of the narrow-band near-fault velocity pulse associated with permanent tectonic displacement in the fault direction. It shows very little spatial difference across the array. However, along the y -direction (E-W) the GM pattern of the forward directivity near-fault velocity pulse exhibits the previously described spatial pattern. Similar to the SA-shake maps at $T = 0.65$ s, the SA ($T=2$ s) x and y -shake maps present smaller values at IS610, however, larger values are recorded at IS608 and IS601 in southwestern part of the town. It is interesting to note that the observation at both x and y components are somewhat similar, presumably as near-fault velocity pulses are observed along both directions, even though they are of different physical origin and of different frequency extents.

Clues to the reasons why the central part of town exhibits lower motions can be found in the town's geology. A historical earthquake N-S fault has been mapped and lies directly through the centre of town (west of IS609, under IS611 and IS608 stations, and further south). Moreover, the fault serves as a conduit for geothermal water that reaches the surface, resulting in a geothermal area in the centre of town and a widespread geothermal anomaly around IS611 and towards the north (Sæmundsson and Kristinsson, 2005; Rahpeyma et al., 2016). Then, underneath the surficial lava layer of several meters is a softer sedimentary layer, resulting not only in a velocity reversal (Rahpeyma et al. 2016), but has been affected by the geothermal activity. This area is therefore believed to attenuate higher-frequency motions more effectively than the outskirts of town, where this effect is not observed in data or in local geology. These spatial differences in geology are also what is believed to contribute to the large scatter in the observed high-frequency motions, as exhibited in Figure 5-15. However, the high-frequency motions were comparable. Finally, we note that at longer periods, the size of the small-aperture array becomes comparable in size or even small compared to the seismic wavelengths, and such small-spatial scale effects are less systematically observed.

Figure 5-15: Kriged shake maps for SAs at $T = 0.65$ (top), and 2 s (bottom) across Hveragerði obtained for two horizontal accelerograms of x (N-S direction, left-side panels) and y (E-W direction, right-side panels).

5.2.4 Seismic loss estimation

One of the main objectives of the present study is to carry out a scenario-based risk assessment using the collated building database for detailed building typologies, considering the most recent local and global fragility functions, in two resolution levels of municipality and building-by-building. The scenario event utilized in the study is the M_W 6.3 Ölfus earthquake occurred in May 2008.

To this end, first, the key building typologies are identified according to the SERA taxonomy system (Crowley et al., 2020) developed in the European Seismic Risk Model 2020 (ESRM20) project. Based on the local engineer's expert opinion in Iceland, structures built before 2008 are designed based on less rigorous regulations than modern seismic codes; thereby, no buildings are classified as high ductility. Due to a few numbers of existing 3-storey buildings, they are classified as 2-storey building class. In total, buildings are classified into eight main typologies based on their level of ductility, construction material, lateral load resisting system, and building's height. The ductility level reflects different levels of seismic design. Herein, the structures are divided into two ductility levels. Namely, low ductility structures were built before 1976 that incorporated minimal seismic provision and medium ductility structures that

included some seismic design degree and made after 1976. Note that the first seismic code was implemented in 1976 in Iceland. The standard construction materials are CR (reinforced concrete), W (wood) and MUR+CB (unreinforced masonry with concrete blocks). Although the LLRS for almost all buildings is wall (LWAL), for timber buildings, a moment frame (LFM) is believed to be a more appropriate LLRS. The reason is the limited available fragility functions for wood buildings in the global library of fragility models (the fragility models associated with LWAL LLRS were considerably different from the reality). Table 5-7 presents the identified model building typologies for Hveragerði building stock, their associated short names, and the distribution of the number of buildings within each typology. The most prominent building typologies in Hveragerði are W1, CM1, and then CL1 with 35.4%, 31.7%, and 16.77% of the building stock, respectively.

The global fragility models developed by [Martins and Silva \(2020\)](#), hereinafter MS20, associated with the identified building typologies are employed. Considering the low-rise buildings in Hveragerði, the fragility models attributed to either PGA or SA at $T = 0.3$ s are utilized dependent on building height and availability of the fragility model. Then, the performance of the global fragility models is compared to the most recent local fragility and vulnerability model developed by [Bessason et al. \(2020\)](#), hereafter Bea20.

Table 5-7: Building typologies for residential buildings in Hveragerði according to the SERA taxonomy system.

Typology*	CR-LWAL-DUL-H1	CR-LWAL-DUL-H2	CR-LWAL-DUM-H1	CR-LWAL-DUM-H2	W-LFM-DUM-H1	W-LFM-DUM-H2	MUR-CB99-LWAL-DNO-H1	MUR-CB99-LWAL-DNO-H2
Label	CL1	CL2	CM1	CM2	W1	W2	M1	M2
No. of buildings	127	30	240	24	268	20	34	14
Average economic cost**	177171	154820	191982	169501	174292	156562	156152	152424

*: The building typologies are selected in accordance with building classes for which global fragility functions were available.

** : The average economic cost values are given in Icelandic Krona (ISK) per m^2 area floor for new construction

The significant spatial variation of the ground motion IMs over the small study area illustrates that the assumption of uniform distribution of a single ground motion parameter for a relatively small cell in seismic risk assessment can give deceptive results. In this regard, we conducted the scenario-based loss estimation in two resolution levels, at the highest geographical resolution of building-by-building as well as at a municipality level treating the whole town as one cell (2×2 km), i.e., all buildings information is aggregated and IMs refer to centre point of the cell.

Furthermore, to have an informed view of the seismic risk, two sources of uncertainty, namely: replacement value (monetary building values) and ground shaking IM, are incorporated in the loss estimation through a logic tree framework. The open-source algorithm, SELENA ([Molina et al. 2010](#)), has been adapted to estimate the seismic loss at Hveragerði town.

For high-resolution loss estimation, we employ the statistics of the inferred spectral-based IMs at building coordinates across Hveragerði obtained from their corresponding Kriged shake maps associated with PGA and SAs at short-to-long periods. Therefore, ground shaking values are provided in three logic-tree branches: the mean IM, upper bound IM, and lower bound IM, which are calculated by $\text{mean} \pm \text{one standard deviation}$, with weights of 70%, 15%, and 15%.

Moreover, for municipality level, the statistics of PGA and SAs are computed over recording stations and the same three logic tree branches with similar weights as for the high-resolution loss estimation are incorporated.

To determine the economic value, first, the replacement value for each building (dwelling) is normalized by the floor area. The mean and standard deviation of the normalized monetary values are calculated for the whole Hveragerði, corresponding to each building typology. Having the statistic of the monetary values (known as economic values), three branches of the economic values are defined considering the mean, mean - standard deviation (lower bound of the economic value) and mean + standard deviation (upper bound of the economic values) and hence incorporated within the logic-tree framework with weights of 60%, 20% and 20%. The same approach as ground shaking is assigned to calculate the monetary values at high and classical resolution levels.

5.2.4.1 Results and Discussion

Figure 5-16a presents the repair-to-replacement cost ratio (MDR) for eight building typologies predicted using MS20 fragility models in the classical municipality level (orange bars) and high-resolution of building-by-building level (blue bars). A dispersion in damage ratios must be considered by the logic tree branch when loss results are used to develop risk management strategies. Therefore, in this study, the 84th and 16th percentiles of the MDRs are indicated by grey transparent bars. As we expected, low ductility classes such as CL1 and CL2 result in higher losses than higher ductile buildings such as CM1 and CM2. Note that CL1 and CM1 includes 48% of residential buildings in Hveragerði. Note that by multiplying the MDR estimates illustrated in Figure 5-16a by the replacement costs reported in Table 5-7, the repair cost associated with each building typology can be obtained. To evaluate the performance of the local model in resultant risk metrics, the Bea20 vulnerability model is employed (see Figure 5-16b). Since the Bea20 models are applicable to three building classes of concrete, timber, and masonry, the MDR predictions determined from MS20 models in terms of eight building typologies are weighted based on the number of buildings in each class to be comparable with the Bea20 predictions in three classes (see Figure 5-16b).

According to Figure 5-16a, the MDR estimates associated with municipality level overestimate the ones from building-by-building resolution for most typologies, except for one-storey typologies comprises of large number of buildings such as CL1, CM1, and W1. In particular, in masonry building classes (M1 and M2), high-resolution MDR estimates are significantly lower. We emphasize that in both high- and low-resolution risk assessments conducted in this study, the spatial variability of IMs in the study area were captured through adopting specific logic tree branches for their corresponding median, lower and upper bound values.

As illustrated by the small loss predictions associated with CL1 and CM2 in Figure 5-16a, based on seismic risk assessment, the least vulnerable buildings are those made of reinforced concrete with wall LLRS, in particular with medium ductility. On the other hand, masonry building class (Figure 5-16b) with detailed typologies of M1 and M2 (Figure 5-16a) with the largest MDR estimated by both global and local models are the most vulnerable typology in Hveragerði. When Ölfus earthquakes struck in May 2008, less than 7% of the residential

buildings were masonry buildings, and they are no longer constructed in Iceland, which was an incredibly promising risk mitigation strategy. In Figure 5-16b, for concrete and masonry buildings, Bea20 indicates higher MDRs than MS20. For masonry buildings, the similarity of results between the classical MS20 and Bea20 predictions is noteworthy.

Considering the building-by-building resolution risk assessment, the total weighted combined MDR for the whole Hveragerði is estimated at 8.33%. Rupakhety et al. (2016) obtained a combined MDR of 6.4% for the three most affected towns (Hveragerði, Selfoss and Eyrabakki) after the May 2008 earthquake, assuming 61%, 32% and 7% of the total buildings constructed using concrete, timber, and masonry, respectively. Hence, the higher expected damage of this study for Hveragerði can be attributed to the larger extent of losses in this town relative to the other affected towns.

Figure 5-16: a) Mean damage ratio for eight building typologies predicted using MS20 fragility models, in classical municipality level (orange bars) and high-resolution of building-by-building (blue bars), along with its 84th and 16th percentiles (grey transparent bars). b) MDR for three building classes, predicted by MS20 fragility models and their comparison with corresponding values obtained from the Bea20 local loss model.

Figure 5-17 illustrates the lower and upper bound of MDR predictions obtained from MS20 fragility models for eight identified building typologies. The first and second rows show the sensitivity of the MDR estimates to the ground shaking variability and economic costs (monetary value) across Hveragerði. The estimated values can be compared with the mean MDR presented in Figure 5-6. For instance, for one-storey timber buildings, assuming upper and lower bound of ground shaking (PGA and SAs) at the center of Hveragerði district (classical resolution level), 23.51% and 4.31% of replacement cost would be spent on repairing the buildings in Hveragerði, respectively. The MDR variability due to economic values variation is smaller compared to the ground shaking IMs' effect. As an example, considering the same building class of one-storey timber buildings (W1), the upper and lower bound of MDR estimates corresponding to upper and lower monetary values of buildings for the whole Hveragerði are 13.95% and 11.04%, respectively.

Figure 5-17: The lower and upper bounds of MDR estimates for eight building typologies predicted using MS20 fragility models, accounting for ground shaking intensity variability (first row) and monetary value (second row) Application of knowledge-based exposure modelling framework

5.2.5 Application of knowledge-based exposure modelling framework

This section presents the application of damage scenarios using the knowledge-based exposure modelling framework in Deliverable 4.1. The fragility functions method (M1-TX) and the empirical method using vulnerability classes and EMS-98 (M2-TX-ST*) are applied in this study. The defined building typologies in Table 5-7 and the shake map with PGA values from Figure 5-14 are used to determine the specification of scenarios with classification of PGA values in Lower, Median and Upper bounds.

According to the explanations by TB-3 in the last chapter, new building stock are used for earthquake 2008 which include following changes:

- Just residential buildings are considered for this evaluation.
- Buildings with unknown material and year of construction are omitted from data inventory.
- Buildings with year of construction before 2008 are considered for this study.
- Just RC, Masonry and Timber structures are introduced for building typologies (see Table 5-7).

(a) Fragility functions method (M1-TX):

According to the defined structural types in Table 5-7, six types of structure groups are assigned for TB-3 which are shown in Table 5-8 with selected fragility curves.

Table 5-8: Assigned fragility functions to building types in TB-3

Type *	Selected fragility function (Most suitable) **
RC2_L	FF _{RC2_L-3}
RC2_M	FF _{RC2_M-2}
RC4	FF _{RC4_M-1}
M5	FF _{M5-1}
W2	FF _{Timber-2}
W1_M/H	FF _{Timber-14}

Explanations:

* refer to Annex 4.2 in Deliverable 4.1 for the types and the correlation with SERA taxonomies.

** refer to Table A4-3 in Deliverable 4.1 for the details of every function.

The results of whole mean damage distribution for constant PGA=0.2 g as well as its portion for each type of building typology are shown in Figure 5-18.

**Legend:

Mean DG	0-0.5	0.5-1	1-1.5	1.5-2	2-2.5	2.5-3	3-3.5	3.5-4	4-4.5	4.5-5

Figure 5-18: Mean damage grade distribution and its portion regarding to the building typology before 2008 for PGA=0.2g

Due to the high values of PGA, ranging from 4.35 to 8.71 m/s², which could be correlated to intensity (VIII < I_{EMS} < X) according to [Faenza and Michelini \(2010\)](#), applying method 1 through fragility functions led to high mean damage grade distribution which was not comparable with computed results and mean damage ratios from TB-3. Therefore, the related results for Most suitable scenario is shown for constant PGA = 0.2g for Hveragerdi to extract the portion of mean damage ratio for each building typology.

(b) Empirical method based on vulnerability classes and EMS-98 (M2-TX-ST*):

M2-TX-ST* method is performed based on assigned vulnerability classes using vulnerability tables in Annex 4.2 in Deliverable 4.1. The assigned vulnerability classes for five scenarios are shown in Table 5-9.

The comparison of mean damage grade portions as well as its distribution are shown in Figure 5-19 and Figure 5-20 respectively, using scenarios of M2-TX-ST* method for earthquake 2008 in Hveragerdi.

For the purpose of comparison of results between five scenarios in M2-TX-ST* method, Figure 5-21 shows the entire histogram of scenarios, with results from Figure 5-17, provided by TB3.

Table 5-9: Assigned vulnerability classes for building stock in Hveragerdi, Iceland using Annex 4.2 in D4.1.

Type *	VC Scenarios				
	Very Pessimistic (vp)	Pessimistic (p)	Most Likely (ml)	Optimistic (o)	Very Optimistic (vo)
RC2_L	B	BC	C	CD	D
RC2_M	C	CD	D	DE	E
RC4	C	D	DE	E	F
M5	B	BC	C	CD	D
W2	B	BC	C	CD	D
W1_M/H	D	DE	E	EF	F

Explanations:

* refer to Annex 4.2 in Deliverable 4.1 for the types and the correlation with SERA taxonomies.

VC Scenario

Very Pessimistic (vp)

Pessimistic (p)

Most Likely (ml)

Optimistic (o)

Very Optimistic (vo)

Mean damage grade

Figure 5-19: Comparison of mean damage grade distribution between assigned VC scenarios, Hveragerdi, using building stock before 2008 for EQ in 2008.

VC Scenario

Mean damage grade distribution in Hveragerdi, EQ 2008

Very Pessimistic (vp)

Pessimistic (p)

Most Likely (ml)

Optimistic (o)

Very Optimistic (vo)

****Legend:**

Mean DG	0-0.5	0.5-1	1-1.5	1.5-2	2-2.5	2.5-3	3-3.5	3.5-4	4-4.5	4.5-5

Figure 5-20: Mean damage grade distribution using VC scenarios for Hveragerdi, EQ 2008

Figure 5-21: Comparison of mean damage grade distribution between scenarios regarding to the building typologies using M2-TX-ST* for TB-3, Hveragerdi, EQ 2008

In order to compare the results provided by TB-3 (Figure 5-17) and the M2-TX-ST* results (Figure 5-21), mean damage ratios in Figure 5-21 need to be converted to mean damage grades following one of the recommended correlations by [Maiwald & Schwarz \(2020\)](#). Table 5-10 describes one of four defined criteria to make a connection between damage grade and damage ratio. After conversion, it was observed that the upper bound PGA results of Figure 5-17 are comparable to the very pessimistic results from M2-TX-ST* and the lower bound PGA results are comparable to the (most likely-very optimistic) range results for most building types.

Table 5-10: Defined criteria to relate damage grade and damage ratio ([Maiwald & Schwarz, 2020](#)).

Damage grade	Damage ratio
D0	0
D1	0.3-5
D2	5-20
D3	20-60
D4	60-100
D5	100

6 NEAR REAL-TIME SEISMIC LOSS ASSESSMENT OF STRUCTURES

This section, developed by [Tubaldi et al. \(2021\)](#), proposes a probabilistic framework for near real-time seismic damage assessment that exploits heterogeneous sources of information about the seismic input and the structural response to the earthquake. A Bayesian Network (BN) is built to describe the relationship between the various random variables that play a role in the seismic damage assessment, ranging from those describing the seismic source (magnitude and location) to those describing the structural performance (drifts and accelerations) as well as relevant damage and loss measures. The *a priori* estimate of the damage, based on information about the seismic source, is updated by performing Bayesian inference using the information from multiple data sources such as free-field seismic stations, global positioning system receivers and structure-mounted accelerometers. A bridge model is considered to illustrate the application of the framework, and the uncertainty reduction stemming from sensor data is demonstrated by comparing prior and posterior statistical distributions. Two measures are used to quantify the added value of information from the observations, based on the concepts of pre-posterior variance and relative entropy reduction. The results shed light on the effectiveness of the various sources of information for the evaluation of the response, damage and losses of the considered bridge and on the benefit of data fusion from all considered sources.

6.1 Introduction

The rapid assessment of the ground-shaking intensity and damage distribution in the aftermath of a major earthquake is of paramount importance for ensuring a timely emergency response, accurate loss estimation, and for providing accurate information to the public. It enables emergency management authorities to take action immediately after the earthquake and correctly allocate and prioritize resources to minimize further casualties and speed up recovery from disruption ([Erdik et al., 2011](#)).

Shake-maps have proven to be very effective tools for rapidly responding to earthquakes ([Wald et al., 2008a](#)). They are contour maps of several ground-motion parameters (also called intensity measures), such as peak ground acceleration and pseudo-spectral acceleration at different system periods estimated using empirical ground-motion models (GMMs) based on information on the earthquake source (magnitude and location) and instrumental data from available seismic stations. Some examples of similar approaches include works by [Gehl et al. \(2017\)](#), [Michelini et al. \(2008\)](#) and [Bragato \(2009\)](#). Shake-map information can also be combined with vulnerability curves (e.g. those provided by HAZUS - [FEMA, 2003](#)) for structural damage estimation in an area (see, for instance, the studies by [Wald et al., 2008a](#) and [Lagomarsino et al., 2019](#)).

Structural health monitoring (SHM) systems have also been proven to provide useful information for rapid seismic damage assessment ([Celebi et al., 2004](#); [Limongelli et al., 2017](#)). Most existing SHM methodologies rely on the use of vibration measurements through accelerometers to detect potential structural damage ([Soyoz & Fenq, 2008](#)). Encouraged by the recent technological developments in the field, global positioning system (GPS) receivers have also been increasingly used for damage detection ([Yi et al., 2010](#); [Yi et al., 2013](#); [Im et al., 2013](#); [Kaloop et al., 2017](#)). Yet, associating damage with dynamic features is heavily restrained by the instrumentation layout/specifications, environmental effects and even the algorithms or

methods used (Porter, 2004; Farrar & Worden, 2007; Reynders et al., 2014; Spencer et al., 2004). In addition to the specific sensing techniques focussed on a particular physical parameter, there are recent applications that make use of the multisensory environment and heterogeneous data for SHM (Ozer, 2016). This can take the form of converting sensor information from one domain to another for corrected or enhanced (Ozer & Feng, 2016; Ozer & Feng, 2017; Ozer et al., 2017) dynamic characterization, seeking changes in vibration behaviour as indicators of damage.

Seismic damage assessments should be carried out with probabilistic approaches, given the many uncertainties inherent to the problem. For example, even if the earthquake location and magnitude are known with good accuracy, significant uncertainty stems from the use of GMMs (Douglas & Edwards, 2016; Bommer & Crowley, 2006; Park et al., 2007; Crowley et al., 2008; Wald et al., 2008b). Moreover, SHM sensor measurements are affected by noise, errors and have limited accuracy. Acknowledging the important role of uncertainties, in recent years an increasing number of studies have combined SHM and performance-based earthquake engineering (PBEE) concepts for rapid quantification of earthquake-induced building losses (Celebi et al., 2004; Porter et al., 2006; Cremen & Baker, 2018; Hwang & Lignos, 2018).

Bayesian modelling is a natural choice for carrying out rapid earthquake damage assessments, as it permits the propagation of uncertainties through models and allows updating the a priori estimates when new information becomes available. In particular, BNs are ideal tools for describing the probabilistic relationships between the various parameters involved in the damage assessment and for integrating the available knowledge of the earthquake scenario and the structural response. In this context, Bayraktarli et al. (2005), Bensi (2010), Broglio et al. (2013) and Gehl (2017) proposed BN frameworks for risk assessment of urban infrastructure systems. Wu (2014) developed a Bayesian framework for estimating the seismic damage in a structural system both before and after an earthquake, combining earthquake early warning and SHM data. Bayesian modelling can also be useful for quantifying the added value of the information provided by sensors and monitoring systems (Zonta et al., 2014a; Cappello et al., 2016; Bolognani et al., 2018; Li & Pozzi, 2019; Long et al., 2020). Approaches commonly employed for quantifying the reduction of uncertainty due to the available information are based on the concept of pre-posterior variance (Zonta et al., 2014; Long et al., 2020; Zonta et al., 2014b, Thöns, 2018) or relative entropy reduction (Limongelli & Giordano, 2020).

In Section 6, a probabilistic framework based on BNs is developed to quantify the benefit of various sensors for seismic damage assessment of critical structures under earthquake loading. The proposed framework relies on heterogeneous sources of information, such as those provided by seismometers typically used for deriving shake-maps, structure-mounted accelerometers and GPS receivers. The framework is applied to evaluate the seismic damage of a two-span bridge model located in a zone of high seismicity. To the authors' knowledge, this is the first time that heterogeneous sensing techniques are used in a BN framework to update the estimates of the seismic losses of a system, and that the effectiveness of these sensing techniques is compared by using the pre-posterior variance and relative entropy reduction metrics.

The sub-section 'Seismic damage assessment' illustrates in detail the various stages of the seismic damage assessment, the parameters involved and the technologies that are available to measure them. The sub-section 'Bayesian framework' illustrates the BN developed to describe the relationship between the various parameters involved in the seismic damage assessment, and to update these parameters based on additional available information from different

sources. It also presents the alternative approaches for quantifying the uncertainty reduction stemming from the sensor data. The sub-section 'Case-study' illustrates the implementation of the method on the two-span bridge considered as a case-study. This is followed by a discussion of the results and the conclusion.

6.2 Seismic damage assessment

The Bayesian framework for seismic damage assessment combines four types of analyses, namely hazard analysis, structural analysis, response analysis and loss analysis, which is consistent with PBEE frameworks (Porter, 2003; Moehle & Deierlein, 2004). Since the focus of this study is the rapid damage assessment in the aftermath of an earthquake, the first stage is replaced by the assessment of the level of shaking at the site, given that the main characteristics of the earthquake are known. The subsequent subsections describe in more detail the four analysis stages, together with the involved parameters and the technologies for measuring them.

6.2.1 Seismic shaking analysis

This analysis provides an estimate of the probabilistic distribution of a given ground-motion parameter or IM at the site of interest given the following variables that are assumed to be known: the moment magnitude of the earthquake (M_w); the epicentre of the earthquake, if a point-source event is assumed, or the rupture location and its extent for finite-fault scenarios; and other parameters characterizing the fault such as the faulting mechanism, the fault geometry and the depth to the top of the rupture. The analysis is carried out following the Bayesian procedure developed by Gehl et al. (2017) for generating shake-maps. A GMM is used to estimate the ground motion at the site, given the earthquake's characteristics. The GMM is generally characterized by the following form:

$$\log(IM_i) = f(M_w, R_i, \mathbf{s}) + \eta + \zeta_i \quad (6-1)$$

where $f(M_w, R_i, \mathbf{s})$ is a function describing the lognormal mean of IM_i , that is, the IM at the location ' i ', based on the earthquake magnitude M_w , a measure of the source-to-site distance R_i and other parameters collected in the vector \mathbf{s} ; η is the inter-event (or between-event) error term from the GMM; and ζ_i is the intra-event (or within-event) error term from the GMM.

The inter-event error term describes the systematic variability in the ground motions throughout the region produced by different earthquakes of the same magnitude and rupture mechanism. The intra-event error describes the variability in ground-motion intensity at various sites of same soil classification and distance from the source during a single earthquake (Bommer & Crowley, 2006). Thus, following the studies by Park et al. (2007) and Crowley et al. (2008), the same inter-event variability is applied to all sites of interest within a given earthquake scenario, whereas the intra-event variability is represented by a spatially correlated Gaussian random field. This can be built based on the intra-event error terms ζ_i and the correlation coefficient ρ_{ij} between the ground-motion parameters at two sites i and j , for $i, j = 1, 2, \dots, N_{sites}$, where N_{sites} is the number of sites of interest. The corresponding covariance matrix of the ground-motion IM field has the following form:

$$\Sigma_{\text{IM}} = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{\eta}^2 + \sigma_{\xi_i}^2 & \cdots & \sigma_{\eta}^2 + \rho_{ij}\sigma_{\xi_i}\sigma_{\xi_j} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \cdots & \cdots & \sigma_{\eta}^2 + \sigma_{\xi_j}^2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (6-2)$$

where σ_{η} and σ_{ξ} represent the standard deviations of respectively the inter- and intra-event error terms provided by the GMM. Further details about this representation of the ground-motion field can be found in the study by [Gehl et al. \(2017\)](#) and in [Schiappapietra & Douglas \(2020\)](#).

The field observations of the ground-motion parameters at seismic stations can be used as evidence to update the prior estimates of the IM at the site of interest. The spatial correlation structure between the IMs at the monitored points and at the site plays a major role in the propagation of the observations ([Jayaram & Baker, 2009](#)).

6.2.2 Structural analysis

Structural analysis is performed to estimate the probabilistic distribution of one or more engineering demand parameters (EDPs), describing the response of structural and non-structural components, based on the seismic shaking intensity. A joint probabilistic seismic demand model should be considered to describe the relationship between the EDPs and the IM, by also accounting for the correlation between the various EDPs. This is very important because the correlation structure is a basis for updating the probabilistic distribution of one EDP (e.g. floor acceleration in a building) given the observation of another (e.g. storey drift).

Alternative approaches can be employed to develop the joint probabilistic seismic damage model (PSDM), such as multi-stripe analysis ([Scozzese et al., 2020](#)), incremental dynamic analysis ([Vamvatsikos & Cornell, 2002](#)), or cloud analysis ([Mackie & Stojadinovic, 2005](#)). In this study, cloud analysis is adopted. For this purpose, the structural model is analysed under a set of ground-motion records of different IM levels. The samples of the various response parameters (EDP_i , for $i = 1, 2, \dots, N_{EDP}$) are then fitted by a regression model. In particular, a bilinear model is considered in this study ([Tubaldi et al., 2016](#); [Freddi et al., 2017](#)), since it allows a better description of the evolution of the structural response with the seismic intensity. The model for the generic i th EDP has the following form (see Figure 6-1):

$$\ln(EDP_i | IM) = \left[a_1 + b_1 \ln(IM) + \ln \varepsilon_1 \right] H(IM - IM^*) + \left[a_1 + b_1 \ln(IM^*) + b_2 (\ln(IM) - \ln(IM^*)) + \ln \varepsilon_2 \right] \left[H(IM^* - IM) \right] \quad (6-3)$$

in which a_1 is the intercept of the first segment, b_i for $i=1, 2$ are the slopes of the two segments (see Figure 6-1), IM^* is the breakpoint IM , which is defined as the point of intersection of the two segments. The step function $H(\square)$ controls which of the two segments must be considered (i.e., $H = 0$ for $IM \leq IM^*$, and $H = 1$ for $IM > IM^*$). The probability distribution of each EDP is also described by the values of the error functions ε_i which are characterized by a lognormal distribution with lognormal zero mean and lognormal standard deviation β_i . Moreover, in order to define a joint probability density function (PDF) for the various EDPs, a covariance

matrix must be assigned, which has the same form as that of Equation (6-2). For this purpose, different correlation coefficients must be estimated for the two conditions corresponding to $IM \leq IM^*$ and $IM > IM^*$, thus leading to two correlation matrixes, Σ_{EDP}^I and Σ_{EDP}^{II} .

Figure 6-1: Illustration of the bilinear regression model.

A brief description of the EDPs considered in this study and relevant measurement techniques are given below. Table 6-1 summarizes the EDPs of interest and possible sensors to collect observations directly and indirectly.

Table 6-1: Engineering demand parameters and measurement possibilities.

EDP	COMPONENT PERFORMANCE	DIRECT MEASUREMENT	INDIRECT MEASUREMENT
Peak transient displacement (TD)	Global, structural components, non-structural components	GPS Receivers, Laser vibrometer, Transducers, Camera	Accelerometers
Residual displacement (RD)	Global, structural components	GPS Receivers, Laser vibrometer, Transducers, Camera	Accelerometers
Peak absolute acceleration (PA)	Non-structural components, bridge deck	Accelerometers	GPS Receivers

6.2.2.1 Peak transient displacements

The maximum absolute values of the transient displacements (or of geometrically derived quantities, such as drifts) during the time history of motion of a structure are important indicators of structural performance. Many vulnerability curves for structures are based on these EDPs. Peak transient displacements (TDs) can be derived from the time histories of structures' relative displacements with respect to the base, and a wide range of sensors (both contact and non-contact) can be used to measure them. [Lemnitzer et al. \(2014\)](#) employed transducers such as linear variable differential transformers (LVDTs) to measure the shear deformations of a wall across two floors of a building, whereas [Li et al. \(2020\)](#) proposed the use of smartphone cameras. [Trapani \(2015\)](#) developed SAFEQUAKE, a hinged bar instrumented with two bi-axial accelerometers measuring accelerations, one at each end of the beam and

remaining parallel to the building floors, and one bi-axial inclinometer or accelerometer measuring the tilt of the beam. There are also some applications of GPS systems for real-time monitoring of displacement measurements. However, GPS technology is limited by low sampling rates and because it only measures the displacements at the building roof or bridge deck level (Celebi, 2000).

6.2.2.2 Residual displacements

The residual drift or permanent deformations of structural components after the earthquake may be used to infer the degree of damage sustained by the structure. Many studies have investigated the correlation between maximum drifts and residual displacements (RDs; see study by Dai et al. (2017) for a recent review on the topic). However, most of these studies have aimed at developing empirical formulae to relate the RDs and TDs and to provide a deterministic relation between the two EDPs, without any information regarding the dispersion (Ruiz-Garcia & Chora, 2015) nor any consideration of its dependence on the seismic intensity. Probabilistic studies relating TDs and RDs or drifts are scarce. Goda (2010) developed a joint PDF for the probability distribution of TD and RD seismic demands using a copula. Ruiz-Garcia & Miranda (2010) evaluated and compared demand hazard curves for residual drifts and maximum transient drifts in multi-storey building frames. Uma et al. (2010) developed a probabilistic performance-based seismic assessment framework where the performance levels defined by pairs of maximum-residual deformations are derived using bivariate probability distributions. Yazgan and Dazio (2012) proposed a Bayesian approach for post-earthquake damage assessment using the information from known RDs to update the probability distribution of maximum transient drifts in building frames.

6.2.2.3 Peak absolute accelerations

Many non-structural components in buildings are damaged during earthquakes when subjected to large absolute acceleration demands rather than high drift demands. Suspended ceilings, parapets and light fixtures are typical building components sensitive to accelerations. Along with masonry infills, ceiling systems are the non-structural elements most prone to damage during an earthquake. Absolute accelerations are typically measured via accelerometers. Accelerations may also be derived by differentiating velocities and displacements but obtaining reliable estimates can be problematic unless smooth velocity or displacement signals with high sample rates are available. Excessive bridge accelerations can cause serviceability problems, and in case of an earthquake, may distort operational flow (e.g. driver safety – Siringoringo & Fujino, 2018). Although mostly disregarded, vertical bridge accelerations can sometimes be excessive and may necessitate external devices for control (Parvin & Ma, 2001).

6.2.3 Damage analysis

In this stage, the EDPs are used to estimate the level of damage of the structure, typically described by one or more damage states (DSs). In buildings, damage of structural components can be described as a function of the peak inter-storey drift ratio, and that of non-structural

components based on the peak absolute accelerations (PAs) (Cremen & Baker, 2018; Gkimprxis et al., 2020). In bridges, the damage of the bearings, shear keys, columns and abutments is controlled by kinematic quantities, such as displacements and curvatures. Bridge piers are often the most vulnerable components of a bridge (Tubaldi et al., 2010, 2012) and their damage can be expressed as a function of the peak drift ratio (Zhang & Alam, 2019) or it can be related to the maximum displacement ductility experienced (Choi et al., 2004; Dutta, 1999).

6.2.4 Loss analysis

In this final stage, various decision variables (DVs) can be calculated, such as repair cost, casualties and loss-of-use duration (money, deaths and downtime), based on the damage sustained by the structural components. Padgett et al. (2010) after Basöz & Mander (1999) associated loss levels with damage measures experienced by bridges. Lu et al. (2018) pursued a similar loss assessment scheme for buildings with multi-class damage descriptions. Similar to these studies, in this article, structural losses related to damage are formulated in terms of loss ratios (LRs), repair and replacement costs normalized by the bridge cost.

6.3 Bayesian framework

This sub-section presents the Bayesian framework developed for near real-time loss assessment and describes the methods used for quantifying the effectiveness of sensors for uncertainty reduction.

6.3.1 Bayesian network

This sub-section illustrates the BN developed to describe the probabilistic relationship between the parameters specified in the previous section, to perform predictive analysis and to update these parameters based on additional information from different observations (see Figure 6-2). The magnitude M_w and epicentre of the earthquake are assumed to be known, and three different types of information are assumed to be available to update the probabilistic relationship of the variables in the network: on-site seismometers located close to the site of the structure, providing information on IM levels; GPS data, updating the knowledge of the RD; and accelerometer data, updating the knowledge of the PA in the bridge deck.

The nodes of the BN represent random variables characterized by a PDF. In particular, nodes are related to their parent and child variables through edges stating conditional dependencies between variables (i.e. use of conditional probability distributions). The nodes that have no parents are termed as root nodes and they are associated with marginal probability distributions. Node junction patterns can take different forms such as collider (M_w and R to IM), fork (IM to EDPs) and chain (TD to damage, damage to loss) with varying dependency features. Two forms of probabilistic inference can be carried out in BNs: predictive analysis that is based on evidence (i.e. information that the node is in a particular state) on root nodes and diagnostic analysis, also called Bayesian learning, where observations enter into the BN through the child nodes. When evidence enters the BN, it is spread inside the network thereby updating the

probability distribution of the variables through one of the two forms of inference mentioned above.

Figure 6-2: Bayesian network illustrating the relationship between the parameters involved in the damage and loss assessment (observed quantities indicated with thick lines).

The seismic shaking is modelled by the deterministic root nodes that describe the magnitude of the earthquake event, M_w , and the vector \mathbf{R}_e that collects the distances between the source and the site, and the source and the seismic stations. For demonstration purposes, two seismic stations (represented by IM_2 and IM_3) are assumed here to be in the vicinity of the bridge site (represented by IM_1).

Following the study by [Gehl et al. \(2017\)](#), the inter-event variability is modelled by the root node W , which is parent to the three IMs of interest (i.e. the one at the site and the ones at the seismic stations) and follows a normal standard distribution. The intra-event variability is modelled via three root nodes, U_j , for $j = 1, 2, 3$, which also follow a normal standard distribution. The joint conditional distribution of the IMs, given W and U_j , can be expressed by the following relation:

$$\ln(IM_i|W, U_j) = \ln \overline{IM}_i(M_w, R_i) + \sigma_\xi \sum_{j=1}^3 t_{ij} U_j + \sigma_\eta W \quad i=1,2,3 \quad (6-4)$$

where \overline{IM}_i is the median value of the IM and $\ln \overline{IM}_i(M_w, R_i)$ is the lognormal mean, which is a function of M_w and R_i (see also Equation (6-1)), σ_ξ and σ_η are the lognormal standard deviations describing respectively the intra-event and inter-event variability, t_{ij} is a term of the lower triangular matrix obtained through a Cholesky factorization of \mathbf{R}_{IM} , which is the spatial correlation matrix expressing the correlation between the IMs at the various sites.

A similar approach is used for the PSDM describing the conditional distribution of the EDPs given the IM at the site, IM_1 . However, in this case, a bilinear model is employed, and thus two different error variables and correlation matrices have to be considered, one for $IM_1 < IM^*$ and the other for $IM_1 > IM^*$. Two other root nodes, denoted as $egps$ and $eacc$, are used to describe the measurement errors of the observations obtained with GPS and accelerometers. These error variables are assumed to be zero-mean normally distributed variables. Finally, a damage model is employed to describe the conditional relationship between the various DSs of the system and the EDPs, and a loss model to relate the losses to damage.

The BN detailed in Figure 6-2 is used to perform predictive analysis, starting from the prior distribution of the root nodes, and diagnostic analysis, entering an observation at the nodes IM_2 , IM_3 , RD_{obs} and PA_{obs} . For this purpose, the OpenBUGS software ([Lunn et al., 2009](#)) is employed, which is interfaced with the R statistical tool. OpenBUGS is able to treat both deterministic (e.g. M_w and R_e) and probabilistic (e.g. IM_i , $\ln(TD)$) variables, which are sampled through a Markov-chain Monte-Carlo (MCMC) sampling scheme. Each chain is built with a Gibbs sampling scheme, where variables are successively sampled from the posterior distribution of previous variables: the posterior distribution of a variable is obtained from the product of the prior distribution and the likelihood function (probability of a given observation occurring given the prior distribution). The samples are then aggregated in order to estimate empirical statistics of the variables of interest, which represent the posterior distributions. Although Bayesian inference based on sampling provides only approximate solutions (i.e. the posterior distribution is built from the samples), it has the benefit of being much more flexible than exact inference algorithms such as junction-tree inference (e.g. it allows modelling continuous variables using various probability distributions). Due to the approximate nature of the

posterior distributions sampled by the MCMC scheme, there is no absolute guarantee that exact distribution parameters may be obtained. However, various steps may be taken in order to ensure a reasonable accuracy of the results:

- Generation of multiple MCMC chains starting with different combinations of initial conditions, in order to ensure that all chains end up converging towards the same values.
- Generation of a high number of samples for each chain (e.g. several tens of thousands).
- Definition of a 'burn-in phase', where the first part of each chain is taken out from the estimation of the posterior distribution, in order to remove samples that have not yet converged.
- Thinning of the samples (i.e. only one sample in every five is considered in each chain), in order to reduce autocorrelation effects that are inherent to MCMC sampling.

Specific statistical tools in OpenBUGS are dedicated to the estimation of auto-correlation and of the minimum number of samples. In any case, preliminary tests are necessary to calibrate the sampling parameters carefully. The chosen sampling results from a trade-off between the required accuracy level and the computational cost.

6.3.2 Quantification of sensors' effectiveness for uncertainty reduction

6.3.2.1 Pre-posterior variance

The effectiveness of the monitoring strategy can be described based on the concept of pre-posterior variance (Zonta et al., 2014b), which represents the expected value of the variance of the random variable of interest (e.g. EDP) after monitoring is performed, that is, after Bayesian updating is carried out based on the available information. The pre-posterior variance accounts for all the possible combinations of outcomes of the monitoring system and thus it is independent of any specific observation. Compared with the prior variance, the pre-posterior variance gives an idea of how useful the monitoring process is in gaining information on the unknown parameter. A pre-posterior variance much smaller than the prior indicates that the proposed monitoring method improves our knowledge of the parameter. On the contrary, similar values of the pre-posterior and prior variances indicate that monitoring is not expected to bring any significant knowledge improvement.

Let $p(\theta)$ denote the prior distribution of a generic random variable θ , such as a node of the BN which is not deterministic, and $p(\theta|y)$ the posterior distribution, following an observation y . The expected value and variance of the posterior distribution of θ can be expressed as:

$$\mu_{\theta|y}(y) = \frac{\int_{D\theta} p(\theta|y) \cdot \theta \cdot d\theta}{\int_{D\theta} p(\theta|y) \cdot d\theta} = \frac{\int_{D\theta} p(\theta|y) \cdot \theta \cdot d\theta}{p(y)} \quad (6-5)$$

$$\sigma_{\theta|y}^2(y) = \frac{\int_{D\theta} p(\theta|y) \cdot (\theta - \mu_{\theta|y}(y))^2 \cdot d\theta}{p(y)} \quad (6-6)$$

Since the observation is unknown *a priori*, these quantities can be seen as function of the observation y . The pre-posterior variance can be obtained by taking the expectation with respect to y :

$$\sigma_{\theta,PP}^2 = E[\sigma_{\theta|y}^2(y)] = \int_{D_y} \sigma_{\theta|y}^2(y) \cdot p(y) \cdot dy = \int_{D(\theta,y)} p(\theta|y) \cdot (\theta - \mu_{\theta|y}(y))^2 \cdot d\theta \cdot dy \quad (6-7)$$

In practice, $\sigma_{\theta,PP}^2$ can be estimated with a Monte-Carlo approach. For this purpose, a set of possible monitoring scenarios are generated by performing predictive analysis and generating multiple samples of the possible observations. Each observation is then used as input in a diagnostic analysis to produce a sample of the posterior distribution of the variable of interest. The pre-posterior variance is then obtained by averaging the values of $\sigma_{\theta|y}^2(y)$ obtained for the different observations.

The expected effectiveness of the monitoring system is measured by the square root of the ratio between the prior and the pre-posterior variances:

$$\eta = \sqrt{\frac{\sigma_{\theta}^2}{\sigma_{\theta,PP}^2}} = \frac{\sigma_{\theta}}{\sigma_{\theta,PP}} \quad (6-8)$$

This synthetic parameter can be used to compare the reduction of uncertainty in the estimation of θ obtained via alternative monitoring techniques, and can also be used to evaluate the benefits of fusing the data from different sensors. It can be demonstrated that this parameter is always higher than 1, even though for some observations y the ratio between σ_{θ}^2 and $\sigma_{\theta|y}^2(y)$ can be less than 1.

6.3.2.2 Reduction of relative entropy

As an alternative to the pre-posterior analysis approach, a relative entropy measure can be used to quantify the information gain from the available observations. Relative entropy, also called Kullback-Leibler Divergence, expresses the difference between two probability distributions to identify the value of new information or more specifically, observations (Kullback & Leibler, 1951; Gray, 2011; Limongelli & Giordano, 2020). According to Shannon (1948), the information entropy for a random variable θ with posterior distribution $p(\theta|y)$ is defined as the following:

$$H[p(\theta|y)] = - \int_{D_{\theta}} \ln[p(\theta|y)] p(\theta|y) d\theta \quad (6-9)$$

The cross entropy between two posterior and prior probability distributions, which measures the expected information that is required to get from one distribution to another, is:

$$H[p(\theta|y), p(\theta)] = - \int_{D_{\theta}} \ln[p(\theta)] p(\theta|y) d\theta \quad (6-10)$$

The relative entropy $D_{KL} [p(\theta|y), p(\theta)]$ measures the so-called information geometry in moving from the prior to the posterior and can be expressed as:

$$D_{KL} [p(\theta|y), p(\theta)] = H [p(\theta|y), p(\theta)] - H [p(\theta|y)] = \int_{D_\theta} \frac{\ln [p(\theta)]}{\ln [p(\theta|y)]} p(\theta|y) d\theta \quad (6-11)$$

According to the formulation, the relative entropy of the observation and reference distribution is lower bounded by 0. In other words, the greater the difference between the two probability distributions, the greater the relative entropy gained from the arrival of observational data. As for the case of the pre-posterior variance, the relative entropy is estimated via a Monte-Carlo approach by averaging all the possible monitoring outcomes. Thus, the obtained effectiveness measure is independent of the specific observation y .

6.4 Case-study

In this subsection, the application of the framework presented above to a bridge structure is described.

6.4.1 Case-study description

6.4.1.1 Structural system model for damage and loss assessment

For demonstration purposes, the structural system considered in this study consists of a two-span bridge with a continuous multi-span steel-concrete composite deck, arbitrarily located in the area of Patras, Greece (longitude 21.906, latitude 38.278, in decimal degrees). The bridge is representative of a class of regular medium-span bridges commonly used in transportation networks (Dezi, 2008; Tubaldi et al., 2013), as shown in Figure 6-3. The bridge superstructure, designed according to the specifications given in Eurocode 4 (EN 1994-2, 2000), consists of a reinforced concrete slab of width $B = 12$ m, which hosts two traffic lanes, and of two steel girders positioned symmetrically with respect to the deck centreline at a distance of 6 m. Class C35/45 concrete is used for the superstructure slab. The reinforcement bars are made of grade B450C steel, and the deck girders are made of grade S355 steel. The distributed gravity load due to the self-weight of the deck and of non-structural elements is 138 kN/m, for a weight per unit length $m_d = 14.07$ ton/m. The reinforced concrete piers have a circular cross-section of diameter $D = 1.8$ m. They are made of class C30/37 concrete, with a longitudinal reinforcement steel ratio of 1% and a transverse reinforcement volumetric ratio $\rho_w = 0.5\%$. Further details about the bridge can be found in the study by Tubaldi et al. (2013).

Figure 6-3: a) Two-span bridge profile, b) transverse deck section (source Tubaldi et al., 2013).

A three-dimensional finite element (FE) model of the bridge is developed in OpenSees (McKenna et al., 2006) following the same approach described in the study by Tubaldi et al. (2010), that is, using linear elastic beam elements for describing the deck, and the beam element with inelastic hinges developed by Scott & Fenves (2006) to describe the pier. Further details of the FE model and of the pier properties are given in the study by Tubaldi et al. (2010). The elastic damping properties of the system are described by a Rayleigh damping model, assigning a 2% damping ratio at the first two vibration modes. The FE model described in this study is assumed to be deterministic and characterized by no epistemic uncertainties. Future extensions of the methodology will consider how introducing some uncertainty in the model (e.g. considering the approach outlined by Tubaldi et al., 2012) would affect the results. Figure 6-4 shows the hysteretic response of the pier to a bi-directional ground-motion record, in terms of moment-curvature of the base section, and base shear-top displacement, along the two principal directions of the bridge. It can be observed that the model is characterized by some degradation of stiffness and pinching, that results from the constitutive model adopted to describe the concrete fibres in the plastic hinge region (Concrete 02 in OpenSees). A more sophisticated description of the hysteretic behaviour of the pier is out of the scope of this study.

Figure 6-4: a) Base moment-curvature response and b) Base shear-top displacement response.

A set of 221 ground-motion records is used to derive the PSDM: 120 of these were selected by Baker et al. (2011) for the performance assessment of a variety of structural systems located in

active seismic regions. These records are representative of a wide range of variation in terms of source-to-site distance (R) (from 8.71 to 126.9 km), soil characteristics (the average shear wave velocity V_s in the top 30m of soil spans from 203 to 2016 m/s) and moment magnitude (M_w) (from 5.3 to 7.9), so as to obtain more robust and general results. It is noted that the V_s values of many of these records are higher than those assumed for deriving the seismic shaking scenarios considered here. This approach, potentially resulting in some bias in the estimation of the PSDM, is consistent with current practice. The remaining ground motions are taken from the recordings of different stations during the 1994 Northridge earthquake and they were added in order to achieve a more confident estimate of the response for high IM values. The large number of records in the set allows estimation with good confidence of the statistics of the response parameters, even of those which are characterized by a significant dispersion such as the residual displacement (Scozzese et al., 2020). The median horizontal (geometrical mean) spectral displacement response $S_d(T)$ at the fundamental period of the bridge ($T=0.45s$) for a damping ratio of 2% is selected as the IM . It is noteworthy that the GMM by Akkar & Bommer (2010), which is used in this study, is formulated in terms of the pseudo-spectral acceleration $S_a(T)$, which is related to $S_d(T)$ through the expression $S_a(T) = S_d(T)/\omega^2$, where $\omega=2\pi/T$. An amplification factor $\eta = 1.195$ is used to account for a 2% damping factor instead of 5%, based on the expression $\eta = \sqrt{\frac{10}{5+\xi}}$ taken from Eurocode 8 (Baker et al., 2011).

The PSDM described in Section 6.2.2 is fitted to the 221 samples of the various response parameters of interest for the performance assessment, namely the residual displacement ($EDP_1=RD$), the peak transient displacement ($EDP_2=TD$), and the peak absolute accelerations ($EDP_3=PA$). Figure 6-5 shows the sample values of the EDPs vs. IM in the log-log plane and in the untransformed plane. In the same figures, the lognormal mean and median of the fitted PSDM are also plotted. The same value of IM^* is used for the various EDPs. It is obtained by considering the samples of the RD s, since the change of slope is more evident from these. In fact, for $IM \leq IM^*$ the response of the system is in the linear range, and the residual displacements are zero, whereas for $IM > IM^*$ the residual displacements assume values different from zero and increase for increasing IM levels. It is noteworthy that the value of $IM^* = 0.0286$ m corresponds on average to a drift ratio of 0.68% (defined as the ratio between the peak transient displacement TD and the pier height), which signals the onset of nonlinearity of the system due to concrete cracking and rebar yielding. The peak top displacements and the absolute accelerations increase almost linearly with the seismic intensity and their trend of variation does not change significantly when IM exceeds IM^* .

Figure 6-5: Sample values and model results in terms of RD, TD, and PA vs. IM in the log-log plane (left column) and in the natural plane (right column).

The covariance matrices Σ_{EDP}^I and Σ_{EDP}^{II} , collecting the information on the variance of the error variables (in the lognormal space) and on their correlation, for the two branches of the PSDM (corresponding respectively to $IM_1 \leq IM^*$ and $IM_1 > IM^*$), are:

$$\Sigma_{EDP}^I = \begin{bmatrix} 3.700 & 0.271 & 0.039 \\ 0.270 & 0.222 & 0.114 \\ 0.039 & 0.114 & 0.156 \end{bmatrix} \quad \Sigma_{EDP}^{II} = \begin{bmatrix} 2.875 & 0.612 & 0.203 \\ 0.612 & 0.293 & 0.126 \\ 0.203 & 0.126 & 0.098 \end{bmatrix} \quad (6-12)$$

and the corresponding correlation matrices are:

$$\mathbf{R}_{\text{EDP}}^I = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0.299 & 0.0516 \\ 0.299 & 1 & 0.611 \\ 0.051 & 0.611 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{R}_{\text{EDP}}^{II} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0.667 & 0.382 \\ 0.667 & 1 & 0.744 \\ 0.382 & 0.744 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (6-13)$$

It can be observed that the residual displacements are characterized by a significant dispersion, which is much higher than that of the other EDPs. Moreover, the correlation between the error variable in the PSDM of RD and the error variable in the PSDMs for the other EDPs is quite low for $IM_1 \leq IM^*$, but it increases for $IM_1 > IM^*$. This is expected, since for $IM_1 \leq IM^*$ the residual drifts are very low. The highest correlations are observed between the errors for the PSDMs of RD and TD (correlation coefficient of 0.667 for the second branch of the PSDM) and for the PSDMs of TD and PA (correlation coefficient of 0.774). The correlation between RD and PA is quite low, though not negligible (correlation coefficient of 0.382). This suggests that the information on accelerations may be used to reduce the uncertainty in the estimation of the bridge maximum and residual displacements. It is noteworthy that the proposed approach is different from resorting to double integration of the measured acceleration signal for estimating the displacements, which is characterized by several limitations (see e.g. [Trapani et al., 2015](#)).

The damage of the bridge is assumed to be controlled by the pier. Similarly to [Choi et al. \(2004\)](#), the pier damage is expressed as a function of the ductility demand as follows:

$$DS = \begin{cases} \mu < 1 \text{ (no damage)} \\ 1 < \mu < 2 \text{ (DS1)} \\ 2 < \mu < 4 \text{ (DS2)} \\ 4 < \mu < 7 \text{ (DS3)} \\ 7 < \mu \text{ (collapse)} \end{cases} \quad (6-14)$$

where μ and DS denote respectively the ductility demand and the damage state of the bridge. The relationship between the pier top displacement TD and the ductility demand μ is evaluated by performing pushover analysis of the bridge in the longitudinal direction.

The losses are obtained using the equation below ([Padgett et al., 2010](#); [Basöz & Mander, 1999](#)):

$$Loss = \begin{cases} 3\% \text{ (} x < DS1 \text{)} \\ 8\% \text{ (} DS1 < x < DS2 \text{)} \\ 25\% \text{ (} DS2 < x < DS3 \text{)} \\ 100\% \text{ (} DS3 < x \text{)} \end{cases} \quad (6-15)$$

6.4.1.2 Seismic scenarios and field observations

It is assumed that the bridge is equipped with one accelerometer and one GPS antenna, both mounted at the level of the superstructure above the pier. The measurement error of the GPS antenna is characterized by a normal distribution with zero mean and a standard deviation of 1 mm, whereas the one of the accelerometer by a normal distribution with zero mean and a standard deviation of 0.002 m/s². These values are based on the noise root mean square (RMS) levels of exemplary low-cost sensor specifications extracted from representative datasheets (see e.g. [Yetitmoves, 2020](#), for the noise of a GNSS-based displacement measurement device and <https://www.st.com/en/mems-and-sensors/lis331dlh.html> for a low-cost MEMS accelerometer). The hypothetical bridge is located close to two existing seismic stations (see Figure 6-6). The first one (PATRA-C) is at the latitude 38.269 and longitude 21.760, whereas the second one (RIO) is at the latitude 38.296 and longitude 21.791. These coordinates correspond to a distance between the site and PATRA-C of 12.8 km, and between the site and RIO of 10.2 km. The distance between the two stations is 4 km.

The seismic hazard at the site is quantified by considering the seismic source zonation of the European Seismic Hazard Model ([Woessner et al., 2013](#)). The earthquake scenarios used in the next sections are two possible realizations obtained by sampling from this model. The prediction of the ground motions at the site from the considered earthquake point sources is made using the GMM by [Akkar & Bommer \(2010\)](#), assuming soft soil conditions ($V_{s30} < 360$ m/s) and a strike-slip fault mechanism. The spatial correlation model proposed by [Jayaram & Baker \(2009\)](#) is used to build the correlation matrix \mathbf{R}_{IM} expressing the correlation between the IMs at different sites. The terms of \mathbf{R}_{IM} are the correlation coefficients ρ_{ij} between the ground-motion parameters at two sites i and j , expressed as:

$$\rho_{ij} = \exp\left(-\frac{3r_{ij}}{b}\right) \quad (6-16)$$

in which r_{ij} is the distance between the sites and b is the correlation distance.

Figure 6-6: Map with indications of bridge site, seismic point sources for Scenario 1 and 2, and seismic stations.

It is noteworthy that the correlation distance varies significantly from site to site and from earthquake to earthquake, and it also changes with the structural period (Schiappapietra & Douglas, 2020). Equations for capturing the dependence of b on these parameters are provided by Jayaram and Baker (2009), from which the value of b for this study (15.9 km) is taken. As a result, the covariance matrix Σ_{IM} related to the IMs (IM_1 , IM_2 , IM_3 corresponding respectively to the bridge site and PATRA-C and RIO stations) in lognormal space, as well as the spatial correlation matrix R_{IM} between the sites, are estimated as follows:

$$\Sigma_{IM} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.105 & 0.021 & 0.026 \\ 0.021 & 0.105 & 0.056 \\ 0.026 & 0.056 & 0.105 \end{bmatrix} \quad R_{IM} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0.089 & 0.146 \\ 0.089 & 1 & 0.470 \\ 0.146 & 0.470 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (6-17)$$

It is worth noting that the correlation values between the sites are very low, which is due to the quickly decreasing spatial correlation model. However, the arbitrary case-study that is defined here is consistent with the usual seismic network density in Europe (e.g., exposed sites are often a dozen km or more away from the nearest seismic station). Since the information provided by the seismic stations in terms of uncertainty reduction at the bridge site are expected to be low due to the low correlation between IM_1 and IM_2 and IM_3 , the case of a ground accelerometer placed at the base of the bridge is also considered to quantify the maximum uncertainty reduction achievable by a perfect knowledge of the IM_1 .

6.4.2 Rapid damage assessment for a single scenario

This sub-section describes the results of the Bayesian updating for Scenario 1, which corresponds to the seismic point source 1, with Magnitude M_w 5, located 28.0 km from the site and 40.6 km and 38.2 km from respectively stations PATRA-C and RIO (Figure 6-6).

Predictive analysis is first run based on the information at the root nodes (including the deterministic ones, M_w and \mathbf{R}_e , that describe the earthquake scenario). Subsequently, multiple independent diagnostic analyses are performed by entering a piece of evidence one at a time at the nodes IM_2 , IM_3 , RD_{obs} and PA_{obs} and also by entering the information at these nodes at the same time. These analyses are performed with OpenBugs (Lunn et al., 2009) using three MCMC chains generated with different combinations of initial conditions. This is to ensure that the three different starting points converge towards similar posterior distributions. Each chain contains 10,000 samples, which are obtained by starting from 60,000 iterations, discarding the first 10,000 (burn-in) and thinning to reduce autocorrelation. Ultimately, a total of 30,000 samples is used to estimate the posterior distributions. It is noteworthy that the time required to perform a single Bayesian Inference analysis is quite low (of the order of a few seconds on a standard PC).

Figure 6-7 shows the empirical cumulative distribution function for the prior distribution of the various parameters of interest, and the posterior distributions given the observations of the GPS, accelerometers (Acc) and seismic stations (Map). The results obtained by combining the observations are also shown for comparison (Com). Table 6-2 reports median values and standard deviations of the prior and posterior distributions, together with the observations from the various sensors.

Figure 6-7: Empirical cumulative distribution function (CDF) of the parameters of interest before and after updating with observations from Scenario 1.

Table 6-2: Median and lognormal standard deviation of prior and posterior distribution of parameters of interest for a realization from Scenario 1.

Observation Source	Observation	RD		TD		PA		IM		LR	
		Median [m]	β	Median [m]	β	Median [m/s ²]	β	Median [m]	β	Median [-]	β
None (Prior)	-	$1.22 \cdot 10^{-5}$	2.873	0.0031	0.845	0.389	0.704	0.0019	0.744	0	0
Seismic stations	0.0011 m, 0.0000596 m	$1.20 \cdot 10^{-5}$	2.877	0.00270	0.828	0.351	0.696	0.0017	0.724	0	0
GPS	$2.8 \cdot 10^{-4}$ m	$1.02 \cdot 10^{-5}$	2.599	0.00260	0.834	0.343	0.691	0.0016	0.726	0	0
Accelerometer	0.672 m/s ²	$1.60 \cdot 10^{-5}$	2.897	0.00449	0.406	0.695	0.029	0.0028	0.447	0	0
Combined	-	$1.45 \cdot 10^{-5}$	2.491	0.005	0.446	0.694	0.029	0.0028	0.486	0	0

The prior distribution is characterized by low values of the various EDPs, as expected given the low magnitude and high epicentral distance of the source. Thus, the expected losses are zero. The residual displacements are very small, though significantly dispersed, with a value of lognormal standard deviation β of the order of 2.8, whereas the other parameters are characterized by smaller dispersion, with values of β of the order of 0.7-0.8. The information from the sensors generally results in a reduction of the uncertainty, corresponding to a steeper empirical cumulative distribution function (CDF) for the posterior distributions of the parameters of interest compared to the prior, and to a reduced lognormal standard deviation. The use of accelerometer outperforms the other sensing strategies in terms of uncertainty reduction. In particular, using accelerometers the dispersion of the absolute acceleration of the deck reduces from 0.7 to about 0.03, but the dispersion of the residual displacements remains unvaried, due to the low correlation existing between accelerations and residual displacement for low seismic intensities, such that the residual displacements are very low. The reduction of uncertainty of the residual displacements is not significant even if GPS are used, due to the significant noise to signal ratio, thus resulting in a reduction in the dispersion of the residual only by 10%. The overall reduction of uncertainty is more significant if the combined observations from the various sensors are used. However, there is only a minimal improvement to consider additional information from other sensors if the accelerometers are already used, as demonstrated by the fact that the distributions of all the EDPs with the exception of the RD for the Acc and Com cases almost overlap.

A larger earthquake (Scenario 2) is considered, which corresponds to a realization generated considering seismic point source 2, with Magnitude M_w 6.5, located 20.7 km from the site and 14.6 km and 12.7 km from respectively station PATRA-C and RIO (Figure 6-6). The results corresponding to this realization are shown in Figure 6-8 and in Table 6-3.

Figure 6-8: Empirical cumulative distribution function (CDF) of the parameters of interest before and after updating with observations from Scenario 2.

In this case, the prior distribution is characterized by relatively high values of the TD , resulting in a median drift ratio of 0.78%, which corresponds to an inelastic behaviour of the pier. However, the median value of the RD is still very low, as a result of the hysteretic behaviour of the pier and the stiffness degradation and pinching (see Figure 6-4). The realization considered is characterized by a high value of the observation of the accelerometer compared to the prior median estimate, which results in an increased median value of PA and of the other response parameters compared to the prior one. It is noteworthy that the posterior CDFs of all the monitored random variables (with the exception of the absolute accelerations) updated considering the observation of the accelerometer are characteristic of a bimodal distribution. This can again be explained by the observation of the peak absolute acceleration that is significantly different from the one median value of the prior (4 times higher). It is also worth to observe that there is also an increase of dispersion for all the parameters that are not directly measured by the accelerometers. The median value of the LR increases from 0 to 1, although the dispersion increases, too. Using the information from seismic maps also results in a general increase of median values and of dispersion of the parameters. This is because the observed values of IM_1 and IM_2 (respectively 0.0627m and 0.0904m) are higher than the median values of the prior estimates (respectively 0.0429m and 0.0488m). The GPS observations do not change significantly median values but reduce slightly the dispersions. Fusing the observations from the various sensors results in lower uncertainty in the estimates of the RD , TD , PA and IM compared to the prior estimates, whereas the uncertainty in the LR remains quite high. This trend may be explained by the fact that all the observed quantities (i.e., IM s at seismic stations, residual displacements and peak accelerations of the bridge) are consistently higher than the median prior estimates and thus when the observations are fused this result in a more confident and less disperse estimates of the EDPs. It is noteworthy that in order to properly quantify the uncertainty reduction, the average results from multiple realizations of observations must be considered, as discussed in Section 6.3.2 and done in the next sub-section.

Table 6-3: Median and lognormal standard deviation of prior and posterior distribution of parameters of interest for a realization from Scenario 2.

Observation Source	Observation	RD		TD		PA		IM		LR	
		Median [m]	β	Median [m]	β	Median [m/s ²]	β	Median [m]	β	Median [-]	β
None (Prior)	-	$9.2 \cdot 10^{-5}$	2.672	0.042	0.857	2.76	0.696	0.0272	0.744	0	0.04
Seismic stations	0.0627m, 0.0904 m	$6.67 \cdot 10^{-4}$	3.0744	0.077	1.040	4.826	0.855	0.0486	0.947	0.08	0.5
GPS	$5.4 \cdot 10^{-4}$ m	0.00023	1.841	0.057	0.702	3.955	0.607	0.0429	0.719	0.03	0.125
Accelerometer	8.103 m/s^2	0.0195	2.52	0.194	0.437	8.1	0.002	0.122	0.807	1	1.097
Combined	-	0.0008	0.919	0.101	0.172	8.1	0.002	0.065	0.282	0.25	1.339

6.4.3 Quantification of uncertainty reduction

This subsection describes the results of the quantification of the uncertainty reduction for the two earthquake scenarios of Figure 6-6. In particular, Figure 6-9 illustrates the evolution of the estimates of η for the various parameters of interest with the number of samples drawn from the Scenario 1 (moderate earthquake). The results for PA when accelerometer observations are used are not shown because they are significantly high due to the low noise to signal ratio. It can be observed that 1000 samples are sufficient to achieve quite accurate estimates of this monitoring effectiveness measure based on pre-posterior variance analysis for all the parameters of interest. For the case of the loss ratio LR , characterized by higher values of η and a lower convergence rate, 2000 samples are required. Considering more samples would not significantly increase the accuracy of the estimates. With this number of samples, confident estimates of the values of the relative entropy measure D_{KL} can also be achieved for all the parameters of interest.

Figure 6-9: Evolution with the number of samples of the monitoring effectiveness measure based on pre-posterior variance for the various parameters of interest and observation sources (Scenario 1).

Table 6-4 and Table 6-5 show the values of the effectiveness measures obtained based on respectively the pre-posterior variance and the reduction of relative entropy for Scenario 1 and 2. These estimates of η and D_{KL} are based on 1000 samples in the case of all the parameters except LR, for which 2000 samples are used. With regards to the first measure of effectiveness, it can be observed that the values of η are all higher than 1 as expected, since adding information from sensors can only reduce uncertainty on average. For the same reason, the combined observations from multiple sensors result in a higher effectiveness, due to the lower variance of the parameters of interest compared to that obtained with a single sensor's observation. GPS are the most effective sensors for reducing the uncertainty in the residual drifts, and their effectiveness increases with the seismic intensity, since for low intensities the noise-to-signal ratio of the RD is high (the RD are zero until the pier yields). Accelerometers are the most effective sensors for reducing the uncertainty of the PA, and also of the TD, given the significant correlation existing between PA and TD. The information from seismic stations located reasonably distant from the site does not provide any benefit in terms of uncertainty reduction, given the low correlation existing between the IM at the site and that at the stations. The reduction of uncertainty achieved for the losses is high in the case of low seismic intensity, and low for high seismic intensity. Moreover, in the case of low levels of shaking, sensors mounted on a structure can help to reduce the uncertainty in the estimation of the shaking intensity, and thus can be used to further improve shake-maps and achieve better estimates of the losses at structures not directly equipped with sensors. In the case of strong earthquakes, this effect of uncertainty reduction in the estimation of the IM is lost.

In order to shed further light into the reduction of uncertainty achievable with information on ground shaking intensity, the case of a ground accelerometer placed at the base of the structure is also considered, providing an upper bound of the benefit in terms of uncertainty reduction deriving from the use of shake-maps. It can be observed that if the seismic stations are located very close to the site, then the information they provide helps to reduce the uncertainty of the various parameters of interest. Similar observations were made in other studies (see e.g. [Douglas, 2013](#); [Ioannou et al., 2015](#)), indicating that a very dense network of seismometers in the vicinity of the site is required to obtain accurate estimates of the ground-motion intensity. With regards to the second measure of the sensors' effectiveness (D_{KL}), the observed trends are quite similar to those obtained for the first one, i.e., the accelerometer mounted on the structure is the most effective for estimating displacements and accelerations, the GPS for the residuals, and higher effectiveness is achieved fusing more and more data. The reduction of uncertainty associated with shake-maps observations is quite low, a bit higher in the case of higher seismic intensity. This phenomenon is again explained by the distance from the two seismic stations to the bridge site (i.e., around a dozen km), which is close to the spatial correlation distance of the [Jayaram and Baker \(2009\)](#) model, i.e. 15.9 km. As a result, the updates made to the values of the *IM* are much reduced, highlighting the need to deploy dense networks of seismic stations around exposed assets.

The only significant difference between the trends of the two effectiveness measures is for the LR estimates for Scenario 1, characterized by high values of η for the accelerometer and combined observations, and generally low values of D_{KL} for all the observations. The opposite trend is observed for Scenario 2. This discrepancy can be caused by the fact that the losses, are generally very small, with a median value of 0 of the prior distribution. Moreover, in contrast

to what is observed using the other effectiveness measurement, the reduction of uncertainty in the IM due to the observations is quite significant.

Table 6-4: Pre-posterior variance-based effectiveness measure for estimation of various parameters of interest.

Scenario	M_w [-]	R [km]	Observation Source	RD	TD	PA	IM	LR
1	5	30	Seismic stations (1)	1.002	1.015	1.011	1.025	1.000
			GPS (2)	1.110	1.012	1.000	1.017	1.000
			Accelerometer (3)	1.010	1.717	9.315	1.504	15.150
			Ground accelerometer (4)	1.003	1.982	1.507	28.020	4.575
			Combined (1,2,3)	1.120	1.730	9.327	1.524	15.150
			Combined (2,3,4)	1.124	2.321	10.009	28.280	42.580
2	6.5	20.7	Seismic stations (1)	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000
			GPS (2)	1.344	1.055	1.008	1.017	1.086
			Accelerometer (3)	1.000	1.477	49.220	1.000	1.921
			Ground accelerometer (4)	1.277	1.869	2.164	316.160	1.305
			Combined (1,2,3)	1.428	2.305	49.220	1.026	2.348
			Combined (2,3,4)	1.579	3.531	50.430	317.826	2.250

Table 6-5: Reduction of relative entropy-based effectiveness measure for estimation of various parameters of interest.

Scenario	M_w [-]	R [km]	Observation Source	RD	TD	PA	IM	LR
1	5	30	Seismic station (1)	0.045	0.193	0.164	0.472	0.012
			GPS (2)	9.004	0.195	0.152	0.323	0.017
			Accelerometer (3)	0.121	28.261	182.464	18.838	0.200
			Ground accelerometer (4)	0.094	31.891	11.628	211.279	0.176
			Combined (1,2,3)	9.729	28.625	182.279	18.960	0.201
			Combined (2,3,4)	11.403	58.142	184.095	211.551	0.200
2	6.5	20.7	Seismic station (1)	0.374	1.217	1.259	5.415	0.073
			GPS (2)	31.771	8.794	6.296	12.151	0.139
			Accelerometer (3)	31.983	72.592	215.994	111.206	34.637
			Ground accelerometer (4)	4.126	27.991	41.805	220.421	4.067
			Combined (1,2,3)	51.566	119.331	216.049	112.024	36.688
			Combined (2,3,4)	62.447	132.049	214.224	220.441	32.072

6.5 Conclusion and future work

This section illustrates a Bayesian framework for near-real-time seismic damage assessment of critical structures that exploits heterogeneous sources of information from shake-maps, GPS receivers, and accelerometers placed on the structure. Two alternative measures are proposed for quantifying the reduction of uncertainty from the observations, based on the concepts of pre-posterior variance and relative entropy reduction. The proposed framework is applied to

investigate the effectiveness of the alternative sensing strategies for the rapid estimation of the response and the losses at a bridge under a moderate and a strong earthquake scenario.

Based on the observed results, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- Among the sensors considered, the GPS provides the best results in terms of uncertainty reduction when used to compute the residual displacements of the piers, whereas the accelerometer placed at the top of the deck provides the best results in terms of reducing the uncertainty in the estimate of the maximum absolute accelerations and drifts. The expected effectiveness of shake-maps is quite low, unless a seismic station is located very close to the structure.
- The effectiveness of the sensors changes significantly with the shaking intensity. In the case of low shaking intensity, the effectiveness of the sensors in reducing the uncertainty is jeopardized by noise/measurement errors, particularly for the case of residual displacements. These errors become less significant in the case of high seismic shaking.
- When the data from different sensors are combined together through the proposed Bayesian Network, higher reductions of uncertainty are achieved when compared to when only single observation sources are considered.
- The reduction of uncertainty in the losses can be very significant, whereas that in the estimate of the seismic shaking intensity is generally quite low.
- The two measures of the monitoring effectiveness provide consistent results for most of the observed parameters and can be used interchangeably to quantify the reduction of uncertainty achievable with a monitoring strategy.

7 RAPID EARTHQUAKE LOSS UPDATING OF SYSTEMS VIA A BAYESIAN APPROACH

This section details the development of a BN framework for the damage and loss updating of spatially distributed systems (built areas, road networks).

7.1 Introduction

Rapid loss assessment following an earthquake event is of utmost importance for crisis managers, in order to quantify the extent of the disaster and localize ‘hot-spots’ before planning adequate emergency measures. Therefore, several rapid response systems have been developed worldwide, as detailed in the review by [Guérin-Marthe et al. \(2021\)](#). Such tools usually couple shake-maps (i.e., the updated field of ground-motion parameters, based on earthquake’s characteristics and recordings from seismic stations) with damage and loss assessment models (i.e., fragility or vulnerability functions). While such systems are mostly applied to common buildings and the estimation of casualties, the treatment of the performance loss of critical infrastructure and its consequences remains mostly overlooked. Only a few rapid response systems include the damage estimation of infrastructure components (e.g., USGS ShakeCast system; [Lin et al., 2018](#)), and none of them evaluate losses at system level so far. The inherent complexity of infrastructure systems, composed of interdependent components of various types, poses extra challenges in terms of modelling and simulation time ([Franchin, 2014](#)).

Moreover, [Guérin-Marthe et al. \(2021\)](#) introduce a distinction between two types of rapid response systems:

- Procedures that do not account for near-real time observations: the characteristics of the earthquake (e.g., magnitude, location, style-of-faulting) are just used to generate a ground-shaking map from a ground-motion model (GMM). Then, this map is fed into damage and loss estimation models in order to generate a very quick overview of the situation (TELES, [Yeh et al., 2006](#); QLARM, [Trendafiloski et al., 2011](#)).
- Procedures that couple shake-maps of the event with damage and loss estimation models in order to account for near-real time observations (e.g., USGS PAGER, [Wald et al., 2010](#); ELER, [Zülfikar et al., 2017](#); SEISAID, [Auclair et al., 2014](#)).

In the latter case, integrating strong-motion recordings of the event into the shake-map provides more accurate estimates of the intensity measures (IMs) at the vulnerable sites, thus leading to more reliable prediction of losses. However, it should be noted that, in most cases, only the mean values of the shake-map are used in the loss assessment step, ignoring the fact that GMM outcomes describe a full probabilistic distribution of IMs, even when conditioned on observations. A rigorous rapid response system should ensure the propagation of the uncertainties due to the estimation of ground shaking up to loss predictions. Therefore, this section investigates a proof-of-concept rapid response procedure that would integrate the following features, in answer to the aforementioned gaps: (1) loss estimation for built areas and infrastructure systems, (2) integration of various types of observations to constrain the predictions, (3) propagation of all sources of uncertainty, from hazard to losses, and (4) ability to treat real-world systems over large areas.

In order to address points (2) and (3), Bayesian Networks (BNs) have emerged as a very promising mathematical tool, well adapted to seismic risk analyses that mobilize a probabilistic framework and dependencies between many variables (Bensi et al., 2011). The inference operations on a BN enable the combination of the initial estimates (i.e., prior distribution provided by predictive models) and of field observations (i.e., providing evidence at some nodes) in order to generate updated posterior distributions of the variables of interest, under Bayes' rule. Therefore, thanks to their probabilistic inference capabilities, BNs constitute an adequate solution for the updating of damage and loss estimates in the crisis phase (Bensi et al., 2015). Regarding the ground-shaking part, a shake-map algorithm based on Gaussian BNs has also been proposed by Gehl et al. (2017). Bensi et al. (2013) have demonstrated the application of BN modelling techniques to the seismic risk assessment of infrastructure systems, thus ensuring the feasibility of point (1).

However, physical infrastructure components are usually strongly interconnected, and most of them contribute to the performance of the system (e.g., sets of bridges contributing to numerous possible routes in a road network). As a result, evaluation of the system performance measure (S) based on the combination of the states of n components is one typical case of dimensionality curse, as the size of the system node S (i.e., linked to the number of parent nodes) grows exponentially with n (i.e., combinatorial explosion). Such limitations hinder the application of exact inference algorithms to large real-world systems (Cavalieri et al., 2017; Gehl et al., 2018), i.e. point (4).

Bensi et al. (2013) have explored various strategies based on the BN's topology in order to alleviate the scalability issue: they advocate the grouping of components into parallel or series sub-systems through the identification of minimum link sets (MLSs) or minimum cut sets, thus limiting the amount of edges converging towards a given node. These BN formulations are all based on discrete variables: continuous variables (e.g., IM) are discretized into interval sets in order to be combined with variables that have discrete states by default (e.g., damage states of a component). More recent efforts have focused on solving this issue by improving data structures in discrete BNs and reducing memory storage via conditional probability matrices (Byun et al., 2019). This matrix-based BN framework has been further generalized by Byun & Song (2021) to be applied to multi-state systems. Thanks to the decomposition into minimum link sets (MLSs) and the identification of super-components (i.e., sub-sets of components that are only in series or parallel), Applegate & Tien (2019) have also proposed a computationally efficient approach that has the capacity to deal with interdependent infrastructure systems.

Alternative BN frameworks have also been proposed, such as the use of a compression algorithm to reduce the memory storage space of the conditional probability table of the system node S (Tien et al., 2016, 2017). On the other hand, Pozzi & Der Kiureghian (2013) have investigated Gaussian BNs, which consist of continuous variables and have therefore the merit of greatly reducing the sizes of (discrete) conditional probability tables (CPTs). However, this approach requires all variables to be represented by a Gaussian distribution, which is not the case of the components' states (i.e., discrete damage states). This strong limitation prevents the use of exact inference algorithms, and approximate inference engines, such as importance sampling or Gibbs sampling, have to be used instead.

The aforementioned issues have been identified and characterized by Cavalieri et al. (2017), who examined current challenges posed by the BN modelling of real-world infrastructure systems, in terms of both computational complexity and level of system analysis (i.e.,

formulation of the system performance measure). These considerations have led to the development of an approximate BN approach (Gehl et al., 2018), where an incomplete naïve formulation (i.e., a set of component nodes converging towards the system node) is learned from off-line stochastic loss scenarios: although less straightforward to implement, this method is able to deal with large real-world systems and to estimate elaborate system performance measures (i.e., not limited to connectivity analyses). However, this approach is based on the sampling of numerous earthquake events in the exposed area, based on the regional seismicity, which is not required in a rapid response context where the earthquake parameters (location, magnitude) are usually known with reasonable accuracy within minutes (Cremen & Galasso, 2020). Moreover, the corresponding BN uses discretized variables in an exact inference scheme, so that the width of the intervals (discrete states) may influence the accuracy of the results.

Most of the aforementioned studies have mostly focused on the component-to-system links (e.g., Byun et al., 2019; Applegate & Tien, 2019; Tien et al., 2016), assuming for instance that components are roots nodes in the BN, associated with a marginal probability of failure, or that a single root node IM points towards all component nodes. However, in the context of post-earthquake rapid assessment, the accurate consideration of hazard-related variables leading to component failure probabilities (and their respective correlation structure) is of utmost importance to reach situation awareness. While the modelling of the spatial correlation of seismic IMs has been extensively described by Bensi et al. (2011), its coupling with component and system variables adds yet another layer of complexity. Moreover, seismic responses of components may also be cross-correlated, further complicating the structure of the BN. If a discrete BN formulation is adopted, assuming 20 interval sets for each IM variable (which is not a very accurate description of all possible values) may lead to CPT sizes of up to 20^n for n vulnerable sites. Strategies to simplify the spatial correlation structure, such as Dunnett-Sobel decomposition (Dunnett & Sobel, 1955), may be used; however, they also constitute a form of approximation that becomes less accurate for a large number of sites. As an example, the approximate BN approach by Gehl et al. (2018) has partly solved the component-to-system scalability issue; however, the computational bottleneck has been moved to the joint estimation of IM at the locations of all bridges in the system.

Therefore, pending the development of *ad hoc* BN algorithms that are able to address some of the scalability issues, it is proposed here to adopt a more pragmatic approach based on a sampling inference algorithm (i.e., Monte-Carlo Markov-Chain sampling). This procedure, implemented in the OpenBUGS software (Lunn et al., 2009), has the benefit of avoiding some of the scalability issues and of considering different types of variables (continuous and discrete). The objective here is not to introduce new inference algorithms, but rather to exploit state-of-the-art techniques in order to demonstrate the use of BNs in an operational capacity during the rapid response phase. To this end, the following features are put forward in the proposed loss updating procedure:

- Joint estimation of the probabilistic distribution of damage to residential buildings and connectivity loss of a road network;
- Integration of two types of observations (i.e., evidence), namely the knowledge of the IM at some locations of the exposed area (either via accelerometric stations or via macroseismic testimonies) and the estimation of the damage state (DS) of some physical components (from structural health monitoring techniques);

- Modelling of the spatial correlation of IMs, as well as the correlation between seismic capacities of components;
- Idealization of the road network into a conceptual *Super-Network*, in order to reduce the number of components to process;
- Decomposition of the system into MLSs for connectivity analysis.

Taken separately, none of the above-listed features constitute original developments; however the main novelty resides in their integration under a unique framework in order to facilitate the treatment of large real-world systems. Section 7.2 details the proposed BN approach for the loss updating of a road network and a built area. A small numerical example is developed in Section 7.3, in order to demonstrate the approach and check the accuracy of the sampling scheme. Then, Section 7.4 applies the BN framework to a real-world area, namely a road network connecting dozens of municipalities in the Pyrenees mountain range (TB-2, France). Finally, results are discussed in Section 7.5, where a sensitivity study is also carried out to investigate the influence of parameters that have been seldom studied, such as the correlation between the seismic capacities of the exposed physical components (i.e., bridges and building typologies).

7.2 Proposed approach to update losses from observations

This section describes the procedure that is put forward to update losses in a rapid response context, by making use of various types of field observations. First, the main principles are outlined, along with the datasets and models that are required for the updating. Then, the process to conceptualize the physical road network into an abstract *Super-Network* is detailed. Finally, the implementation of the BN in the OpenBUGS software (Lunn et al., 2009) is discussed.

7.2.1 Main principles of the loss updating procedure

The proposed loss updating procedure, summarized in Figure 7-1, is articulated around two main types of data:

- '*Static*' data, which includes the conventional models and datasets that are needed to perform conventional risk assessment: knowing the characteristics of the earthquake (magnitude and location), a GMM is applied to estimate the IM distributions at the locations of the exposed elements, accounting for soil amplification factors. Vulnerability models and fragility curves are also used to predict the damage probabilities of exposed elements, given the IM distributions. Finally, in the case of a road network, the knowledge of the graph topology is also needed in order to access system performance measures such as the network connectivity between two points (Argyroudis et al., 2015). All these models put together result in the prior distributions of the variables of interest (i.e., *IM*, *DS*, *S*).
- '*Live*' data, which represents the observations (strong-motion recordings and damage identification of bridges) that can be entered as evidence in the variables *IM* and *DS*. The objective is to constrain the prior estimates by generating posterior distributions of the variables of interest, given the evidence.

The road network is subjected to a pre-processing step, with the objective of simplifying the initial graph topology into an abstract *Super-Network* that is specifically suited to connectivity analysis. This step has the effect of reducing the network's size and complexity, thus facilitating the identification of MLSs. All the data is then entered in a BN structure, which is solved with OpenBUGS: the sampling inference algorithm generates Monte-Carlo Markov Chains (MCMCs), which contain numerous samples of all variables, given the evidence. These samples are finally used to build empirical posterior distributions, with the effect of improving situational awareness for crisis managers. The loss updating procedure is able to generate a wide range of outcomes, such as damage distributions in built areas, damage probabilities of bridges or the probability that the road network connectivity is lost. The seismic response of bridges may also be updated, given the observations of some damaged bridges, so that updated fragility models may be built and applied to subsequent earthquakes.

Figure 7-1: Proof-of-concept of the procedure for the rapid earthquake loss assessment of built areas and infrastructure systems.

7.2.2 Road network processing

The proposed BN model currently relies on the estimation of the connectivity loss of the network, i.e. whether two given locations along the network are still connected or not (binary indicator). Since the analysis is limited to simple connectivity, it is proposed to reduce the complexity of the problem by building a conceptual network (i.e., Super-Network) based on the physical one, via the following steps (see Figure 7-2):

- Starting from a physical network with n nodes and m edges (among which, q bridges represent vulnerable edges), only nodes that have a degree equal to 1 (extremities of the network) or strictly above 2 (intersections) are kept as nodes of interest.
- By virtually removing the q vulnerable edges from the adjacency matrix of the network, it is possible to quickly identify all nodes that are accessible from each other without crossing a bridge (i.e., the nodes that stay connected with each other in the altered adjacency matrix).
- These nodes are grouped into a Super-Node: by definition, all nodes belonging to the same Super-Node are always connected with each other. If a bridge is used to connect two nodes within the same Super-Node, it may be removed from the network (such as bridge #4 in Figure 7-2). This assumption is only valid when performing a simple connectivity analysis since other performance measures based on travel distance or duration would require the knowledge of alternate paths and so on.
- The sets of bridges (i.e., vulnerable paths) that are linking two Super-Nodes are identified: this step is facilitated by the fact that only nodes of degree 2 may constitute vulnerable paths (i.e., extremities and intersections are absorbed in Super-Nodes). These paths are referred to as Super-Edges, and they represent sub-systems of bridges in series. Bridges may be then represented by the coordinates of their centroids.

This step leads to a dramatic reduction of the size of the network: in the example in Figure 7-2, the initial topology of 15 nodes and 17 edges is simplified into a Super-Network of 2 Super-Nodes and 2 Super-Edges.

Figure 7-2: Illustration of the construction of a Super-Network from a physical network.

In order to identify all MLSSs, the recursive algorithm proposed by Cavalieri et al. (2017) has been implemented. It only considers edges (initially, pipelines in a water supply systems) as vulnerable components, which is perfectly compatible with the notion of Super-Edge (i.e., representing an in-series system of vulnerable bridges). The recursion starts with the graph G containing all edges and it identifies the shortest path between a predefined origin and destination. Then an edge is removed, and the search for the shortest path continues on the reduced graph G^* . Each time, the shortest path is stored into the list of MLSSs, until the whole network has been explored.

7.2.3 Proposed BN modelling

BNs organize random variables in the form of a directed acyclic graph, where the dependencies between the various nodes are represented by conditional probabilities. An inference is performed on the BN when one or more nodes are observed (i.e. evidence is entered by specifying a given state) and when the probabilities of the other nodes are updated. In the case of a forward analysis, evidence may be entered at the root nodes, and the updated distributions can be estimated at the child nodes (e.g. distribution of infrastructure losses given the occurrence of some natural hazard events). Conversely, a backward analysis consists in the inference of the root nodes based on the observation of a given child node (e.g. updated distribution of the seismic intensity level given the observation of a given loss level).

It is proposed here to build a BN with the OpenBUGS tool (Lunn et al., 2009), which enables the modelling of continuous and discrete variables in the same BN. The OpenBUGS library is freely available and integrated in the R (www.r-project.org) environment (see demonstration script in Deliverable Report D4.9). This tool has been used in various seismic risk applications, such as the derivation of empirical fragility functions for residential buildings (Ioannou et al., 2020), the updating of damage models for water pipelines (Gehl et al., 2021), or the integration of various types of observations for the identification of structural damage (Tubaldi et al., 2021). The trade-off is the use of approximate inference, via MCMC sampling, instead of exact inference such as the junction-tree algorithm (Huang & Darwiche, 1996).

For a given earthquake event, the knowledge of epicentre location and magnitude is assumed. Then, as shown in Figure 7-3, the variables involved in the loss assessment are the following:

- The vector \mathbf{IM} represents the distribution of the logarithm of the ground-motion parameter of interest (e.g., peak ground acceleration, PGA) at the locations $i = 1 \dots n$ (for n exposed components) and $j = n+1 \dots n+m$ (for m recordings from seismic stations). It follows a normal distribution of mean $\boldsymbol{\mu}_{\log \mathbf{IM}}$ and covariance $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{IM}}$.
- The vector \mathbf{C} represents the distribution of the logarithm of the seismic response of the n components, also expressed in terms of IM. It follows a normal distribution of mean $\boldsymbol{\mu}_{\log \mathbf{c}}$ and covariance $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{c}}$.
- The variables DS_i represent the binary damage states (0 = failure, 1 = survival) of the n components. Each DS_i is determined as follows:

$$\begin{cases} DS_i = 0 & \text{if } IM_i > C_i \\ DS_i = 1 & \text{if } IM_i \leq C_i \end{cases} \quad (7-1)$$

- The variables MLS_k represent the binary states of the q MLSs. In the case of a road network, $MLS_k = 1$ if the MLS route is accessible (i.e., no failed bridges along the itinerary, if we assume that bridges constitute the weak link of the transport infrastructure), and 0 if not. An MLS_k composed of p components follows the Boolean rule of an in-series system:

$$MLS_k = DS_1 \times \dots \times DS_p \quad (7-2)$$

- The variable S represents the performance measure of the system. In the case of a road network, it corresponds to the accessibility between two given points A and B of the network. Thanks to the MLS decomposition, it follows the Boolean rule of an in-parallel system:

$$S = MLS_1 + \dots + MLS_q \quad (7-3)$$

With q MLSs, S takes discrete values between 0 and q , thus representing the number of possible routes between A and B.

Figure 7-3: Proposed BN formulation for a system decomposed into MLSs and for built areas.

While the left part of the BN in Figure 7-3 is relevant for the performance analysis of an infrastructure system (such as the connectivity between two locations along a road network), it is also possible to expand the study by considering the damage to common buildings. In this case, following the approach detailed in [Sedan et al. \(2013\)](#), built areas are represented as polygons (representing building blocks or city districts) of homogeneous seismic vulnerability. Then, the distribution of damage states within each built area is obtained by applying the semi-empirical vulnerability method by [Lagomarsino & Giovinazzi \(2006\)](#). A vulnerability index V is assigned to each built area, and the mean damage grade μ_D is expressed as a function of the

EMS-98 macroseismic intensity I_{EMS} (which is obtained from the distribution of IM via ground-motion intensity conversion equations):

$$\mu_D = 2.5 \left[1 + \tanh \left(\frac{I_{EMS} + 6.25V - 13.1}{2.3} \right) \right] \quad (7-4)$$

Ultimately, the proportion of damage states in each built area, based on the EMS-98 scale (Grünthal, 1998), is obtained by applying a discrete beta distribution based on μ_D (Lagomarsino & Giovinazzi, 2006). Then, by considering a vector \mathbf{V} of vulnerability indices, of mean $\boldsymbol{\mu}_v$ and covariance $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_v$, the BN framework for the damage assessment of common buildings may be defined as in the right part of Figure 7-3.

The probabilistic variables (\mathbf{IM} , \mathbf{C} , \mathbf{V}) are entered in the OpenBUGS environment, along with the mathematical expressions (e.g., Equations 7-1 to 7-4) that are needed to define deterministic variables (DS , MLS , S , I_{EMS} , μ_D). Evidence may be entered for IM_j (representing ground-motion measurements, as in shake-map procedures), for DS_i (the measurement of the damage state of some components) and μ_D (assuming a field inventory of damages in some built areas).

The Bayesian inference is performed by initiating several MCMC chains, with different combinations of initial conditions (i.e., starting values of the probabilistic variables). Each chain is built with a Gibbs sampling scheme, where variables are successively sampled from the posterior distribution of previous variables: the posterior distribution of a variable is obtained from the product of the prior distribution (e.g., the initial estimate of IM) and the likelihood function (probability of a given observation occurring given the prior distribution).

Within each chain, a large number of samples are generated until convergence is considered to be reached, by running tests as a calibration step as shown in Section 7.5.1. The generated samples are then used to estimate empirical statistics of the variables of interest (i.e., posterior distributions).

7.2.4 Definition of prior distributions

The prior distributions of the variables that are probabilistically defined (\mathbf{IM} , \mathbf{C} , \mathbf{V}) are assumed to follow normal/lognormal distributions, whose parameters are obtained from predictive uncertain models.

In the case of \mathbf{IM} , the mean of the logarithm of the ground-motion parameter distribution ($\boldsymbol{\mu}_{\log \mathbf{IM}}$) is given by a ground-motion model (GMM), based on the earthquake characteristics that are assumed to be known with confidence shortly after the event. The covariance matrix $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{IM}}$ is assembled as follows:

$$\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{IM}} = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_\eta^2 + \sigma_{\xi i}^2 & \cdots & \sigma_\eta^2 + \rho_{ij} \sigma_{\xi i} \sigma_{\xi j} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \cdots & \cdots & \sigma_\eta^2 + \sigma_{\xi j}^2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (7-5)$$

where σ_η and σ_ξ respectively represent the standard deviations of the inter- and intra-event error terms, which are given by the GMM. The term ρ_{ij} represents the spatial correlation of the

intra-event error between sites i and j , and it may be defined by available models in the literature (e.g., [Jayaram & Baker, 2009](#)).

The seismic response \mathbf{C} of components is provided by fragility curves, where the elements of $\mu_{\log c}$ correspond to the median fragility, and the standard deviations of \mathbf{C} correspond to the fragility dispersion β . The dispersion term β may be further decomposed into β_R and β_M , which respectively represent the uncertainty due to record-to-record variability and the uncertainty due to imperfect knowledge or modelling of the component ([Crowley et al., 2019b](#)). A third type of uncertainty, related to the definition of the damage state threshold, is neglected here for simplification purposes. Therefore, the covariance matrix $\Sigma_{\mathbf{C}}$ is expressed as follows:

$$\Sigma_{\mathbf{C}} = \begin{bmatrix} \beta_{Ri}^2 + \beta_{Mi}^2 & \cdots & \rho_{ij}^R \beta_{Ri} \beta_{Rj} + \rho_{ij}^M \beta_{Mi} \beta_{Mj} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \cdots & \cdots & \beta_{Rj}^2 + \beta_{Mj}^2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (7-6)$$

The term ρ_{ij}^R , representing the correlation of the response due to record-to-record variability between components i and j , is very difficult to quantify without the knowledge of the seismic records used in the derivation of the fragility curves. A qualitative rationale may postulate that components i and j – that are spatially very close to each other – may experience ground motion inputs with similar characteristics in terms of duration, frequency content, etc. and therefore their record-to-record variability should be fully correlated. On the other hand, spatially-distant components are likely to be subjected to different ground-motion (e.g., different spectral shapes), and therefore their record-to-record variability should be uncorrelated. Such considerations are discussed in [Silva \(2019\)](#), who advocates the use of a correlation structure similar to the one that models the spatial correlation of the intra-event error. Although deserving further investigation, this assumption is also used here for the characterization of ρ_{ij}^R .

The correlation of the component-to-component variability within the same class/typology, represented by ρ_{ij}^M , also requires more knowledge of how the corresponding fragility curves are derived. Therefore, it is proposed to consider the extreme cases in the application (see Section 7.4), namely fully correlated or uncorrelated variability, in order to investigate the impact of these assumptions on the posterior distributions. The decomposition of the dispersion into β_R and β_M is not always detailed in available fragility models (i.e., only the global dispersion β is specified). Various assumptions regarding this decomposition are also tested in the application example.

Finally, the vulnerability indices \mathbf{V} of built areas are obtained from a field inventory by structural engineers. The standard deviations of the elements of \mathbf{V} may be obtained from the upper and lower bounds of the vulnerability estimates (e.g., see Table 3 of [Lagomarsino & Giovinazzi, 2006](#)). Regarding the correlation structure, the same issues discussed for the definition of $\Sigma_{\mathbf{C}}$ hold for $\Sigma_{\mathbf{V}}$.

7.3 Numerical verification of the sampling algorithm

This section investigates the accuracy of the OpenBUGS BN on a synthetic test-case. To this end, a Gaussian BN is introduced as the reference solution for the small studied system.

7.3.1 Definition of the synthetic system

The accuracy of the sampling-based inference scheme used in OpenBUGS is firstly investigated on a trivial synthetic system. Two components arranged in-series (e.g. two bridges that must be crossed to go from one point to another) are considered: they are respectively 10 and 15 km away from an earthquake epicentre (with assumed magnitude M_w 6.3). A PGA observation is added, located at a site 12.5 km from the epicentre (at an equal distance between the two components). Therefore, the corresponding BN is built for a vector \mathbf{IM} containing 3 elements (the first two representing the sites of the components, and the last one the observation), and a vector \mathbf{C} containing 2 elements (one for each component). The marginal and conditional probabilities of all variables involved in this BN are expressed as follows, using the same convention as in Section 7.2.3 (Equations 7-1 to 7-3):

$$P_{\mathbf{IM}}(\mathbf{im}) = \phi(\log \mathbf{im}, \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\log \mathbf{IM}}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{IM}}) = \phi\left(\log \mathbf{im}, \begin{bmatrix} 0.3346 \\ 0.0878 \\ 0.2025 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 0.1815 & 0.0740 & 0.1132 \\ 0.0740 & 0.1815 & 0.1132 \\ 0.1132 & 0.1132 & 0.1815 \end{bmatrix}\right) \quad (7-7)$$

$$P_{\mathbf{C}}(\mathbf{c}) = \phi(\log \mathbf{c}, \boldsymbol{\mu}_{\log \mathbf{C}}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\mathbf{C}}) = \phi\left(\log \mathbf{c}, \begin{bmatrix} -0.0083 \\ -0.0083 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 0.2000 & 0.0400 \\ 0.0400 & 0.2000 \end{bmatrix}\right) \quad (7-8)$$

where $\phi(\cdot, \boldsymbol{\mu}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma})$ is the multivariate normal probability density function, of mean $\boldsymbol{\mu}$ and covariance $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}$.

$$\begin{cases} P(DS_1 = ds_1 | im_1, c_1) = (1 - ds_1) \cdot H(im_1 - c_1) + ds_1 \cdot H(c_1 - im_1) \\ P(DS_2 = ds_2 | im_2, c_2) = (1 - ds_2) \cdot H(im_2 - c_2) + ds_2 \cdot H(c_2 - im_2) \end{cases} \quad (7-9)$$

where $H(\cdot)$ is the Heaviside function, $ds_i = 0$ denotes failure and $ds_i = 1$ denotes survival, for $i = 1, 2$.

$$P(S = s | ds_1, ds_2) = (1 - s) \cdot (1 - ds_1 \cdot ds_2) + s \cdot ds_1 \cdot ds_2 \quad (7-10)$$

where $S = 0$ denotes disconnection (at least one of the in-series bridges has failed) and $S = 1$ denotes accessibility.

7.3.2 Verification method

Such a system is small enough to be solved with a BN using an exact inference algorithm such as the junction-tree technique. However, the discretization of all continuous variables (\mathbf{IM} , \mathbf{C}) also represents a challenge that could lead to inaccuracies in the outcome. Therefore, it is proposed to apply a Gaussian BN to the problem described in Section 7.3.1. A Gaussian BN contains only continuous variables with normal distributions and it also has the benefit of being compatible with exact inference algorithms. The Gaussian BN is presented in Figure 7-4, with the following set of variables and their related distributions:

- $U_i, i = 1..3$: Standard normal variables that are used to model the correlation between the IMs.

$$U_i \sim \mathcal{N}(0,1) \quad (7-11)$$

- $V_i, i = 1..2$: Standard normal variables that are used to model the correlation between the seismic capacities of the components.

$$V_i \sim \mathcal{N}(0,1) \quad (7-12)$$

- $IM_i, i = 1..3$: Logarithm of the IM of interest (here, PGA), which follows a normal distribution where the mean is the linear combination of conditioning variables U_i .

$$IM_i \sim \mathcal{N}(IM_{0,i} + \sigma_i \sum_{j=1}^i t_{ij} U_j, \varepsilon^2) \quad (7-13)$$

In Equation (7-13), the terms t_{ij} are elements of the transformation matrix \mathbf{T} , which is used to generate a correlated vector \mathbf{Z} of standard normal variables by transforming the independent variables U_i (assembled into the vector \mathbf{U}): $\mathbf{Z} = \mathbf{T}\mathbf{U}$. The lower triangular matrix \mathbf{T} results from the Cholesky decomposition of the correlation matrix \mathbf{R} , which is obtained from the covariance matrix Σ_{IM} in Equation (7-5). $IM_{0,i}$ represents the mean GMM estimation of IM at location i , and σ_i is the standard deviation provided by the GMM.

- $C_i, i = 1..2$: Logarithm of the seismic capacity of component i , which follows a normal distribution where the mean is the linear combination of conditioning variables V_i .

$$C_i \sim \mathcal{N}(C_{0,i} + \beta_i \sum_{j=1}^i t'_{ij} V_j, \varepsilon^2) \quad (7-14)$$

In Equation (7-14), the terms t'_{ij} are elements of the transformation matrix \mathbf{T}' , which is used to generate a correlated vector \mathbf{Z}' of standard normal variables by transforming the independent variables V_i (assembled into the vector \mathbf{V}): $\mathbf{Z}' = \mathbf{T}'\mathbf{V}$. The lower triangular matrix \mathbf{T}' results from the Cholesky decomposition of the correlation matrix \mathbf{R}' , which is obtained from the covariance matrix Σ_{c} in Equation (7-6). $C_{0,i}$ represents the prior mean of the seismic capacity of component i , and β_i is the standard deviation provided by the fragility curve.

- $D_i, i = 1..2$: Damage indicator of component i , which follows a normal distribution where the mean is the linear combination of conditioning variables IM_i and C_i .

$$D_i \sim \mathcal{N}(C_i - IM_i, \varepsilon^2) \quad (7-15)$$

The damage indicator is a continuous variable, however it may be easily interpreted as a discrete damage state. If D_i is positive, then it means that $C_i > IM_i$, which translates into $DS_i = 1$, as defined in Equation (7-1). Conversely, D_i being negative implies that $DS_i = 0$ (i.e., component failure). Therefore, without breaking the Gaussian assumption in the BN, it is possible to access P_{fi} , the probability of failure of component i :

$$P_{f,i} = P(D_i \leq 0) = \Phi\left(-\frac{\mu_{D_i}}{\sigma_{D_i}}\right) \quad (7-16)$$

where μ_{D_i} and σ_{D_i} are respectively the mean and standard-deviation of variable D_i , which are obtained when solving the Gaussian BN. Φ represents the standard normal cumulative distribution function.

The resulting Gaussian BN in Figure 7-4 is implemented in the Bayes Net toolbox (Murphy, 2001), which has the ability to apply exact inference (i.e., junction-tree algorithm) to continuous Gaussian variables.

Figure 7-4: Gaussian BN used for the numerical verification on the synthetic example. Red circles represent nodes that are evidenced (see Section 7.3.3).

With the proposed Gaussian BN, an issue arises when needing to specify that a given component i has failed or survived as an evidence. Since such an evidence takes the form of an inequality (e.g., $D_i > 0$ for survival), it cannot be entered directly into the BN, which can only treat hard evidence (i.e., a scalar value determining a continuous variable). Therefore it is proposed to decompose the posterior distributions over all possible values of D_i , given the damage state of the bridge. A similar decomposition framework for the treatment of soft evidence has been introduced by Fayjaloun et al. (2021b). Let Y be a variable of interest in the BN; then its posterior distribution given the observation of $DS_i = 1$ is decomposed as follows:

$$P(Y|DS_i = 1) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} P(Y|D_i)P(D_i|DS_i = 1)dD_i \quad (7-17)$$

$P(D_i | DS_i=1)$ represents the conditional probability of observing the value D_i given the damage state of the component: this probability is estimated by using the *a priori* distribution of D_i and by truncating its probability density function, named p_{trunc} (i.e., keeping only the positive part of the support and normalizing the function):

$$P(Y|DS_i = 1) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} P(Y|D_i)p_{trunc}(D_i)dD_i \approx \sum_k P\left(Y\left|D_i = \frac{D_{i,k+1}+D_{i,k}}{2}\right.\right) [P_{trunc}(D_{i,k+1}) - P_{trunc}(D_{i,k})] \quad (7-18)$$

where P_{trunc} represents the cumulative distribution function of D_i . If a discretization is applied to the continuous variable D_i , then the integral may be approximated by summing over the discrete intervals $[D_{i,k}; D_{i,k+1}]$, as shown in Figure 7-5.

Figure 7-5: (a) Prior distribution of D_i ; (b) Truncated and normalized distribution of D_i ; (c) Discretized weights applied to the decomposition.

With a very refined discretization, this approach is able to converge quickly towards the exact solution. However, it requires to loop over a large number of BNs (each time defined with a different evidence value), and the computations using such an approach become intractable when several observations need to be entered. Therefore, this method is only used on the trivial synthetic example in order to provide trustworthy results that can be compare to the MCMC sampling-based approach.

7.3.3 Results

The comparison between the Gaussian BN and the OpenBUGS outcomes is detailed in Table 7-1, by considering two evidence scenarios: scenario 1 only considers that $\log im_3 = -0.1$; while scenario 2 assumes that an additional type of observation is available, i.e. that component #2 has survived (i.e., $ds_2 = 1$). An example of OpenBUGS model is shown in Figure 7-6.

```

model
{
  IM[1:3] ~ dnorm(muIM[], tau1[, ])
  tau1[1:3, 1:3] <- inverse(cov_IM[, ])
  C[1:2] ~ dnorm(muC[, ], tau2[, ])
  tau2[1:2, 1:2] <- inverse(cov_C[, ])

  for (i in 1:2) {
    frag[i] <- phi((C[i] - IM[i])/1.00000E-06)
  }
  DS[1, 1] ~ dbern(frag[1])
  Dobs[1, 1] ~ dbern(frag[2])

  PfSystem <- 1 - DS[1, 1] * Dobs[1, 1]

  prec.IM <- 1/1.00000E-06
  IMobs[1, 1] ~ dnorm(IM[3], prec.IM)
}

```

Figure 7-6: OpenBUGS model for scenario 2. Observations (evidence) are the quantities *Dobs* and *IMobs*.

Table 7-1: Posterior distributions of the variables of interest, for the two evidence scenarios. Observed values are in bold font. C_2 and IM_2 are expressed in $\log_{10} \text{ m/s}^2$.

	Prior	Evidence scenario 1 ($im_3 = -0.1$)		Evidence scenario 2 ($im_3 = -0.1, ds_2 = 1$)	
		Gaussian BN	OpenBUGS BN	Gaussian BN	OpenBUGS BN
$P(s = 0)$	0.8320	0.7576	0.7592	0.5717	0.5706
$\overline{im}_1; \sigma_{im1}$	0.3346 ; 0.4260	0.1459 ; 0.3330	0.1469 ; 0.3334	0.1420 ; 0.3332	0.1408 ; 0.3326
$\overline{im}_2; \sigma_{im2}$	0.0878 ; 0.4260	-0.1009 ; 0.3330	-0.0994 ; 0.3334	-0.2391 ; 0.2954	-0.2387 ; 0.2957
$\overline{im}_3; \sigma_{im3}$	0.2025 ; 0.4260	-0.1 ; /	-0.1 ; /	-0.1 ; /	-0.1 ; /
$\overline{c}_1; \sigma_{c1}$	-0.0083 ; 0.4472	-0.0083 ; 0.4317	-0.0083 ; 0.4469	0.0416 ; 0.4433	0.0415 ; 0.4437
$\overline{c}_2; \sigma_{c2}$	-0.0083 ; 0.4472	-0.0083 ; 0.4317	-0.0081 ; 0.4473	0.2411 ; 0.3510	0.2419 ; 0.3508
$P(ds_1 = 0)$	0.7106	0.6090	0.6101	0.5717	0.5706
$P(ds_2 = 0)$	0.5618	0.4341	0.4350	0	0

Due to the sampling approximation present in both methods, the posterior values cannot be perfectly matched; however, they are in very close agreement, and most discrepancies appear around the 3rd or 4th decimals. Such a level of precision is sufficient for seismic risk applications since it appears that the mismatch is negligible in light of the much greater uncertainties that usually accompany loss assessment models. This numerical test is also an opportunity to verify the soundness of the Bayesian modelling assumptions: all variables are updated given the evidence, and their posterior distribution is shifted in the expected direction (e.g., reduction of the seismic intensity due to the observation of a low-intensity im_3 , better seismic resistance of the components due to the observation of the survival of component #2, etc.). It is also worth noting that the uncertainty on these variables is gradually reduced as more evidence is entered (i.e., smaller standard-deviations in evidence scenario 2).

A more systematic investigation of the updating capabilities of the BN approach is shown in Figure 7-7, where the values of im_3 are gradually increased in evidence scenario 2. The top plots show the evolution of the posterior distributions of variables IM_2 and C_2 , in terms of 16th, 50th and 84th percentiles, obtained with the OpenBUGS approach. The bottom plots show the evolution of the error between the Gaussian BN and OpenBUGS estimates, which is defined as follows:

$$Err = \frac{E[Y|IM_3=im_3, DS_2]_{OBN} - E[Y|IM_3=im_3, DS_2]_{GBN}}{E[Y|IM_3=im_3, DS_2]_{GBN}} \quad (7-19)$$

On the right plots of Figure 7-7, evidence scenario 2 is modified in order to consider the case where the failure of component #2 is observed.

Figure 7-7: Top left: posterior distributions of variables IM_2 and C_2 , in terms of 16th, 50th and 84th percentiles, with evidence $IM_3 = im_3$ and $DS_2 = 1$; Top right: posterior distributions of variables IM_2 and C_2 , in terms of 16th, 50th and 84th percentiles, with evidence $IM_3 = im_3$ and $DS_2 = 0$; Bottom: Error rate between the Gaussian BN and OpenBUGS estimates.

From Figure 7-7, the following points may be noted:

- In the case that $DS_2 = 1$ is observed, C_2 is well above IM_2 for low values of im_3 and the gap narrows as im_3 increases. IM_2 is influenced by the evidence of IM_3 and tends to increase, which has the effect of forcing C_2 to increase even more in order to respect the condition $DS_2 = 1$. It has also been found that the correlation between IM_2 and C_2 increases, reflecting the higher constraints that are applied by large values of im_3 .
- In the case that $DS_2 = 0$ is observed, low values of im_3 induce low values of IM_2 as well, forcing C_2 to be reduced dramatically. As im_3 increases, the constraints become more relaxed, and IM_2 increases enough so that C_2 deviates less from its prior distribution.
- Regarding the error rates, no significant biases or trends are observed. The errors seem to be well constrained under 0.03 (i.e., around 3% of deviation at the maximum), confirming the suitability of the sampling-based BN for the problem at hand.

7.4 Application to a real-world road network

This section describes the case-study area in the French Pyrenees mountain range (TB-2) and the construction of the corresponding BN model.

7.4.1 Description of the case-study area

The proposed BN approach for rapid response is applied to a road network composed of 118 bridges (i.e., vulnerable components), which connects 53 municipalities (i.e., built areas) located in a valley around Bagnères-de-Luchon (Pyrenees, France). The case-study area is detailed in Figure 7-8.

Figure 7-8: Situation map of the Luchon case-study area.

The typologies of the 118 bridges are identified based on photographs and aerial pictures, and their conditional probability of failure is defined by fragility functions, some of which are taken from the SYNER-G database (Crowley et al., 2011). The most common bridge type consists of short single-span bridges (length < 50 m), followed by masonry arch bridges. In total, 18 different fragility curves have been assigned (3 models for the 83 single-span bridges, 3 for the 7 continuous multi-span bridges, and 12 for the 28 arch bridges). The fragility curve corresponding to the first limit state is considered as the threshold of the loss of functionality of the bridge (i.e., failure of the component), assuming that even small structural damage might be enough to prevent safe passage.

For the 53 municipalities, the information concerning the characteristics of the residential buildings is extracted from the building census data freely provided by the French National Institute of Statistics and Economic Studies (INSEE). From INSEE data, we are using mainly three items: the building type (e.g. individual building, collective building), the number of stories and the construction age period. We associate the age period range of construction to the evolution of the construction technics and the evolution of seismic design codes. With these data, we classify the different buildings types into the EMS-98 vulnerability classes (Grünthal,

1998). For each building type in each municipality, we estimate the associated number of buildings and the associated population. Then, for the building types distributed into the EMS-98 classes, we estimate the RISK-UE vulnerability indices based on the method developed by Lagomarsino & Giovinazzi (2006).

The studied area is surrounded by several seismic stations (see Figure 7-8), which are used as sources of observations to constrain estimates of the strong-motion field. All selected fragility curves use PGA as IM; therefore, the regional GMM by Tapia (2006) is applied here for the estimation of the prior distribution of IM. For PGA, the spatial correlation model by Jayaram & Baker (2009) is expressed as:

$$\rho_{ij} = \exp\left(-\frac{3h}{8.5}\right) \quad (7-20)$$

where h is the inter-site distance in km.

Finally, site effects are modelled via soil amplification factors, which were estimated from local investigations and soil measurements (Roullé et al., 2012).

7.4.2 Construction of the BN model

The assembled Super-Network is displayed in Figure 7-9, where the position of the abstract Super-Nodes is estimated as the mean of the coordinates of the nodes belonging to each Super-Node. This preliminary step leads to a dramatic simplification of the network since the initial 607 nodes and 689 edges are now replaced by 52 Super-Nodes and 67 Super-Edges. Out of the initial 118 bridges, only 96 are kept in the Super-Network, since some of them are not useful to ensure the connectivity between Super-Nodes.

For demonstration purposes, the connectivity between a location A (downtown of Bagnères-de-Luchon) and a location B (Northern end of the road network) is studied here, in order to simulate the possibility to send rescue teams from the North to the affected area after a potential earthquake (see Figure 7-9). Thanks to the Super-Network conceptualisation, the decomposition of all possible paths between A and B becomes computationally manageable: 60 MLs are identified, mobilising 25 bridges in total (i.e., most bridges are involved in multiple MLs), as shown in Figure 7-10.

Figure 7-9: Construction of the Super-Network from the physical network.

Figure 7-10: Summary of the identified MLSs and location of the observations.

Finally, this structure is implemented in OpenBUGS in order to build the corresponding BN, which contains the following nodes:

- The vector **IM**, containing 156 elements (96 bridge sites + 53 built area centroids + 7 observations);
- The vector **C**, containing 96 elements;
- The vector **V**, containing 53 elements;
- 96 *DS* nodes;
- 53 μ_D nodes;
- 60 *MLS* nodes;
- 1 *S* node.

The updating capabilities of the BN are tested with a hypothetical Mw 6.3 earthquake scenario, located south of the road network (0.60° lon, 42.65° lat). Hypothetical observations from 7 seismic stations and damage measures on 5 bridges are set as evidence in the BN (2 survivals and 3 failures). It is assumed that one of the monitored bridges belongs to the identified MLSs, and it has been observed as intact (see Figure 7-10).

7.5 Results and discussion

This section details the updated loss distributions obtained from the BN while discussing the impact of various factors, such as the number of MCMC samples or the correlation between the seismic response of the bridges.

7.5.1 Checking the accuracy of the updated ground-motion field

As the numerical test in Section 7.3 could only be performed on a small example with a reduced number of variables, another test is conducted here on all IM variables involved in the case-study. In the BN, the **IM** vector represents a spatially-correlated Gaussian field, for which analytical solutions have been developed (Vanmarcke, 1983; Stafford, 2012): such an updating procedure is actually adopted in current systems for the generation of shake-maps (Worden et al., 2018), thus constituting the reference solution. Since this solution is only available for the ground-motion field, the IM variables are updated here using only the 7 seismic observations (i.e., no observations of the damage states of bridges). IMs are updated at the locations of the 96 bridges of interest and the centroids of the 53 built areas: the updated distributions are compared to the analytical solution for different sizes of MCMC samples (respectively three chains of 3 000, 5 000, 15 000 and 25 000 samples each, with the removal of a burn-in phase of 2 000 samples in each chain). The errors rates $\varepsilon_{E(IM)}$ and $\varepsilon_{\sigma_{\log IM}}$ of the posterior distributions estimated with the BN with respect to the exact analytical solution, at all vulnerable sites, are summarized in Figure 7-11:

$$\begin{cases} \varepsilon_{E(IM)} = \frac{E(IM_{sampled}) - E(IM_{exact})}{E(IM_{exact})} \times 100 \\ \varepsilon_{\sigma_{\log IM}} = \frac{\sigma_{\log IM_{sampled}} - \sigma_{\log IM_{exact}}}{\sigma_{\log IM_{exact}}} \times 100 \end{cases} \quad (7-21)$$

where $E(IM)$ is the expectation of the posterior IM distribution and $\sigma_{\log IM}$ is the standard deviation of the logarithm of IM.

Figure 7-11: Histograms of the error rate of the mean and standard deviation of the posterior IM distribution at the various sites, with respect to the analytical solution, for various lengths of the MCMC chains.

The estimated posterior distributions of IM are globally in very good agreement with the analytical solution, both in terms of mean and standard deviation, thus providing further confidence with respect to the application of the proposed sampling-based inference algorithm. This comparison exercise serves as a preliminary step to calibrate the size of samples and ensure proper convergence of the posterior distributions. In the current application, Figure 7-11 shows that satisfying accuracy levels are quickly reached as the size of samples grows. Therefore, it is decided to opt for a chain size of 15 000 samples, in order to keep the error rate well below 1%. With this choice, the complete BN (including also *C*, *DS*, *MLS* and *S* nodes) is solved in less than half an hour with a medium-performance personal computer (8 GB memory): this timeframe is in line with what should be expected from elaborate rapid response systems, although it could be further improved with the use of dedicated computing servers.

7.5.2 Influence of the correlation assumptions on the results

Following the discussion of Section 7.2.4 on the assumptions to be made for the covariance models, three different correlation hypotheses are tested for the response \mathbf{C} of bridges:

- *Corr1*: no correlation is introduced, so that $\Sigma_{\mathbf{c}}$ is simply a diagonal matrix.
- *Corr2*: only the correlation of the record-to-record variability is introduced, with a correlation model decreasing with inter-bridge distance (i.e., Eq. 7-6 with $\rho^{M_{ij}} = 0$).
- *Corr3*: in addition to the correlation of the record-to-record variability, a full correlation between bridges of the same type (i.e., using the same fragility model) is assumed, i.e. $\rho^{M_{ij}} = 1$ if bridges i and j are in the same typology.

Global results for the system connectivity are detailed in Table 7-2, where it is shown that the proposed approach is also able to identify which MLS is the most likely to remain accessible (i.e., “best” MLS).

Table 7-2: Results of the Bayesian updating, in terms of probability of disconnection between points A and B (i.e., $S = 0$) and of identification of the “best” MLS, for the various correlation assumptions.

	Prior	Posterior		
		<i>Corr1</i>	<i>Corr2</i>	<i>Corr3</i>
Pr(Disconnection)	0.095	0.342	0.353	0.435
“Best” MLS	#45	#49	#21	#3

A significant difference is observed between the prior and posterior probabilities of disconnection, due to the assumption that the damage states of 5 bridges were entered as evidence (see Figure 7-10). The evidence of a bridge’s state has an impact on the system at various levels:

- The observation of a bridge failure directly modifies the accessibility of the MLS(s) to which it belongs, and in turn system connectivity.
- If the seismic response \mathbf{C} is modelled with a constrained correlation model (i.e., *Corr2* or *Corr3*), then the observation of a bridge’s state may modify the seismic response of other bridges, in turn modifying their probability of failure and ultimately the accessibility of the MLSs to which they belong.
- Finally, as seen in Figure 7-7, the observation of a bridge’s state may also modify the distribution of the IM at the base of the bridge, in turn modifying the ground-shaking field in the vicinity.

The differences between the three correlation models are noticeable: the extreme configurations *Corr1* and *Corr3* should be used as upper and lower bounds of the model outcome, pending an in-depth investigation of appropriate correlation models for the seismic response. Furthermore, each assumption leads to the identification of a different MLS as the least affected route, which could have a large impact on emergency operations. An example of the changes in the rapid estimate of the post-earthquake condition of the network is provided in Figure 7-12, both in terms of failure probability of bridges and identifying the most accessible MLS. Similar updating may also be performed for the damage assessment of built areas (see Figure 7-13).

Figure 7-12: Left: prior distribution using only the characteristics of the earthquake event; Right: posterior distribution using field observations (with *Corr3* model).

Figure 7-13: Top: prior mean of μ_D (mean damage grade) of the built areas; Bottom: posterior distribution using field observations (with *Corr3* model).

Apart from the changes in the mean damage and loss values, the Bayesian updating is especially useful for reducing the related uncertainties; and therefore, gaining more confidence in rapid damage assessment. In Figure 7-14, the updated standard-deviations of $\log PGA$, used as IM, are reduced by half (from around 0.42 in the prior distribution down to the 0.20-0.25 range) in the immediate vicinity of seismic stations. On the other hand, the survival/failure observations on bridges have a reduced impact on the distribution of IM, since the probability updating enters here in competition with the updating of C , which have an equal contribution in the damage sampling (see Equation 7-1).

Figure 7-14: Posterior standard-deviation $\sigma_{\log PGA}$ of the IMs at the locations of interest (with *Corr3* model).

The updating process of the response C is further detailed in Figure 7-15, where the posterior distribution of a given C_i is used to assemble a fragility function, through the following expression:

$$P_f(PGA) = \Phi\left(\frac{im - \bar{c}_i}{\sigma_{c_i}}\right) \quad (7-22)$$

Two opposite configurations are shown in Figure 7-15:

- In the top plots, bridge #533 is observed as intact, and its updated response distribution is therefore moving towards higher PGA levels. The response of bridge #546, a neighbouring bridge of the same type, is also updated, but to a lesser extent. As expected, the correlation model *Corr1* (no correlation at all) has no impact on the response. Since

- the two bridges are only about 2 km apart, the application of model *Corr2* (only distance-dependent correlation) has a noticeable influence on the response distribution. Model *Corr3* has the most influence since it corresponds to the strongest correlation structure.
- In the bottom plots, bridge #629 is observed as failed, and its updated response distribution is therefore moving towards lower PGA levels. Similar trends are observed for bridge #661 of the same type: in this case, the effect of model *Corr2* is less noticeable, since the two bridges are further apart (10 km).

Figure 7-15: Updating of the seismic response of bridges, based on damage observations.

The updated seismic response may then be used as a prior distribution in subsequent risk analyses: this feature is especially useful in the earthquake aftershock phase, since the updated fragility models may be directly applied to the components that have survived, in order to refine the aftershock risk assessment.

7.6 Conclusions

This study has investigated the implementation of a Bayesian Network-based framework for improving situational awareness during the rapid response phase following an earthquake event. It has been demonstrated that a BN built in OpenBUGS environment is able to provide updated losses for a real-world road network and built areas based on available observations. The BN is solved with a MCMC sampling scheme, which delivers approximate posterior distributions: this approximate solution, as opposed to exact inference algorithms, is a necessary trade-off in order to treat systems of hundreds of components exposed to spatially distributed hazards. Moreover, the sampling inference scheme used in OpenBUGS can combine continuous (e.g., intensity measures, seismic capacities) and discrete variables (e.g., damage states), which has the benefit of introducing exact distributions instead of discretizing continuous variables. Regarding road networks, when connectivity loss is used as a simple system indicator, the decomposition of the system into MLSs is also essential in reducing the complexity of the BN. As a result, in the studied example, posterior distributions are generated within 20 or 30 minutes. Moreover, the decomposition into MLSs has the benefit of identifying specific routes associated with probabilities of accessibility: this information has the potential to be used by emergency managers to set up dedicated evacuation routes or safe itineraries to hospitals. Each MLS can also be associated with a travel distance or travel duration, in order to develop more elaborate performance indicators than connectivity loss.

The input of field observations has the expected effect of refining the loss estimates, thus providing more confidence in the information delivered to emergency responders. The main mechanism behind the updating process is due to the formulation of the covariance matrices Σ_{IM} and Σ_c : while the correlation between intensity measures is well studied, the correlation between the seismic capacities of components is less obvious. Various correlation assumptions have been tested here, in an attempt to quantify this effect: further investigations will be required in order to propose a robust model for the covariance of the seismic response. It is shown that correlated seismic capacities also lead to updated fragility models, depending on the observed damage on components. Such a feature of the BN model would be especially useful to update the risk assessment models in the aftershock phase, for instance. Finally, the results of such a BN application can constitute the starting point of rapid repair strategies for bridges, in order to improve the seismic resilience of transportation systems.

8 CONCLUSIONS

This report has detailed the actions taken in Task 4.5 for the development of a procedure for Rapid Earthquake Loss Prediction. The initial literature review of existing RRE systems (Guérin-Marthe et al., 2021) has led to the identification of several gaps and opportunities for improvement, some of which have been addressed here. Besides the technical points raised by the literature review, more generic conclusions regarding the use of RRE systems have been drawn:

- While harmonized RRE systems are desirable for a widespread use, it is important to bear in mind that some inputs such as specific GMMs, soil amplification maps and building inventories have to be provided at a local scale, in order for the resulting information to be trusted by authorities.
- The level of confidence that risk and disaster managers can have in such tools may be improved if these systems are also used in a planning and mitigation capacity (e.g., generation of prospective hazard and risk scenarios). Therefore such RRE systems are not only tools for disaster operational management, but they are as important when used for exercises and planning via scenarios, as well as for risk studies and mitigation efforts.
- RRE systems must strive to deliver information that is immediately understandable and operational for crisis management, otherwise they will be quickly dismissed and forgotten. To overcome the well-known pitfall of “non-applicable applied research” and to favour the operational declination of RREs, it appears to be very important to involve stakeholders early in the development of these tools.

The comparison between the SELENA and Armagedom methods, applied to two distinct areas (Luchon Valley and region of Alicante), has shown that the results are consistent and have similar spatial distributions of damages, even though the two damage computation approaches are completely different (one based on vulnerability indices and the other on fragility curves). The main source of the differences between the two methods is due to the conversion between ground-motion parameters (e.g., PGA) and macroseismic intensity, where the choice of GMICE has a large influence on the damage distribution generated by the Armagedom approach.

The comparison between different spatial resolutions of soil maps and building exposure datasets (from European level to local level) has shown that, in the specific case of Luchon Valley, the use of the European soil map (with an amplification factor up to 1.5) and the European building database led to an underestimation of the heavy damage classes (D3–D5). Using the regional soil map (with an amplification factor up to 1.8) and the National statistics building database results in similar estimates to those using the local soil map (with an amplification factor up to 1.8) and a field-investigation database for the buildings.

The Value of Information study on the contribution of various types of measurements to the rapid damage identification of structures has shown that GPS measurements provide the best results in terms of uncertainty reduction when used to compute residual displacements, whereas the accelerometer placed at the top of the structure provides the best results in terms of reducing the uncertainty in the estimate of the maximum absolute accelerations and drifts. However, unless a seismic station is located very close to the structure, it is found that the expected effectiveness of shake-maps is quite low: this observation reinforces the need to

propagate consistently the uncertainties due to ground shaking estimation up to the distribution of losses.

The effectiveness of the sensors changes also significantly with the level of shaking intensity: for low intensity, the noise/measurement errors in the sensors reduce their effectiveness, while these errors become less significant in the case of high seismic shaking.

Finally, it is observed that the combination of data from different sensors within the BN leads to a dramatic reduction of uncertainty, when compared to cases with only single observation sources.

The main development of Task 4.5 pertains to the implementation of a Bayesian updating framework that generates loss estimates for built areas and infrastructure systems, while integrating various types of observations. This approach has been successfully applied to Luchon Valley (TB-2), where the connectivity of a road network is quantified in a rapid response context. The input of field observations has the expected effect of refining the loss estimates, thus providing more confidence in the information delivered to emergency responders. However, this application has raised additional questions, such as the role of the correlation between the variability of the fragility models of components: further investigations will be required in order to propose a robust model for the covariance of the seismic response. It is also shown that correlated seismic capacities also lead to updated fragility models, depending on the observed damage on components. Such a feature of the BN model would be especially useful to update the risk assessment models in the aftershock phase, for instance. Finally, the results of such a BN application can constitute the starting point of rapid repair strategies for bridges, in order to improve the seismic resilience of transportation systems.

REFERENCES

Akkar, S., & Bommer, J. J. (2010). Empirical equations for the prediction of PGA, PGV, and spectral accelerations in Europe, the Mediterranean region, and the Middle East. *Seismological Research Letters*, 81(2), 195-206.

Ambraseys, N.N.; Douglas, J.; Sarma, S.K.; Smit, P.M. (2005). Equations for the Estimation of Strong Ground Motions from Shallow Crustal Earthquakes Using Data from Europe and the Middle East: Horizontal Peak Ground Acceleration and Spectral Acceleration. *Bull. Earthq. Eng.*, 3, 1–53, doi:10.1007/s10518-005-0183-0.

Applegate, C. J., & Tien, I. (2019). Framework for probabilistic vulnerability analysis of interdependent infrastructure systems. *Journal of Computing in Civil Engineering*, 33(1), 04018058.

Argyroudis, S., Selva, J., Gehl, P., & Pitilakis, K. (2015). Systemic seismic risk assessment of road networks considering interactions with the built environment. *Computer-Aided Civil and Infrastructure Engineering*, 30(7), 524-540.

Atkinson, G., and Sonley, E. (2000). Empirical relationships between modified Mercalli intensity and response spectra. *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America*, 90: 537–544.

Auclair, S., Monfort, D., Colas, B., Langer, T., & Bertil, D. (2014). Outils de réponse rapide pour la gestion opérationnelle de crises sismiques. *Colloque SAGEO*.

Auclair, S., Monfort, D., Colas, B., Langer, T., & Perrier, P. (2015). Evaluation rapide des bilans matériels et humains: une aide essentielle à la gestion opérationnelle des crises sismiques. *9ème Colloque National AFPS*.

Auclair, S., Boulahya, F., Birregah, B., Quique, R., Ouaret, R., & Soulier, E. (2019). SURICATE-Nat: Innovative citizen centered platform for Twitter based natural disaster monitoring. *6th International Conference on Information and Communication Technologies for Disaster Management, ICT-DM 2019*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICT-DM47966.2019.9032950>

Azarbakht et al. (2020). Report on the limits and potential applications of current state-of-the-art OEF, EEW and RRE systems for European conditions. *TURNkey Report D3.1*.

Baker, J. W., Lin, T., Shahi, S. K., & Jayaram, N. (2011). New ground motion selection procedures and selected motions for the PEER transportation research program. *PEER report*, 3.

Bal, I.E.; Bommer, J.; Stafford, P.J.; Crowley, H.; Pinho, R.J.S.M. (2010). The Influence of Geographical Resolution of Urban Exposure Data in an Earthquake Loss Model for Istanbul. *Earthq. Spectra*, 26, 619–634, doi:10.1193/1.3459127.

Barbat, A. H., Moya, F. Y., & Canas, J. A. (1996). Damage scenarios simulation for seismic risk assessment in urban zones. *Earthquake Spectra*. <https://doi.org/10.1193/1.1585889>

Basöz, N., & Mander, J. B. (1999). *Enhancement of the highway transportation lifeline module in HAZUS*. National Institute of Building Sciences.

Bayraktarli, Y. Y., Ulfkjaer, J. P., Yazgan, U., & Faber, M. H. (2005). On the application of Bayesian probabilistic networks for earthquake risk management. In *9th International Conference on Structural Safety and Reliability (ICOSSAR 05)* (pp. 20-23).

Bellotti, D., Borzi, B., Famà, A., Quaroni, D., Vecchi, A., Mauro, A., Vergara, L. Tisalvi, M., & Iacobini, F. (2019). Development of web-based tools for large-scale post-seismic emergency management of railway infrastructures, *10th New York City Bridge Conference*, USA, August 26-27.

Benedetti, D., & Petrini, V. (1984). Sulla vulnerabilità sismica di edifici in muratura: Proposta su un metodo di valutazione. *L'industria Delle Costruzioni*.

Bensi, M. T. (2010). *A Bayesian Network Methodology for Infrastructure Seismic Risk Assessment and Decision Support* (Doctoral dissertation, University of California, Berkeley).

Bensi, M. T., Kiureghian, A. D., & Straub, D. (2011). A Bayesian Network Methodology for Infrastructure Seismic Risk Assessment and Decision Support. *PEER Report No. 2011/02*, Pacific Earthquake Engineering Research Center.

Bensi, M., Der Kiureghian, A., & Straub, D. (2013). Efficient Bayesian network modeling of systems. *Reliability Engineering & System Safety*, 112, 200-213.

Bensi, M., Kiureghian, A., & Straub, D. (2015). Framework for post-earthquake risk assessment and decision making for infrastructure systems. *ASCE-ASME Journal of Risk and Uncertainty in Engineering Systems, Part A: Civil Engineering*, 1(1), 04014003.

Bernardini, A. (2000). La Vulnerabilità Degli Edifici: Valutazione a Scala Nazionale Della Vulnerabilità Sismica Degli Edifici Ordinari. *Research Report, CNR-Gruppo Nazionale per La Difesa Dai Terremoti*, Rome, Italy (in Italian).

Besson, B., Bjarnason, J. Ö., & Rupakhety, R. (2020). Statistical modelling of seismic vulnerability of RC, timber and masonry buildings from complete empirical loss data. *Engineering Structures*, 209, 109969.

Bolognani, D., Verzobio, A., Tonelli, D., Cappello, C., Glisic, B., Zonta, D., & Quigley, J. (2018). IWSHM 2017: Quantifying the benefit of structural health monitoring: what if the manager is not the owner?. *Structural Health Monitoring*, 17(6), 1393-1409.

Bommer, J. J., & Crowley, H. (2006). The influence of ground-motion variability in earthquake loss modelling. *Bulletin of Earthquake Engineering*, 4(3), 231-248.

Borzi, B., Crowley, H., & Pinho, R. (2008). Simplified pushover-based earthquake loss assessment (SP-BELA) method for masonry buildings. *International Journal of Architectural Heritage*, 2(4), 353–376.

Borzi, B., Di Meo, A., Faravelli, M., Fiorini, E., & Onida, M. (2011a). Definizione di una procedura di prioritizzazione per interventi di mitigazione del rischio degli edifici scolastici. *XIV Convegno L'Ingegneria Sismica in Italia ANIDIS*.

Borzi, B., Di Meo, A., Faravelli, M., Fiorini, E., & Onida, M. (2011b). Mappe di rischio sismico e scenario per gli edifici scolastici italiani. *XIV Convegno L'Ingegneria Sismica in Italia ANIDIS*.

Borzi, B., et al. (2021). Report on recommendations on fragility functions for buildings and infrastructure components to be used in rapid response context. *TURNkey Report D4.2*.

Borzi, B., Onida, M., Faravelli, M. *et al.* IRMA platform for the calculation of damages and risks of Italian residential buildings. *Bull Earthquake Eng* 19, 3033–3055 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10518-020-00924-x>

Bosco, F., Deschamps, A., & Auclair, S. (2019). Rapid assessment of seismic impact in Western Alpine area: development in Italy and French cross-border project (ALCOTRA RISVAL). *38° Convegno Nazionale GNGTS (Roma, 12-14 Novembre 2019)*.

Bozzoni, F., & Lai, C.G. (2017). Tools for rapid seismic response assessment of strategic facilities under GIS environment: applications to Italian seaports and embankment dams. *Proceedings, 3rd International Conference on Performance-Based Design in Earthquake Geotechnical Engineering*, PBD-III, Vancouver, Canada, July 16 - 19, Paper No. 512.

Bozzoni, F., Lai, C. G., Marsan, P., Conca, D., & Fama, A. (2018). WebGIS Platform for Seismic Risk Assessment of Maritime Port Systems in Italy. *4th PIANC Mediterranean Days Congress*.

Bozzoni, F., Ozcebe, A.G., Balia, A., Lai, C.G., Borzi, B., Nascimbene, R., Khairy, D., Gabbianelli, G., Ippoliti, L., Berardi, S., Trombetti, M., & Moroni, C. (2020). Seismic ground response analyses at an international airport in Northern Italy by using a stochastic-based approach. *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Mechanics*, 58(2), 499-511. DOI: 10.15632/jtam-pl/119017.

Bragato, P. L. (2009). Assessing regional and site-dependent variability of ground motions for ShakeMap implementation in Italy. *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America*, 99(5), 2950-2960.

Broglio, S., Crowley, H., & Pinho, R. (2013). *Bayesian Network framework for macro-scale seismic risk assessment and decision support for bridges*. IUSS Press.

Byun, J. E., & Song, J. (2021). Generalized matrix-based Bayesian network for multi-state systems. *Reliability Engineering & System Safety*, 107468.

Byun, J. E., Zwirgmaier, K., Straub, D., & Song, J. (2019). Matrix-based Bayesian Network for efficient memory storage and flexible inference. *Reliability Engineering & System Safety*, 185, 533-545.

Calvi, G. M. (1999). A displacement-based approach for vulnerability evaluation of classes of buildings. *Journal of Earthquake Engineering*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13632469909350353>.

Calvi, G. M., Pinho, R., Magenes, G., Bommer, J. J., Restrepo-Vélez, L. F., & Crowley, H. (2006). Development of seismic vulnerability assessment methodologies over the past 30 years. *ISET Journal of Earthquake Technology*.

Cappello, C., Zonta, D., & Glišić, B. (2016). Expected utility theory for monitoring-based decision-making. *Proceedings of the IEEE*, 104(8), 1647-1661.

Cavaleri, F., Franchin, P., Gehl, P., & D'Ayala, D. (2017). Bayesian networks and infrastructure systems: Computational and methodological challenges. In P. Gardoni (Ed.), *Risk and reliability analysis: Theory and applications*, Springer.

Celebi, M. (2000). GPS in dynamic monitoring of long-period structures. *Soil Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering*, 20(5-8), 477-483.

Celebi, M., Sanli, A., Sinclair, M., Gallant, S., & Radulescu, D. (2004). Real-time seismic monitoring needs of a building owner—and the solution: a cooperative effort. *Earthquake Spectra*, 20(2), 333-346.

Choi, E., DesRoches, R., & Nielson, B. (2004). Seismic fragility of typical bridges in moderate seismic zones. *Engineering structures*, 26(2), 187-199.

Coburn, A., & Spence, R. (1992). *Earthquake protection* (John Wiley). <https://doi.org/10.5459/bnzsee.27.2.163>.

Conca, D., Bozzoni, F., & Lai, C. G. (2020). Interdependencies in Seismic Risk Assessment of Seaport Systems: Case Study at Largest Commercial Port in Italy. *ASCE-ASME Journal of Risk and Uncertainty in Engineering Systems, Part A: Civil Engineering*, 6(2), 04020006.

Corbane, C.; Hancilar, U.; Ehrlich, D.; De Groeve, T. (2017). Pan-European seismic risk assessment: A proof of concept using the Earthquake Loss Estimation Routine (ELER). *Bull. Earthq. Eng.*, 15, 1057–1083.

Cremen, G., & Baker, J. W. (2018). Quantifying the benefits of building instruments to FEMA P-58 rapid post-earthquake damage and loss predictions. *Engineering Structures*, 176, 243-253.

Cremen, G., & Galasso, C. (2020). Earthquake early warning: Recent advances and perspectives. *Earth-Science Reviews*, 103184.

Crowley, H. (2014). Earthquake risk assessment: present shortcomings and future directions. In *Perspectives on European earthquake engineering and seismology* (pp. 515-532). Springer, Cham.

Crowley, H., Pinho, R., Bommer, J. J., & Bird, J. F. (2006). Development of a displacement-based method for earthquake loss assessment. *European School for Advanced Studies in Reduction of Seismic Risk, Pavia, Research Report No. ROSE-2006, 1*.

Crowley, H., J. J. Bommer, and P. J. Stafford (2008). Recent developments in the treatment of ground-motion variability in earthquake loss models. *Journal of Earthquake Engineering*, 12(2), 71-80.

Crowley, H., Colombi, M., Silva, V., Monteiro, R., Ozcebe, S., Fardis, M., Tsionis, G., & Askouni, P. (2011). Fragility functions for roadway bridges. In *SYNER-G Deliverable Report D3.6*.

Crowley, H.; Rodrigues, D.; Silva, V.; Despotaki, V.; Romao, X.; Castro, J.M.; Akkar, S.; Hancilar, U.; Ptilakis, K.P.D.; Belvaux, M.; et al. (2018). Towards a Uniform Earth-Quake risk Model for Europe. In *Proceedings of the 16th European Conference on Earthquake Engineering*, Thessaloniki, Greece, 18-21 June.

Crowley, H.; Weatherill, G.; Riga, E.; Ptilakis, K.; Roullé, A; Tourlière, B.; Lemoine, A.; Gracianne Hidalgo, C. (2019a). *Delivrable SERA: D26.4 Methods for Estimating Site Effects in Risk Assessments*.

Crowley, H., Pinho, R., van Elk, J., & Uilenreef, J. (2019b). Probabilistic damage assessment of buildings due to induced seismicity. *Bulletin of Earthquake Engineering*, 17(8), 4495-4516.

Crowley, H., Despotaki, V., Rodrigues, D., Silva, V., Toma-Danila, D., Riga, E., ... & Gamba, P. (2020). Exposure model for European seismic risk assessment. *Earthquake Spectra*, 36(1_suppl), 252-273.

Cousins, J., Science, G. N. S., Hutt, L., & Zealand, N. (1998). Estimated casualties in New Zealand earthquakes. *Statistics*.

Dai, K., Wang, J., Li, B., & Hong, H. P. (2017). Use of residual drift for post-earthquake damage assessment of RC buildings. *Engineering Structures*, 147, 242-255.

D'Ayala, D., & Speranza, E. (2002). An integrated procedure for the assessment of seismic vulnerability of historic buildings. *12th European Conference on Earthquake Engineering*.

Dabbeek, J.; Silva, V. (2020). Modeling the residential building stock in the Middle East for multi-hazard risk assessment. *Nat. Hazards*, 100, 781-810, doi:10.1007/s11069-019-03842-7.

Dezi L. Architectural and structural design of short and medium span composite bridges. In: *Proceedings of 7th International Conference on Steel Bridges*, Guimaraes, Portugal, 2008.

Di Meo, A., Borzi, B., Quaroni, D., Onida, M., & Pascale, V. (2018). Real-Time Damage Scenario and Seismic Risk Assessment of Italian Roadway Network. *16th European Conference on Earthquake Engineering*.

Di Pasquale, G., Orsini, G., & Romeo, R. W. (2005). New Developments in Seismic Risk Assessment in Italy. *Bulletin of Earthquake Engineering*, 3(1), 101–128.

Douglas, J. (2013). Seismic network design to detect felt ground motions from induced seismicity. *Soil Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering*, 48, 193-197.

Douglas, J., & Edwards, B. (2016). Recent and future developments in earthquake ground motion estimation. *Earth-Science Reviews*, 160, 203-219.

Dunnett, C. W., & Sobel, M. (1955). Approximations to the probability integral and certain percentage points of a multivariate analogue of Student's t-distribution. *Biometrika*, 42(1/2), 258-260.

Dutta, A. (1999). *On energy based seismic analysis and design of highway bridges* (Doctoral dissertation, State University of New York at Buffalo).

European Committee for Standardization (CEN). *Eurocode 4. Design of composite steel and concrete structures. Part 2: Composite bridges*, ENV 1994-2, Brussels, 2000.

European Committee for Standardization (CEN). *European Standard EN 1998-1: 2005 Eurocode 8: Design of structures for earthquake resistance. Part 1: General rules, Seismic action and rules for buildings*. European Committee for Standardization: Brussels, Belgium, 2005.

Erdik, M., Sesetyan, K., Demircioglu, M. B., Hancilar, U., & Zülfiyar, C. (2011). Rapid earthquake loss assessment after damaging earthquakes. *Soil Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering*, 31(2), 247–266.

Faenza, L., and Michelini, A. (2010). Regression analysis of MCS intensity and ground motion parameters in Italy and its application in ShakeMap. *Geophys. J. Int.*, 180, 1138–1152.

Falcone, G.; Boldini, D.; Amorosi, A. (2018). Site response analysis of an urban area: A multi-dimensional and non-linear approach. *Soil Dyn. Earthq. Eng.*, 109, 33–45, doi:10.1016/j.soildyn.2018.02.026.

Falcone, G.; Acunzo, G.; Mendicelli, A.; Mori, F.; Naso, G.; Peronace, E.; Porchia, A.; Romagnoli, G.; Tarquini, E.; Moscatelli, M. (2021). Seismic amplification maps of Italy based on site-specific microzonation dataset and one-dimensional numerical approach. *Eng. Geol.*, 289, 106170, doi:10.1016/j.enggeo.2021.106170.

Faravelli, M., Borzi, B., Pagano, M., & Quaroni, D. (2018). Using OpenQuake to define seismic risk and real time damage scenario in Italy. *16th European Conference on Earthquake Engineering*.

Farrar, C. R., & Worden, K. (2007). An introduction to structural health monitoring. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society A: Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences*, 365(1851), 303-315.

Fayjaloun, R., Negulescu, C., Roullé, A., Auclair, S., Gehl, P., & Faravelli, M. (2021a). Sensitivity of Earthquake Damage Estimation to the Input Data (Soil Characterization Maps and Building Exposure): Case Study in the Luchon Valley, France. *Geosciences*, 11(6), 249.

Fayjaloun, R., Gehl, P., Auclair, S., Boulahya, F., Guérin-Marthe, S., & Roullé, A. (2021b). Integrating strong-motion recordings and Twitter data for a rapid shakemap of macroseismic intensity. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 101927.

FEMA (2003). *HAZUS-MH technical manual*.

Franchin, P., (2014). A computational framework for systemic seismic risk analysis of civil infrastructural systems. In K. Pitilakis, P. Franchin, B. Khazai, H. Wenzel (Eds.), *SYNER-G: Systemic seismic vulnerability and risk assessment of complex urban, utility, lifeline systems and critical facilities*, Springer, Dordrecht, pp. 23-56.

Freddi, F., Padgett, J. E., & Dall'Asta, A. (2017). Probabilistic seismic demand modeling of local level response parameters of an RC frame. *Bulletin of Earthquake Engineering*, 15(1), 1-23.

Freeman, S. A. (1998). The Capacity Spectrum Method as a Tool for Seismic Design. *11th European Conference on Earthquake Engineering*.

Gehl, P. (2017). *Bayesian networks for the multi-risk assessment of road infrastructure* (Doctoral dissertation, UCL (University College London)).

Gehl, P., Douglas, J., & d'Ayala, D. (2017). Inferring Earthquake Ground-Motion Fields with Bayesian Networks. *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America*, 107(6), 2792-2808.

Gehl, P., Cavalieri, F., & Franchin, P. (2018). Approximate Bayesian network formulation for the rapid loss assessment of real-world infrastructure systems. *Reliability Engineering & System Safety*, 177, 80-93.

Gehl, P., Matsushima, S. & Masuda, S. (2021). Investigation of damage to the water network of Uki City from the 2016 Kumamoto earthquake: derivation of damage functions and construction of infrastructure loss scenarios. *Bulletin of Earthquake Engineering*, 19, 685-711.

Gilles, S. (2010). *Utilization of ELER V2 and improvement of ESMC Earthquake Impact Estimation Method*.

Giovinazzi, S., & Lagomarsino, S. (2004). A macroseismic method for the vulnerability assessment of buildings. *13th World Conference on Earthquake Engineering*.

- Gkimpraxis, A., Tubaldi, E., & Douglas, J. (2020). Evaluating alternative approaches for the seismic design of structures. *Bulletin of Earthquake Engineering*, 18:4331–4361.
- Goda, K. (2010). Statistical modeling of joint probability distribution using copula: application to peak and permanent displacement seismic demands. *Structural Safety*, 32(2), 112–123.
- Goda, K.; Tesfamariam, S. (2019). Financial risk evaluation of non-ductile reinforced concrete buildings in eastern and western Canada. *Int. J. Disaster Risk Reduct.*, 33, 94–107, doi:10.1016/j.ijdrr.2018.09.013.
- Goda, K.; Wilhelm, K.; Ren, J. (2020). Relationships between earthquake insurance take-up rates and seismic risk indicators for Canadian households. *Int. J. Disaster Risk Reduct.*, 50, 101754, doi:10.1016/j.ijdrr.2020.101754.
- Gobbato, M., Yeo, W. M., & Shome, N. (2014). Uncertainty quantification and sensitivity analysis of earthquake casualties. *NCEE 2014 - 10th U.S. National Conference on Earthquake Engineering: Frontiers of Earthquake Engineering*. <https://doi.org/10.4231/D3639K592>.
- Goula, X., Dominique, P., Colas, B., Jara, J. A., Roca, A., & Winter, T. (2008). Seismic rapid response system in the Eastern Pyrenees. *XIV World Conference on Earthquake Engineering*, 12–17.
- Gray, R. M. (2011). *Entropy and information theory*. Springer Science & Business Media.
- Grünthal G. (1998). European Macroseismic Scale 1998 (EMS-98). *Cahiers du Centre Européen de Géodynamique et de Séismologie* 15, Centre Européen de Géodynamique et de Séismologie, Luxembourg.
- Guérin-Marthe, S., Gehl, P., Fayjaloun, R., Negulescu, C., & Auclair, S. (2021). Rapid earthquake response: The state-of-the art and recommendations with a focus on European systems. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 52, 101958.
- Halldórsson, B., & Sigbjörnsson, R. (2009). The Mw6.3 Ölfus earthquake at 15:45 UTC on 29 May 2008 in South Iceland: ICEARRAY strong-motion recordings. *Soil Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering*, 29(6), 1073–1083.
- Hancilar, U., Tuzun, C., Yenidogan, C., Erdik, M., & Katz, O. (2010). ELER software--a new tool for urban earthquake loss assessment. *Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences*, 10(12).
- Hingorani, R., Tanner, P., Prieto, M., & Lara, C. (2020). Consequence classes and associated models for predicting loss of life in collapse of building structures. *Structural Safety*, 85. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.strusafe.2019.101910>.
- Hofer, L.; Zanini, M.A.; Gardoni, P. (2020). Risk-based catastrophe bond design for a spatially distributed portfolio. *Struct. Saf.*, 83, 101908, doi:10.1016/j.strusafe.2019.101908.

- Huang, C., & Darwiche, A. (1996). Inference in belief networks: A procedural guide. *International Journal of Approximate Reasoning*, 15(3), 225-263.
- Hwang, S. H., & Lignos, D. G. (2018). Nonmodel-based framework for rapid seismic risk and loss assessment of instrumented steel buildings. *Engineering Structures*, 156, 417-432.
- Im, S. B., Hurlbaeus, S., & Kang, Y. J. (2013). Summary review of GPS technology for structural health monitoring. *Journal of Structural Engineering*, 139(10), 1653-1664.
- Ioannou, I., Douglas, J., & Rossetto, T. (2015). Assessing the impact of ground-motion variability and uncertainty on empirical fragility curves. *Soil Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering*, 69, 83-92.
- Ioannou, I., Chandler, R. E., & Rossetto, T. (2020). Empirical fragility curves: the effect of uncertainty in ground motion intensity. *Soil Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering*, 129, 105908.
- Jaiswal, K. S., & Wald, D. J. (2010). Development of a semi-empirical loss model within the USGS Prompt Assessment of Global Earthquakes for Response (PAGER) system. *9th US National and 10th Canadian Conference on Earthquake Engineering*.
- Jaiswal, K., Wald, D., & Porter, K. (2010). A Global Building Inventory for Earthquake Loss Estimation and Risk Management. *Earthquake Spectra*.
- Jaiswal, K. S., Wald, D. J., Earle, P. S., Porter, K. A., & Hearne, M. (2011). Earthquake casualty models within the USGS Prompt Assessment of Global Earthquakes for Response (PAGER) system. In *Advances in Natural and Technological Hazards Research* (Vol. 29). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-90-481-9455-1_6
- Jayaram, N., & Baker, J. W. (2009). Correlation model for spatially distributed ground-motion intensities. *Earthquake Engineering & Structural Dynamics*, 38(15), 1687-1708.
- Jia, H., Lin, J., & Liu, J. (2019). An earthquake fatalities assessment method based on feature importance with deep learning and random forest models. *Sustainability* (Switzerland), 11(10). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11102727>.
- Julien-Laferrière, S. (2019). *Earthquake Qualitative Impact Assessment – Performance evaluation*.
- Kalakonas, P.; Silva, V.; Mouyiannou, A.; Rao, A. (2020). Exploring the impact of epistemic uncertainty on a regional probabilistic seismic risk assessment model. *Nat. Hazards*, 104, 997–1020, doi:10.1007/s11069-020-04201-7.
- Kalooop, M. R., Elbeltagi, E., Hu, J. W., & Elrefai, A. (2017). Recent advances of structures monitoring and evaluation using GPS-time series monitoring systems: A review. *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information*, 6(12), 382.

Kappos, A. J., Pitilakis, K., & Stylianidis, K. C. (1995). Cost-benefit analysis for the seismic rehabilitation of buildings in Thessaloniki, based on a hybrid method of vulnerability assessment. *Fifth International Conference on Seismic Zonation (Nice)*, 406–413.

Kullback, S., & Leibler, R. A. (1951). On information and sufficiency. *The annals of mathematical statistics*, 22(1), 79-86.

Lagomarsino, S., and Giovinazzi, S. (2006). Macroseismic and mechanical models for the vulnerability and damage assessment of current buildings. *Bull Earthquake Eng*, 4:415–443 DOI 10.1007/s10518-006-9024-z.

Lagomarsino, S., Cattari, S., Ottonelli, D., & Giovinazzi, S. (2019). Earthquake damage assessment of masonry churches: proposal for rapid and detailed forms and derivation of empirical vulnerability curves. *Bulletin of earthquake engineering*, 17(6), 3327-3364.

Lemnitzer, A., Massone, L. M., Skolnik, D. A., Juan, C., & Wallace, J. W. (2014). Aftershock response of RC buildings in Santiago, Chile, succeeding the magnitude 8.8 Maule earthquake. *Engineering structures*, 76, 324-338.

Lestuzzi, P., Podestà, S., Luchini, C., Garofano, A., Kazantzidou-Firtinidou, D., Bozzano, C., Bischof, P., Haffter, A., & Rouiller, J. D. (2016). Seismic vulnerability assessment at urban scale for two typical Swiss cities using Risk-UE methodology. *Natural Hazards*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11069-016-2420-z>.

Li, J., Xie, B., & Zhao, X. (2020). Measuring the interstory drift of buildings by a smartphone using a feature point matching algorithm. *Structural Control and Health Monitoring*, e2492.

Li, S., & Pozzi, M. (2019). What makes long-term monitoring convenient? A parametric analysis of value of information in infrastructure maintenance. *Structural Control and Health Monitoring*, 26(5), e2329.

Limongelli, M. P., Omenzetter, P., Yazgan, U., & Soyoz, S. (2017). Quantifying the value of monitoring for post-earthquake emergency management of bridges. *Proceedings of 39th IABSE Symposium—Engineering the Future*.

Limongelli, M. P., & Giordano, P. F. (2020). Vibration-based damage indicators: a comparison based on information entropy. *Journal of Civil Structural Health Monitoring*, 1-16.

Lin, K., Wald, D. J., Kircher, C. A., Slosky, D., Jaiswal, K., & Luco, N. (2018). USGS shakecast system advancements. *11th National Conference on Earthquake Engineering, NCEE 2018: Integrating Science, Engineering, and Policy*, 6, 3458–3468.

Long, L., Döhler, M., & Thöns, S. (2020). Determination of structural and damage detection system influencing parameters on the value of information. *Structural Health Monitoring*, 1475921719900918.

Lu, X., Zeng, X., Xu, Z., & Guan, H. (2018). Improving the Accuracy of Near Real-Time Seismic Loss Estimation Using Post-Earthquake Remote Sensing Images. *Earthquake Spectra*, 34(3), 1219-1245.

Lunn, D., Spiegelhalter, D., Thomas, A. and Best, N. (2009) The BUGS project: Evolution, critique and future directions (with discussion), *Statistics in Medicine* 28: 3049-3082.

Mackie, K. R., & Stojadinović, B. (2005). Comparison of incremental dynamic, cloud, and stripe methods for computing probabilistic seismic demand models. *Proceedings of Structures Congress 2005: Metropolis and Beyond* (pp. 1-11).

Maiwald, H., Schwarz, J. (2020). Simulative Erdbebenschadensmodellierung auf Grundlage der EMS-98 – Realitätsnähe und Prognosetauglichkeit. *Ernst & Sohn Verlag für Architektur und technische Wissenschaften GmbH & Co. KG, Berlin. Bautechnik* 97 (2020), Heft 4.

Makhoul, N., & Argyroudis, S. (2018). Loss Estimation Software: Developments, Limitations and Future Needs. *16th European Conference on Earthquake Engineering*.

Manchuel, K.; Traversa, P.; Baumont, D.; Cara, M.; Nayman, E.; Durouchoux, C. (2017). The French seismic CATalogue (FCAT-17). *Bull. Earthq. Eng.*, 16, 2227–2251, doi:10.1007/s10518-017-0236-1.

Maqsood, S. T., & Schwarz, J. (2011). Estimation of human casualties from earthquakes in Pakistan - An engineering approach. *Seismological Research Letters*, 82(1). <https://doi.org/10.1785/gssrl.82.1.32>.

Martins, L., & Silva, V. (2020). Development of a fragility and vulnerability model for global seismic risk analyses. *Bulletin of Earthquake Engineering*, 1-27.

McKenna F, Fenves GL, Scott MH. OpenSees: open system for earthquake engineering simulation. Berkeley (CA): Pacific Earthquake Engineering Center, University of California; 2006.

Medvedev, S. V., & Sponheuer, W. (1969). Scale of Seismic Intensity. *Proc. IV World Conference of the Earthquake Engineering*.

Michellini, A., Faenza, L., Lauciani, V., & Malagnini, L. (2008). ShakeMap implementation in Italy. *Seismological Research Letters*, 79(5), 688-697.

Midorikawa, S. (2005). Dense strong-motion array in Yokohama, Japan, and its use for disaster management. In *Directions in strong motion instrumentation* (pp. 197–208). Springer, Dordrecht.

Molina, S., Lang, D.H., Lindholm, C.D. (2010). SELENA – An open-source tool for seismic risk and loss assessment using a logic tree computation procedure, *Computers & Geosciences*, Volume 36, Issue 3, 2010, Pages 257-269, ISSN 0098-3004, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cageo.2009.07.006>.

Milutinovic, Z., & Trendafiloski, G. (2003). Risk-UE - An advanced approach to earthquake risk scenarios with applications to different European towns. *Report to WP4: Vulnerability of Current Buildings*.

Moehle, J., & Deierlein, G. G. (2004). A framework methodology for performance-based earthquake engineering. In *13th world conference on earthquake engineering* (Vol. 679).

Monfort, D.; Roullé, A. (2016). Estimation statistique de la répartition des classes de sol Eurocode 8 sur le territoire français. Phase 1. Rapport final. *Rapport BRGM/RP-66250-FR*, 48p., 14 fig., 7 tab., 1 ann.

Monfort, D.; Negulescu, C.; Roulle, A.; Colas, B.; Lantada, N.; Valcarcel, J.; Rodriguez, J.; Pujades, L.; Barbat, A.; Irizarry, J.; et al. (2012). Seismic risk scenarios in a cross-border zone of the Pyrenees Pyrenees. In *Proceedings of the 15th World Conference on Earthquake Engineering (WCEE)*, September 2012.

Murphy, K. (2001). The Bayes net toolbox for Matlab. *Computing Science and Statistics*, 33, 1024-1034.

Negulescu, C.; Benaïchouche, A.; Lemoine, A.; Le Roy, S.; Pedreros, R. (2020). Adjustability of exposed elements by updating their capacity for resistance after a damaging event: Application to an earthquake–tsunami cascade scenario. *Nat. Hazards*, 104, 753–793, doi:10.1007/s11069-020-04189-0.

Ozer, E. (2016). *Multisensory Smartphone Applications in Vibration-Based Structural Health Monitoring* (Doctoral dissertation, Columbia University).

Ozer, E., & Feng, M. Q. (2016). Synthesizing spatiotemporally sparse smartphone sensor data for bridge modal identification. *Smart Materials and Structures*, 25(8), 085007.

Ozer, E., & Feng, M. Q. (2017). Direction-sensitive smart monitoring of structures using heterogeneous smartphone sensor data and coordinate system transformation. *Smart Materials and Structures*, 26(4), 045026.

Ozer, E., Feng, D., & Feng, M. Q. (2017). Hybrid motion sensing and experimental modal analysis using collocated smartphone camera and accelerometers. *Measurement Science and Technology*, 28(10), 105903.

Padgett, J. E., Dennemann, K., & Ghosh, J. (2010). Risk-based seismic life-cycle cost–benefit (LCC-B) analysis for bridge retrofit assessment. *Structural Safety*, 32(3), 165-173.

Park, J., P. Bazzurro, and J. W. Baker (2007). Modeling spatial correlation of ground motion intensity measures for regional seismic hazard and portfolio loss estimation, *Proc. of the 10th International Conf. on Applied Statistics and Probability*, Tokyo, Japan, 31 July–3 August 2007.

Parvin, A., & Ma, Z. (2001). The use of helical spring and fluid damper isolation systems for bridge structures subjected to vertical ground acceleration. *Electronic Journal of Structural Engineering*, 1(2), 98-110.

Pittore, M.; Haas, M.; Silva, V. (2020). Variable resolution probabilistic modeling of residential exposure and vulnerability for risk applications. *Earthq. Spectra*, 36, 321–344, doi:10.1177/8755293020951582.

Polese, M.; D'Aragona, M.G.; Prota, A. (2019). Simplified approach for building inventory and seismic damage assessment at the territorial scale: An application for a town in southern Italy. *Soil Dyn. Earthq. Eng.*, 121, 405–420, doi:10.1016/j.soildyn.2019.03.028.

Porter, K. A. (2003). An overview of PEER's performance-based earthquake engineering methodology. In: *Proceedings of ninth international conference on applications of statistics and probability in civil engineering*, 2003.

Porter, K. A. (2004). A survey of bridge practitioners to relate damage to closure. *Report No. EERL 2004-07*, California Institute of Technology, Pasadena, CA.

Porter, K., Mitrani-Reiser, J., & Beck, J. L. (2006). Near-real-time loss estimation for instrumented buildings. *The Structural Design of Tall and Special Buildings*, 15(1), 3-20.

Porter, K. A., Jaiswal, K. S., Wald, D. J., Earle, P. S., & Hearne, M. (2008). Fatality models for the U.S. Geological Survey's Prompt Assessment of Global Earthquakes for Response (PAGER) system. *The 14th World Conference on Earthquake Engineering*.

Pozzi, M., & Der Kiureghian, A. (2013). Gaussian Bayesian network for reliability analysis of a system of bridges. In *Proc. of the 11th International Conf. on Structural Safety and Reliability*, New York, United States.

Rahpeyma, S., Halldorsson, B., Olivera, C., Green, R. A., & Jonsson, S. (2016). Detailed site effect estimation in the presence of strong velocity reversals within a small-aperture strong-motion array in Iceland. *Soil Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering*, 89, 136-151.

Reynders, E., Wursten, G., & De Roeck, G. (2014). Output-only structural health monitoring in changing environmental conditions by means of nonlinear system identification. *Structural Health Monitoring*, 13(1), 82-93.

RISK-UE (2004). *An advanced approach to earthquake risk scenarios, with application to different European towns*. Contract : EVK4-CT-2000-00014.

Roullé, A.; Macau, A.; Figueras, S.; Monfort, D.; Lantada, N.; Susagna, T.; Irizarry, J. (2012). Performing seismic scenarios in the Luchon-Val d'Aran area, Central Pyrenees. In *Proceedings of the 7th European Congress on Regional GEOScientific Cartography and Information Systems: 7th EUROGEO*, June 2012.

Ruiz-García, J., & Miranda, E. (2010). Probabilistic estimation of residual drift demands for seismic assessment of multi-story framed buildings. *Engineering Structures*, 32(1), 11-20.

Ruiz-García, J., & Chora, C. (2015). Evaluation of approximate methods to estimate residual drift demands in steel framed buildings. *Earthquake Engineering & Structural Dynamics*, 44(15), 2837-2854.

Rupakhety, R., & Sigbjörnsson, R. (2013). Rotation-invariant measures of earthquake response spectra. *Bulletin of Earthquake Engineering*, 11(6), 1885-1893.

Rupakhety, R., Sigbjörnsson, R., & Ólafsson, S. (2016). Damage to residential buildings in Hveragerði during the 2008 Ölfus Earthquake: simulated and surveyed results. *Bulletin of Earthquake Engineering*, 14(7), 1945-1955.

Sæmundsson, K., & Kristinsson, S. H. (2005). Soil temperature measurements and faults. *Reykjavík, Iceland (in Icelandic): Iceland GeoSurvey (ÍSOR)*.

Schiappapietra, E., & Douglas, J. (2020). Modelling the spatial correlation of earthquake ground motion: Insights from the literature, data from the 2016–2017 Central Italy earthquake sequence and ground-motion simulations. *Earth-Science Reviews*, 103139.

Schwarz, J., Abrahamczyk, L., Hadidian, N., Haweyou, M., Kaufmann, C. (2021). Report on Knowledge-based exposure modelling framework depending on the accuracy and completeness of available data. TURNkey Deliverable Report D4.1.

Scott, M.H. and Fenves, G.L. (2006), Plastic Hinge Integration Methods for Force-Based Beam-Column Elements, *J. Struct. Eng-ASCE*, 132(2), 244-252.

Scotti, O., Baumont, D., Quenet, G.; Levret, A. (2004). The French macroseismic database SISFRANCE: Objectives, results and perspectives. *Ann. Geophys.*

Scozzese, F., Tubaldi, E., & Dall'Asta, A. (2020). Assessment of the effectiveness of Multiple-Stripe Analysis by using a stochastic earthquake input model. *Bulletin of Earthquake Engineering*, 1-37.

Sedan, O.; Terrier, M.; Negulescu, C.; Winter, T.; Roullé, A.; Douglas, J.; Rohmer, J.; Bes-de-Berc, S.; De Martin, F.; Arnal, C.; et al. (2008). Scénario départemental de risque sismique-Méthodologie et processus de réalisation. *Rapport BRGM/RP-55415-FR*, 459p, 96 fig., 45 tabl., 25 annexes., France.

Sedan, O., Negulescu, C., Terrier, M., Roullé, A., Winter, T., & Bertil, D. (2013). Armagedom — A Tool for Seismic Risk Assessment Illustrated with Applications. *Journal of Earthquake Engineering*, 17:2, 253-281, DOI: 10.1080/13632469.2012.726604.

Shahbazi, P.; Mansouri, B.; Ghafory-Ashtiany, M.; Käser, M. (2020). Introducing loss transfer functions to model seismic financial loss: A case study of Iran. *Int. J. Disaster Risk Reduct.*, 51, 101883, doi:10.1016/j.ijdr.2020.101883.

Shannon, C. E. (1948). A mathematical theory of communication. *The Bell system technical journal*, 27(3), 379-423.

Shimizu, Y., Yamazaki, F., Isoyama, R., Ishida, E., Koganemaru, K., & Nakayama, W. (2004). Development of realtime disaster mitigation system for urban gas supply network. *13th World Conference on Earthquake Engineering*.

Silva, V. (2016). Critical Issues in Earthquake Scenario Loss Modeling. *J. Earthq. Eng.*, 20, 1322–1341, doi:10.1080/13632469.2016.1138172.

Silva, V. (2019). Uncertainty and correlation in seismic vulnerability functions of building classes. *Earthquake Spectra*, 35(4), 1515-1539.

Silva, V, Crowley, H., Pagani, M., Monelli, D., & Pinho, R. (2012). Development and application of OpenQuake, an open source software for seismic risk assessment. *15th World Conference on Earthquake Engineering, Lisbon, Portugal*.

Silva, V.; Amo-Oduro, D.; Calderon, A.; Costa, C.Q.M.; Dabbeek, J.; Despotaki, V.; Martins, L.; Pagani, M.; Rao, A.; Simionato, M.; et al. (2020). Development of a global seismic risk model. *Earthq. Spectra*, 36, 372–394, doi:10.1177/8755293019899953.

Siringoringo, D. M., & Fujino, Y. (2018). Lateral stability of vehicles crossing a bridge during an earthquake. *Journal of Bridge Engineering*, 23(4), 04018012.

Soyoz, S., & Feng, M. Q. (2008). Instantaneous damage detection of bridge structures and experimental verification. *Structural Control and Health Monitoring*, 15(7), 958-973.

Spence, R. (2007). *LESSLOSS Report 2007/07: Earthquake Disaster Scenario Predictions and Loss Modelling for Urban Areas*.

Spencer Jr, B. F., Ruiz-Sandoval, M. E., & Kurata, N. (2004). Smart sensing technology: opportunities and challenges. *Structural Control and Health Monitoring*, 11(4), 349-368.

Stafford, P. J. (2012). Evaluation of structural performance in the immediate aftermath of an earthquake: A case study of the 2011 Christchurch earthquake. *International Journal of Forensic Engineering*, 1(1), 58-77.

Tang, B., Chen, Q., Liu, X., Liu, Z., Liu, Y., Dong, J., & Zhang, L. (2019). Rapid estimation of earthquake fatalities in China using an empirical regression method. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 41. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdr.2019.101306>.

Tapia, M. (2006). *Desarrollo Y Aplicación de Métodos Avanzados Para La Caracterización de La Respuesta Sísmica Del Suelo a Escala Regional Y Local*. PhD thesis, Universidad Politécnica de Catalunya, Barcelona, Spain.

Thöns, S. (2018). On the value of monitoring information for the structural integrity and risk management. *Computer-Aided Civil and Infrastructure Engineering*, 33(1), 79-94.

Tien, I., & Der Kiureghian, A. (2016). Algorithms for Bayesian network modeling and reliability assessment of infrastructure systems. *Reliability Engineering & System Safety*, 156, 134-147.

Tien, I., & Der Kiureghian, A. (2017). Reliability assessment of critical infrastructure using Bayesian networks. *Journal of Infrastructure Systems*, 23(4), 04017025.

Toma-Danila, D., Ciaflan, C. O., Ionescu, C., & Tigianescu, A. (2018). The near real-time system for estimating the seismic damage in Romania (SeisDaRo). Recent upgrades and results. *16th European Conference on Earthquake Engineering*.

Trapani, D. (2015). *A monitoring method for after-earthquake damage evaluation of buildings* (Doctoral dissertation, University of Trento).

Trapani, D., Maroni, A., Debiassi, E., & Zonta, D. (2015, July). Uncertainty evaluation of after-earthquake damage detection strategy. *Proceedings of the 2015 IEEE Workshop on Environmental, Energy, and Structural Monitoring Systems (EESMS)* (pp. 125-130).

Trendafiloski, G., Wyss, M., & Rosset, P. (2011). Loss estimation module in the second generation software QLARM. In *Human Casualties in Earthquakes* (pp. 95-106). Springer, Dordrecht.

Tubaldi E, Barbato M, Dall'Asta A. (2010). Transverse seismic response of continuous steel-concrete composite bridges exhibiting dual load path. *Earthquake Struct*; 1(1): 21-41.

Tubaldi, E., Barbato, M., & Dall'Asta, A. (2012). Influence of model parameter uncertainty on seismic transverse response and vulnerability of steel-concrete composite bridges with dual load path. *Journal of Structural Engineering*, 138(3), 363-374.

Tubaldi, E., Dall'Asta, A., & Dezi, L. (2013). Reduced formulation for post-elastic seismic response of dual load path bridges. *Engineering structures*, 51, 178-187.

Tubaldi, E., Freddi, F., & Barbato, M. (2016). Probabilistic seismic demand model for pounding risk assessment. *Earthquake Engineering & Structural Dynamics*, 45(11), 1743-1758.

Tubaldi, E., Ozer, E., Douglas, J., & Gehl, P. (2021). Examining the contribution of near real-time data for rapid seismic loss assessment of structures. *Structural Health Monitoring*, 1475921721996218.

Uma, S. R., Pampanin, S., & Christopoulos, C. (2010). Development of probabilistic framework for performance-based seismic assessment of structures considering residual deformations. *Journal of Earthquake Engineering*, 14(7), 1092-1111.

Vamvatsikos, D., & Cornell, C. A. (2002). Incremental dynamic analysis. *Earthquake Engineering & Structural Dynamics*, 31(3), 491-514.

Vanmarcke, E. (1983). *Random Fields, Analysis and Synthesis*. The MIT Press, Cambridge, Massachusetts.

Wald, D., Lin, K. W., Porter, K., & Turner, L. (2008a). ShakeCast: Automating and improving the use of ShakeMap for post-earthquake decision-making and response. *Earthquake Spectra*, 24(2), 533-553.

Wald, D. J., Lin, K. W., & Quitoriano, V. (2008b). *Quantifying and qualifying USGS ShakeMap uncertainty* (p. 26). US Geological Survey.

Wald, D., Jaiswal, K., Marano, K. D., Bausch, D. B., & Hearne, M. G. (2010). *PAGER — Rapid assessment of an earthquake's impact*.

Wald, D. J., Quitoriano, V., Worden, B., Hopper, M., & Dewey, J. W. (2011). USGS "Did You Feel It?" internet-based macroseismic intensity maps. *Annals of Geophysics*, 54(6). <https://doi.org/10.4401/ag-5354>.

Whitman, R. V., Anagnos, T., Kircher, C. A., Lagorio, H. J., Lawson, R. S., & Schneider, P. (1997). Development of a national earthquake loss estimation methodology. *Earthquake Spectra*. <https://doi.org/10.1193/1.1585973>.

Woessner J, Danciu L, Kaestli P, Monelli D. Database of seismogenic zones, Mmax, earthquake activity rates, ground motion attenuation relations and associated logic trees. *FP7 SHARE project deliverable D6.6*; 2013.

Worden, C. B., Thompson, E. M., Baker, J. W., Bradley, B. A., Luco, N., & Wald, D. J. (2018). Spatial and spectral interpolation of ground - motion intensity measure observations. *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America*, 108(2), 866-875.

Wu, S. (2014). *Future of Earthquake Early Warning: Quantifying Uncertainty and Making Fast Automated Decisions for Applications* (Doctoral dissertation, California Institute of Technology).

Yazgan, U., & Dazio, A. (2012). Post-earthquake damage assessment using residual displacements. *Earthquake engineering & structural dynamics*, 41(8), 1257-1276.

Yeh, C. H., Loh, C. H., & Tsai, K. C. (2006). Overview of Taiwan earthquake loss estimation system. *Natural Hazards*, 37(1–2), 23–37.

Yetitmoves (2020) Displayce, Science for a safer land, IoT Solution for Monitoring and Early Warning of Displacements. Available online at : <http://yetitmoves.it/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/DISPLAYCE-en.pdf> (accessed on 12 October 2020).

Yi, T., Li, H., & Gu, M. (2010). Recent research and applications of GPS based technology for bridge health monitoring. *Science China Technological Sciences*, 53(10), 2597-2610.

Yi, T. H., Li, H. N., & Gu, M. (2013). Recent research and applications of GPS-based monitoring technology for high-rise structures. *Structural Control and Health Monitoring*, 20(5), 649-670.

Zhang, Q., & Alam, M. S. (2019). Performance-based seismic design of bridges: a global perspective and critical review of past, present and future directions. *Structure and Infrastructure Engineering*, 15(4), 539-554.

Zonta, D., Glisic, B., & Adriaenssens, S. (2014a). Value of information: impact of monitoring on decision-making. *Structural Control and Health Monitoring*, 21(7), 1043-1056.

Zonta, D., Cappello, C., Pozzi, M., & Glisic, B. (2014b). On evaluating monitoring design effectiveness. In *EWSHM-7th European Workshop on Structural Health Monitoring*.

Zülfikar, C., Fercan, N. O. Z., Tunc, S., & Erdik, M. (2017). Real-time earthquake shake, damage, and loss mapping for Istanbul metropolitan area. *Earth, Planets and Space*, 69(1).

APPENDIX I: Fragility functions assignment to Luchon Valley

Table A-1: Assigned fragility functions to Luchon Valley building types.

No.	SERA Taxonomy	Assigned fragility functions (Refer to Table A4-3 in Deliverable 4.1 for the details for every function).		
		Most suitable	Still suitable	Less (or not) suitable
1	CR+PC/LWAL+CDN/HBET:3-5		FFRC5_L-10	
2	CR/LDUAL+CDM/HBET:6-		FFRC3_L-23,FFRC3_L-25,FFRC3_L-27,FFRC3_L-29,FFRC3_L-30,FFRC3_L-32,FFRC3_L-5,FFRC3_L-8,FFRC3_L-11,FFRC3_L-14,FFRC3_L-17,FFRC3_L-20,FFRC3_L-1,FFRC3_L-2,FFRC3_L-3,FFRC3_L-31	
3	CR/LDUAL+CDN/HBET:6-			FFRC3_L-36,FFRC3_L-37,FFRC3_L-39,FFRC3_L-40
4	CR+PC/LWAL+CDN/HBET:6-		FFRC5_L-10	
5	CR/LFINF+CDL/H:1	FFRC1_L-94,FFRC1_L-97		
6	CR/LFINF+CDM/H:2		FFRC1_L-145,FFRC1_L-87,FFRC1_L-95,FFRC1_L-98,FFRC1_L-103,FFRC1_L-133	
7	CR/LFINF+CDL/H:2	FFRC1_L-94,FFRC1_L-97		
8	W/LWAL+CDN/H:1			FFTimber-1,FFTimber-2,FFTimber-3,FFTimber-4
9	CR/LFINF+CDN/HBET:3-5		FFRC1_L-146,FFRC1_L-88	
10	CR/LFINF+CDM/H:1		FFRC1_L-145,FFRC1_L-87,FFRC1_L-95,FFRC1_L-98,FFRC1_L-103,FFRC1_L-133	
11	MUR+ST/LWAL+CDN/H:2	FFM3-6,FFM3-7		
12	CR/LDUAL+CDL/HBET:3-5	FFRC3_L-1,FFRC3_L-24,FFRC3_L-2,FFRC3_L-26,FFRC3_L-3,FFRC3_L-28,FFRC3_L-31		
13	MUR+CL/LWAL+CDN/H:2			FFM5-10,FFM5-9
14	CR/LDUAL+CDM/HBET:3-5		FFRC3_L-5,FFRC3_L-8,FFRC3_L-11,FFRC3_L-14,FFRC3_L-17,FFRC3_L-20,FFRC3_L-31,FFRC3_L-23,FFRC3_L-25,FFRC3_L-27,FFRC3_L-29,FFRC3_L-30,FFRC3_L-32	
15	W/LWAL+CDN/H:2			FFTimber-1,FFTimber-2,FFTimber-3,FFTimber-4
16	CR/LFLS+CDN/HBET:6-			FFRC1_L-93,FFRC1_L-95,FFRC1_L-96,FFRC1_L-98,FFRC1_L-99,FFRC1_L-100,FFRC1_L-101,FFRC1_L-102,FFRC1_L-104
17	MUR+CL/LWAL+CDN/H:1			FFM5-10,FFM5-9
18	CR/LDUAL+CDL/HBET:6-	FFRC3_L-23,FFRC3_L-24,FFRC3_L-25,FFRC3_L-26,FFRC3_L-27,FFRC3_L-28,FFRC3_L-29,FFRC3_L-30,FFRC3_L-32		
19	MUR+ST/LWAL+CDN/H:1	FFM3-6,FFM3-7		
20	CR/LFLS+CDM/HBET:3-5			FFRC1_M-5,FFRC1_M-6,FFRC1_L-120,FFRC1_M-9,FFRC1_M-10,FFRC1_M-26
21	CR/LFLS+CDL/HBET:3-5			FFRC1_L-94,FFRC1_L-95,FFRC1_L-97,FFRC1_L-98,FFRC1_L-9,FFRC1_L-100,FFRC1_L-103
22	MCF/LWAL+CDL/H:2		FFM7-4	
23	CR+PC/LWAL+CDN/H:2			FFRC5_L-10
24	MCF/LWAL+CDL/H:1		FFM7-4	
25	CR/LFLS+CDN/HBET:3-5			FFRC1_L-94,FFRC1_L-95,FFRC1_L-97,FFRC1_L-98,FFRC1_L-9,FFRC1_L-100,FFRC1_L-103

No.	SERA Taxonomy	Assigned fragility functions (Refer to Table A4-3 in Deliverable 4.1 for the details for every function).		
		Most suitable	Still suitable	Less (or not) suitable
26	CR/LDUAL+CDM/HBET:6-		FFRC3_L-23,FFRC3_L-25,FFRC3_L-27,FFRC3_L-29,FFRC3_L-30,FFRC3_L-32,FFRC3_L-5,FFRC3_L-8,FFRC3_L-11,FFRC3_L-14,FFRC3_L-17,FFRC3_L-20,FFRC3_L-1,FFRC3_L-2,FFRC3_L-3,FFRC3_L-31	
27	CR/LDUAL+CDM/HBET:3-5		FFRC3_L-5,FFRC3_L-8,FFRC3_L-11,FFRC3_L-14,FFRC3_L-17,FFRC3_L-20,FFRC3_L-31,FFRC3_L-23,FFRC3_L-25,FFRC3_L-27,FFRC3_L-29,FFRC3_L-30,FFRC3_L-32	
28	CR/LFINF+CDM/H:1		FFRC1_L-145,FFRC1_L-87,FFRC1_L-95,FFRC1_L-98,FFRC1_L-103,FFRC1_L-133	
29	CR/LFINF+CDM/H:2		FFRC1_L-145,FFRC1_L-87,FFRC1_L-95,FFRC1_L-98,FFRC1_L-103,FFRC1_L-133	
30	CR/LFINF+CDL/H:2	FFRC1_L-94,FFRC1_L-97		
31	CR/LDUAL+CDL/HBET:6-	FFRC3_L-23,FFRC3_L-24,FFRC3_L-25,FFRC3_L-26,FFRC3_L-27,FFRC3_L-28,FFRC3_L-29,FFRC3_L-30,FFRC3_L-32		
32	CR/LFINF+CDM/H:1		FFRC1_L-145,FFRC1_L-87,FFRC1_L-95,FFRC1_L-98,FFRC1_L-103,FFRC1_L-133	
33	CR/LDUAL+CDM/HBET:6-		FFRC3_L-23,FFRC3_L-25,FFRC3_L-27,FFRC3_L-29,FFRC3_L-30,FFRC3_L-32,FFRC3_L-5,FFRC3_L-8,FFRC3_L-11,FFRC3_L-14,FFRC3_L-17,FFRC3_L-20,FFRC3_L-1,FFRC3_L-2,FFRC3_L-3,FFRC3_L-31	
34	CR/LFINF+CDM/H:2		FFRC1_L-145,FFRC1_L-87,FFRC1_L-95,FFRC1_L-98,FFRC1_L-103,FFRC1_L-133	
35	CR/LDUAL+CDM/HBET:3-5		FFRC3_L-5,FFRC3_L-8,FFRC3_L-11,FFRC3_L-14,FFRC3_L-17,FFRC3_L-20,FFRC3_L-31,FFRC3_L-23,FFRC3_L-25,FFRC3_L-27,FFRC3_L-29,FFRC3_L-30,FFRC3_L-32	
36	CR/LDUAL+CDL/HBET:3-5	FFRC3_L-1,FFRC3_L-24,FFRC3_L-2,FFRC3_L-26,FFRC3_L-3,FFRC3_L-28,FFRC3_L-31		
37	CR/LFINF+CDL/H:1	FFRC1_L-94		
38	CR/LFLS+CDL/HBET:3-5			FFRC1_L-94,FFRC1_L-95,FFRC1_L-97,FFRC1_L-98,FFRC1_L-9,FFRC1_L-100,FFRC1_L-103
39	MCF/LWAL+CDN/H:1		FFM7-5	
40	MCF/LWAL+CDN/H:2		FFM7-5	
41	CR/LDUAL+CDL/HBET:3-5	FFRC3_L-1,FFRC3_L-24,FFRC3_L-2,FFRC3_L-26,FFRC3_L-3,FFRC3_L-28,FFRC3_L-31		
42	CR/LFINF+CDM/H:2		FFRC1_L-145,FFRC1_L-87,FFRC1_L-95,FFRC1_L-98,FFRC1_L-103,FFRC1_L-133	
43	CR/LFINF+CDL/H:2	FFRC1_L-94		

Table A-2: Assigned structural types for Luchon based on M2-TX-ST method (see Figure 3.3, D4.1)

Id	ID	SERA			RISKUE	Vi	Vi+code	EMS-98 type *
1	CR+PC/LWAL+CDN/HBET:3-5	CR+PC	LWAL	CDN	RC6	0.544	0.564	Frame with moderate level of ERD
2	CR/LDUAL+CDM/HBET:6-/7.0	CR	LDUAL	CDM	RC4	0.386	0.446	Frame with moderate level of ERD
3	CR/LDUAL+CDN/HBET:6-	CR	LDUAL	CDN	RC4	0.386	0.446	Frame with moderate level of ERD
4	CR+PC/LWAL+CDN/HBET:6-	CR+PC	LWAL	CDN	RC6	0.544	0.604	Frame with moderate level of ERD
5	CR/LFINF+CDL/H:1/4.0	CR	LFINF	CDL	RC3.2	0.522	0.662	Frame with moderate level of ERD
6	CR/LFINF+CDM/H:2/7.0	CR	LFINF	CDM	RC3.2	0.522	0.502	Frame with moderate level of ERD
7	CR/LFINF+CDL/H:2/4.0	CR	LFINF	CDL	RC3.2	0.522	0.662	Frame with moderate level of ERD
8	W/LWAL+CDN/H:1	W	LWAL	CDN	W	0.447	0.427	Timber structure
9	CR/LFINF+CDN/HBET:3-5	CR	LFINF	CDN	RC3.2	0.522	0.542	Frame with moderate level of ERD
10	CR/LFINF+CDM/H:1/7.0	CR	LFINF	CDM	RC3.2	0.522	0.502	Frame with moderate level of ERD
11	MUR+ST/LWAL+CDN/H:2	MUR+ST	LWAL	CDN	M1.1	0.873	0.853	Rubble stone, Field stone
12	CR/LDUAL+CDL/HBET:3-5/4.0	CR	LDUAL	CDL	RC4	0.386	0.566	Walls with moderate level of ERD
13	MUR+CL/LWAL+CDN/H:2	MUR+CL	LWAL	CDN	M1.2	0.74	0.72	Simple stone
14	CR/LDUAL+CDM/HBET:3-5/7.0	CR	LDUAL	CDM	RC4	0.386	0.406	Walls with high level of ERD
15	W/LWAL+CDN/H:2	W	LWAL	CDN	W	0.447	0.427	Timber structure
16	CR/LFLS+CDN/HBET:6-	CR	LFLS	CDN	RC1	0.442	0.502	Frame with moderate level of ERD
17	MUR+CL/LWAL+CDN/H:1	MUR+CL	LWAL	CDN	M1.2	0.74	0.72	Simple stone
18	CR/LDUAL+CDL/HBET:6-/4.0	CR	LDUAL	CDL	RC4	0.386	0.606	Walls with moderate level of ERD
19	MUR+ST/LWAL+CDN/H:1	MUR+ST	LWAL	CDN	M1.1	0.873	0.853	Rubble stone, Field stone
20	CR/LFLS+CDM/HBET:3-5/7.0	CR	LFLS	CDM	RC1	0.442	0.462	Frame with moderate level of ERD
21	CR/LFLS+CDL/HBET:3-5/4.0	CR	LFLS	CDL	RC1	0.442	0.622	Frame with moderate level of ERD
22	MCF/LWAL+CDL/H:2	MCF	LWAL	CDL	RC2	0.386	0.526	Reinforced or confined masonry
23	CR+PC/LWAL+CDN/H:2	CR+PC	LWAL	CDN	RC6	0.544	0.524	Frame with moderate level of ERD
24	MCF/LWAL+CDL/H:1	MCF	LWAL	CDL	RC2	0.386	0.526	Reinforced or confined masonry
25	CR/LFLS+CDN/HBET:3-5	CR	LFLS	CDN	RC1	0.442	0.462	Frame with moderate level of ERD
26	CR/LDUAL+CDM/HBET:6-/4.0	CR	LDUAL	CDM	RC4	0.386	0.446	Walls with high level of ERD
27	CR/LDUAL+CDM/HBET:3-5/4.0	CR	LDUAL	CDM	RC4	0.386	0.406	Walls with high level of ERD
28	CR/LFINF+CDM/H:1/4.0	CR	LFINF	CDM	RC3.2	0.522	0.502	Frame with moderate level of ERD
29	CR/LFINF+CDM/H:2/4.0	CR	LFINF	CDM	RC3.2	0.522	0.502	Frame with moderate level of ERD
30	CR/LFINF+CDL/H:2/8.0	CR	LFINF	CDL	RC3.2	0.522	0.662	Frame with moderate level of ERD
31	CR/LDUAL+CDL/HBET:6-/8.0	CR	LDUAL	CDL	RC4	0.386	0.606	Walls with moderate level of ERD
32	CR/LFINF+CDM/H:1/11.0	CR	LFINF	CDM	RC3.2	0.522	0.502	Frame with moderate level of ERD
33	CR/LDUAL+CDM/HBET:6-/11.0	CR	LDUAL	CDM	RC4	0.386	0.446	Walls with high level of ERD

Id	ID	SERA			RISKUE	Vi	Vi+code	EMS-98 type *
34	CR/LFINF+CDM/H:2/11.0	CR	LFINF	CDM	RC3.2	0.522	0.502	Frame with moderate level of ERD
35	CR/LDUAL+CDM/HBET:3-5/11.0	CR	LDUAL	CDM	RC4	0.386	0.406	Walls with high level of ERD
36	CR/LDUAL+CDL/HBET:3-5/8.0	CR	LDUAL	CDL	RC4	0.386	0.566	Walls with moderate level of ERD
37	CR/LFINF+CDL/H:1/8.0	CR	LFINF	CDL	RC3.2	0.522	0.662	Frame with moderate level of ERD
38	CR/LFLS+CDL/HBET:3-5/0.0	CR	LFLS	CDL	RC1	0.442	0.622	Frame with moderate level of ERD
39	MCF/LWAL+CDN/H:1	MCF	LWAL	CDN	RC2	0.386	0.366	Reinforced or confined masonry
40	MCF/LWAL+CDN/H:2	MCF	LWAL	CDN	RC2	0.386	0.366	Reinforced or confined masonry
41	CR/LDUAL+CDL/HBET:3-5/0.0	CR	LDUAL	CDL	RC4	0.386	0.566	Walls with moderate level of ERD
42	CR/LFINF+CDM/H:2/0.0	CR	LFINF	CDM	RC3.2	0.522	0.502	Frame with moderate level of ERD
43	CR/LFINF+CDL/H:2/0.0	CR	LFINF	CDL	RC3.2	0.522	0.662	Frame with moderate level of ERD

Explanations: * EMS-98 types: see tables A4-4 to A4-7 in D4.1.